

THE UNIVERSITY OF READING

**A Study of the Tropical Response
in an Idealised Global Circulation
Model**

Richard Brian Neale

A Thesis Submitted for the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy
Department of Meteorology

May 1999

IMAGING SERVICES NORTH

Boston Spa, Wetherby
West Yorkshire, LS23 7BQ
www.bl.uk

BEST COPY AVAILABLE.

VARIABLE PRINT QUALITY

Abstract

The atmospheric response to idealised Sea Surface Temperature (SST) distributions is investigated using an atmosphere only version of the UKMO Unified Model (UM), which is modified to have an underlying ocean covered surface. The study is motivated by the observational analysis of Ward (1993) who found a Tropic Wide Mode of climate variability linked to variations in tropical SST.

The model climate exhibits strong sensitivity to meridional curvature in SST. For sufficiently weak near-equator SST gradients there is no Hadley circulation and tropical precipitation is no longer organised by large-scale dynamics.

Localised tropical SST anomalies give precipitation increases centred to the west of them. The pattern of precipitation suppression seen is consistent with a tropically confined wave response. Tropical precipitation suppression remote from the SST anomaly is accompanied by a lowering of the cloud top height and a weakening of the Hadley circulation. Intense equatorial westerlies remote from an SST anomaly result due to stationary eddy momentum flux convergence in the horizontal and vertical.

A wavenumber-frequency analysis of model tropical precipitation reveals that the intra-seasonal oscillation is absent from this configuration of the UM. The introduction of zonal non-uniformity due to SST anomalies reduces the magnitude of significant spectral peaks.

Decoupling of SST from the near-surface temperature in the UM restricts a simple boundary layer model when used to reproduce the strength of the UM flow. An intermediate GCM based upon quasi-equilibrium shows a sensitivity to SST significantly different from the UM. The simple dynamical formulation of this model effectively removes the constraint of local angular momentum conservation seen in the UM.

Idealised GCM experimentation is useful in clearly identifying model differences, testing model parameterisations and their interaction with the dynamics, and may provide a bridge between single column models and full GCMs.

Acknowledgements

I would first like to thank my supervisors Brian Hoskins and Mike Davey. Not least for their expert guidance and supervision but also for their assistance in the considerable improvement of my bowling average and navigation of what not to eat at the Met. Office canteen respectively. I also acknowledge the financial support of NERC and the Met. Office. without which I wouldn't have eaten.

On the technical side thanks go to Colin Jones and Roger Brugge for help with Unified Model related problems and John Holden for his TeXperience.

Much appreciation goes to all the people who made my Ph.D. a more than tolerable experience. Special thanks go to Marc, John, Andy, Doug, Rich A, Len and Robin, without whom the Three Tuns would seem a very expensive place.

Last but by no means least I would like to thank my Mum and Dad for always being there at the most difficult of times and always backing me in whatever I do. I just hope they will come to terms with the fact that I will not be sending back piles of cash as I made them believe would happen if I became a doctor.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
1.1	Tropical Climate Variability	2
1.2	Atmospheric Teleconnections	3
1.3	The Tropic Wide Mode (TWM)	5
1.4	Aims of the Study	6
1.5	Thesis Outline	7
2	Mechanisms of the Response to Tropical SST Forcing	9
2.1	Introduction	9
2.2	Tropical Approximations	10
2.3	The Tropical Response Problem	12
2.4	Simple Models	14
2.4.1	Axisymmetric Models	15
2.4.2	Two-Layer Models	19
2.4.3	Surface Forcing and Convective Heating	26
2.4.4	Simple Model of SST Induced Flow	29

2.5	Comparison of Simplified Models	32
2.6	Mechanisms for Remote Forcing	34
2.7	GCM Experiments	37
2.8	The Unified Model	39
2.8.1	General Setup and Parameterizations	39
2.8.2	An Aqua-Planet Version of the UM	41
3	The Zonally Averaged Circulation	44
3.1	Introduction	44
3.2	Determining the Nature of the ITCZ	45
3.3	Representation of Convection	45
3.4	Zonal Mean Observations	48
3.5	Aqua-Planet Model Studies	51
3.6	Description of Experiments	55
3.6.1	Hemispherically Symmetric	55
3.6.2	Hemispherically Asymmetric	56
3.7	Control Climatology	58
3.8	Hemispherically Symmetric Experiment Results	61
3.8.1	Precipitation	61
3.8.2	Circulation	63
3.8.3	Synoptic Structure	66
3.8.4	Communication of SST	67

3.8.5	Comparison with a Zonally Averaged Model	71
3.9	Hemispherically Asymmetric Experiment Results	74
3.9.1	Precipitation	74
3.9.2	Circulation	76
3.10	Comparisons with a Simple Model	80
3.11	Conclusions	82
4	Tropical Sea Surface Temperature Anomalies	84
4.1	Introduction	84
4.2	Motivation and Description of Experiments	85
4.3	Convective Precipitation	88
4.3.1	The Time Average	88
4.3.2	Linearity of the Response	91
4.4	Distribution of Diabatic Heating	93
4.5	Variations in the Tropospheric Depth of Convection	95
4.6	Variations in Precipitation Intensity	97
4.7	Communication of SST to the Atmosphere	99
4.8	Dynamical Response	102
4.9	Response of the Hadley Circulation	106
4.10	Skewed SST Anomalies	109
4.11	Conclusions	113
5	Tropical Wave Number One SST Anomalies	116

5.1	Introduction	116
5.2	Wavenumber One Experiments	117
5.3	Direct Response	117
5.4	Remote Response	124
5.4.1	Equatorial Westerlies	124
5.4.2	Sub-Tropical Surf Zone	128
5.4.3	Mechanisms for Zonal Mean Forcing	129
5.4.4	Storm Track Changes	135
5.5	Conclusions	139
6	Transients	140
6.1	Introduction	140
6.2	Observed Transient Behaviour	140
6.3	Axisymmetric Experiments	143
6.3.1	Precipitation	144
6.3.2	Zonal Wind	145
6.4	Anomaly Experiments	147
6.4.1	Precipitation	148
6.4.2	Zonal Wind	151
6.5	2-D Fourier Analysis of Transient Activity	152
6.5.1	Methodology	153
6.5.2	Observations	154

6.5.3	Control Transient Statistics	157
6.6	Other Aqua-Planet Experiment Transient Statistics	160
6.6.1	Symmetric Spectra	162
6.6.2	Antisymmetric Spectra	164
6.7	Conclusions	166
7	Comparison with Simplified Atmospheric Models	168
7.1	Introduction	168
7.2	Single Layer Boundary Layer Model	169
7.2.1	Model and Experiment Formulation	169
7.2.2	SST or Near Surface Temperature Forcing?	171
7.2.3	Equatorial Confined Anomaly Experiments	172
7.2.4	Off Equatorial Confined Anomaly Experiments	178
7.2.5	Wavenumber One Experiments	179
7.2.6	Discussion	181
7.3	Quasi-Equilibrium Tropical Circulation Model	183
7.3.1	Model and Experiment Formulation	183
7.3.2	Zonally Invariant SST Experiments	185
7.3.3	Confined Anomaly and Wavenumber One Experiments	191
7.3.4	Discussion	195
7.4	Conclusions	196
A7.1	Numerical Formulation of a Simple Model of the Tropical Boundary Layer .	199

8	Conclusions	202
8.1	Convective Response to SST Distribution	202
8.2	Direct Dynamical Response to Convective Heating	205
8.3	Atmospheric Teleconnections	207
8.4	Simple Models and Model Intercomparison	208
8.5	Further Work	209
8.5.1	Tropical Climate Variability	209
8.5.2	Implications for Tropical Climate Modelling	211

Chapter 1

Introduction

The climate of the earth-atmosphere system varies over a wide range of time and space scales, from small micro-scale turbulent fluctuations over a few seconds to global scale temperature variations due to earth orbital changes over tens of thousands of years. Within this vast time frame the sub-period varying from seasonal to decadal time scales is the subject of particular interest to the scientific community. Variability on these time scales has the greatest human impact, particularly in marginal regions of the world where even the slightest shift in the mean climatic conditions can have devastating consequences for the population.

The nature of the earth-atmosphere system is such that variability is rarely confined to single geographical regions and large-scale variations in one particular area can be correlated with another giving rise to covariability properties. The existence of robust large-scale patterns of covariance makes it possible to assess the climate fluctuations in a certain region given its covariance and correlation properties. For instance an increase in mean precipitation would be associated with a decrease in a second region with which the first region was negatively correlated.

Statistical analysis has been performed in many studies using observational data to determine the dominant modes of variability in the atmosphere. Thus with knowledge of past climate variability and the forcing responsible for this variability there exists a potential for predictability in the climate system.

1.1 Tropical Climate Variability

Climate fluctuations over the tropical regions of the globe differ from elsewhere as, to a certain extent, they result directly from fluctuations in the slowly varying Sea Surface Temperature (SST) boundary forcing. The simplest example of this is the effect of the seasonal cycle which provides large external variability of tropical SSTs due to variations in surface heating. Since precipitation variations are in general closely associated with variations in SST (Horel, 1982), the primary climatic consequence of this is a shift in the region of maximum tropical precipitation, the Inter-Tropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ), therefore giving precipitation variability similar to that of the SST. The gross nature and timing of this variability is in general predictable.

The largest interannual mode of variability in SST due to internal forcing is associated with the El Niño phenomenon (Philander, 1985). With a period of 2-5 years the distribution of SSTs in the tropical Pacific basin changes dramatically with western Pacific warm waters extending deep into the central and eastern Pacific. In addition there is atmospheric variability on the same time and space scales, observed as the Southern Oscillation (SO) (Walker, 1923). This combined coupled El Niño/Southern Oscillation (ENSO) phenomena can dominate interannual variability both in the tropical and extra-tropics regions.

Convection in the tropics is an integral part in the communication of SST and SST variability to the overlying atmosphere. The response of the atmosphere to prescribed convective heating can reproduce the observed zonal mean Hadley circulation and westerly sub-tropical jet structure for an ITCZ type heating (Held and Hou, 1980), as well as the observed zonally asymmetric structure (Hoskins and Rodwell, 1995). The tropical wave response to steady tropical convective heating can also be reproduced (Gill, 1980, Lau and Lim, 1982) which can give rise to Walker type circulations. Simple modelling studies have also shown that SST gradients can drive a significant circulation near the surface supplying convective ascent, both in the zonal mean (Schneider and Lindzen, 1977) and in response to SST anomalies (Lindzen and Nigam, 1987).

1.2 Atmospheric Teleconnections

Many of the patterns of atmospheric variability organise into particular coherent patterns or teleconnections which affect regions remote from the area of the original forcing. In the SO component of the ENSO phenomena, decreases in the surface pressure in the eastern and central Pacific are accompanied by an increase in surface pressure in the western Pacific basin. This strong correlation is also observed in many other climate variables including temperature and precipitation, and continues with a see-saw in the anomalies during the opposite La Niña positive Southern Oscillation Index phase of ENSO.

Bjerknes (1966) showed that the longitudinally overturning Walker circulation is an integral part of the SO and can lead to remote suppression of western Pacific precipitation during El Niño conditions, in addition to significant changes in the latitudinally overturning Hadley circulation. Interannual variability linked to Pacific basin ENSO events has also been observed in the tropical Atlantic region (Ropelewski and Halpert, 1996) and during the Asian summer monsoon season (Webster and Yang, 1992). During ENSO years Atlantic precipitation is suppressed and Asian summer precipitation is in general also suppressed with a delayed onset. Modelling studies suggest that this response may be achieved by a shift in position and a change in strength of the Walker circulation (Ju and Slingo, 1995, Saravanan and Chang, 1999).

Teleconnection patterns are also found in observational data which link the tropics with the extra-tropics on seasonal and interannual time scales. Wallace and Gutzler (1981) produced one point correlation maps from monthly mean data and found preferred robust teleconnection patterns, in particular the now well documented Pacific/North American (PNA). The structure of the anomalies was equivalent barotropic, increasing in amplitude with height. The strength of the PNA pattern exhibits variability which correlates with the SO (Horel and Wallace, 1981), such that a negative SO index or El Niño conditions leads to a strengthening of the centres of action of the PNA pattern.

Theoretical and modelling studies have attempted to understand the wave-like appearance of the PNA teleconnection patterns (Webster, 1981, Simmons, 1982). Hoskins and Karoly (1981), from wave theory and results from a linearised baroclinic model, suggest that the PNA type response to tropical heating may be considered as a planetary stationary Rossby

Figure 1.1: Climate anomalies during the operation of the Tropic Wide Mode (TWM) in Boreal winter (JAS).

wave response.

Predictability experiments using more complex GCMs has identified the need for several realisations of an individual experiment in order to obtain significance in any extra-tropical response to tropical forcing. Using an ensemble of GCM experiments, Geisler *et al.* (1985) found predictability in the PNA response, and its location is relatively insensitive to the position of a tropical Pacific SST anomaly such that it remained over a fixed geographical region. Palmer and Mansfield (1986) also found that the dynamical response which leads to the PNA pattern may be a combined response to a tropical heat source, north American orography and interaction with enhanced Pacific storm track activity.

1.3 The Tropic Wide Mode (TWM)

Preferred teleconnection patterns exist in certain regions which have variability that correlates with patterns of SST variability. Ward (1993), from a careful study of observational data, was able to suggest the existence of a large-scale tropical atmospheric teleconnection in the JAS season, which constitutes a tropic-wide mode (TWM) of variability. Fig 1.1 shows typical tropic-wide climate anomalies occurring for the sign of the mode where Sahelian rainfall is higher than average.

On shorter than decadal time scales Ward (1993) found the TWM is forced principally in response to variations in the pattern of west Pacific SST. For this sign of the mode positive SST anomalies frequently, but not exclusively associated with a La Nina event, generate anomalous convergence and ascent over the maritime continent and in the south Pacific convergence zone region. This implies that positive precipitation and diabatic heating anomalies are present in this region. Therefore, convergence preferentially occurs here at the expense of the south China sea region further north where there exists lower-tropospheric anomalous divergence and descent. The observed response in the west Pacific is associated, according to Ward (1993), with a teleconnection pattern giving rise to enhanced precipitation in the monsoon regions of the Sahel and India as well as the Caribbean region.

One view of the coherent variability seen in these remote regions is that it is due to a response in the overturning Hadley circulation. In the wet Sahel sign of the mode this would imply a weakening of the dominant northern hemisphere Hadley cell in the west Pacific region with an intensification elsewhere and associated increase in ITCZ precipitation. One possible mechanism that may allow the communication between the Hadley circulation at different longitudes is via the sub-tropical westerly jets (Ward, 1993). Reduced poleward exports of heat and momentum at one longitude may conceivably lead to changes in the sub-tropical jet at all other longitudes on long enough time scales, thus increasing north-south temperature gradients and generating increased exports of momentum and heat. The work in this thesis is aimed at trying to understand a remote response such as the tropic wide mode, and test hypotheses as to its production mechanism such as modulation of the Hadley circulation.

1.4 Aims of the Study

Given the observed climate variability obtained through the analysis of climate data and the recognition that according to Ward (1993) this variability occurs through robust teleconnection patterns, then this leads us to the following fundamental question.

What succession of physical and dynamical processes lead to the atmosphere responding to tropical SST variability in the manner observed?

The main aim of this study is to at least go some way towards answering this question in order to obtain a greater understanding of the whole atmospheric response to tropical SST. This is undertaken using a staged approach and splitting the study into four particular areas:

1. *The direct response to SST.* This is the first and arguably the most crucial stage in understanding the response to SSTs. Errors made at this stage will permeate the whole response leading to much reduced predictability in the remote response to the forcing. This study will concentrate on how the dominant heat source of the tropical atmosphere, latent heat release within convective clouds, responds to all aspects of the tropical SST field including the magnitude, gradient, scale and shape.
2. *Atmospheric response to convective heating.* The local dynamical response to convective heating can feedback on the heating itself through changes to the moisture supply and atmospheric stability. A number of modelling studies have been performed which predict the direct atmospheric response to a tropical heating distribution (Held and Hou, 1980, Schneider and Lindzen, 1977, Schneider, 1977, Gill, 1980) or SST distribution (Lindzen and Nigam, 1987, Zebiak, 1982, Zebiak, 1986). This study aims to investigate the validity of results from these models when applied to more complicated numerical models of the atmosphere subject to simplified forcings.
3. *Remote effects of SST anomalies: Teleconnections.* Since it appears that tropical climate variability can be communicated over large distances through particular teleconnection patterns, then we need to understand what mechanisms are involved in these teleconnection patterns. In addition, as seen with the tropic wide mode, what patterns of SST and prevailing climate states are conducive to strong teleconnection

patterns?

4. *Comparison of models.* Accompanying much of this numerical modelling study is the assumption that the complex GCM we use is essentially correct. This is almost certainly not the case and analyses of other numerical models, varying in complexity, is performed with the same boundary SST forcing to investigate how robust the results are pertaining to points 1-3.

1.5 Thesis Outline

The thesis is structured in such a way as to give a progressive account of our understanding of the tropical atmosphere using both theory and modelling studies. The conventional approach taken to understand the tropical circulation is questioned, and possible enhancements to this approach become increasingly apparent throughout the work, culminating in proposals for ways in which current methodologies can be complemented and improved.

In Chapter 2 a summary of tropical dynamical theory is given which considers certain tropical approximations, simple dynamical models and the influence of planetary wave activity on extra-tropical regions. The need to understand the atmospheric response to the most basic characteristics of the SST field is addressed in Chapter 3 with axisymmetric modelling experiments using an idealised GCM subject to zonally invariant SST distributions.

A further step towards our understanding is taken in Chapter 4, with examination of the local and remote response to a number of prescribed simplified tropical SST anomalies. Emphasis is put on the remote and zonal mean response to SST anomalies in Chapter 5. Analysis of the response to zonal wavenumber one SST anomalies reveals more clearly how the zonal mean circulation is maintained.

The behaviour of the transient activity in the suite of SST anomaly experiments is investigated in Chapter 6. Marked changes in the characteristics of the wavenumber-frequency statistics for particular experiment are revealed. Comparisons are then performed in Chapter 7 between an idealised GCM, and two simpler models of the tropical atmosphere to determine the robustness of the results, both in terms of the dominant processes which determine the response to SST in our idealised GCM, and the extent to which different

representations of physical processes may lead to model dependent results.

In Chapter 8 the questions posed in this thesis are answered in terms of the results described in the thesis. Recommendations for the future approach towards climate modelling and GCM experimentation are discussed. In particular, in light of the results from this study, the need to take a step back from the more complex model intercomparison projects is stressed. Experimentation of the type performed in this thesis is thought to be valuable in filling the gap that exists between the most complex GCMs, and the simplest single column models in order to fully understand the characteristics of the atmospheric response to SST.

Chapter 2

Mechanisms of the Response to Tropical SST Forcing

2.1 Introduction

The tropics differs from the mid-latitudes in a number of fundamental ways which calls for a different approach when trying to understand and model the observed circulations. The rotation of the earth has a zeroth order influence on large scale disturbances throughout the whole of the atmosphere via the Coriolis force. In the tropics this force is relatively small and the latitudinal gradient of planetary rotation often turns out to be of greater importance. This strong gradient of planetary vorticity provides a wave guide property in the tropics trapping atmospheric disturbances. In addition, unlike the mid-latitudes, latent heating in the tropics from cumulus convection provides the major energy source which can be considered to drive the tropical circulation.

Many simple models have been developed which use these two major approximations and achieve some success. The major stumbling block of this approach lies in these models' ability to relate horizontal distributions of SST to horizontal and vertical distributions of convective heating. In this lies the major tropical problem of understanding the interplay between the balances of convection, radiation, dynamics and surface processes. GCMs of varying complexity have been used to investigate the relative importance of many of these interactions. Attempts have also been made using GCMs to assess the role that

tropical disturbances play in forcing the evolution of the mid-latitude circulation, especially on time scales greater than a week or so. There also remains the problem of tropical-tropical interactions as revealed in the TWM (Ward, 1993), but the mechanisms for these interactions are by no means certain.

2.2 Tropical Approximations

The introduction briefly outlines the importance of the latitudinal variation of planetary vorticity for large scale tropical circulations. A Taylor expansion of the planetary vorticity about the equator, where $f = 0$, allows us to approximate its tropical distribution as a linear function of distance from the equator:

$$f(y) = \beta y, \quad (2.1)$$

where

$$\beta = \frac{2\Omega}{r_e}. \quad (2.2)$$

Making this so called *β plane approximation* results in a maximum error in f of not more than 14% in the range 30°N to 30°S, which covers half the surface of the earth. Representation of the Coriolis parameter in this way is therefore standard in many simplified climate models

Since the release of latent heat in cumulus convection dominates in the tropics, then it is possible to make simplifying approximations to the thermodynamics in order to gain insight into the dominant effects of this heating. The thermodynamic tendency can be written as:

$$\frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} + \omega \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial p} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla \theta = Q_0, \quad (2.3)$$

and, in a steady situation in the tropics, scale analysis reveals that the horizontal terms are of secondary importance due predominantly to the absence of significant horizontal

temperature gradients. Therefore, Eqn. 2.3 can be simplified to:

$$\omega \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial p} = Q_0. \quad (2.4)$$

We now have a balance between the net large-scale heating due to moist processes, represented by Q_0 , and the distribution of ascent and descent. In a tropical feature such as the ITCZ this can be interpreted as a balance between the latent heating from convection and the adiabatic cooling due to ascent in the mid-troposphere. To a first order approximation this can also account for adiabatic warming due to descent in the sub-tropical anticyclones and descending branch of the Hadley circulation being balanced with loss of long-wave radiation to space through clear skies. On large time and space scales this provides a good approximation but the cause and effect relationship between heating and vertical velocity is not obvious. Another problem with making such a diagnostic approximation is that the relationship between heating and temperature in the tropics becomes unclear.

By making the β -plane and thermodynamic approximations it allows us to say something about the balance of vorticity in the tropics. Neglecting the twisting terms, which tend to be of second order importance in the tropics on large length scales, the three dimensional vorticity equation can be written as

$$\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial t} + \omega \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial p} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \zeta = -\zeta D. \quad (2.5)$$

Assuming a steady state solution, approximating the absolute vorticity as just the planetary vorticity f , and neglecting vertical and horizontal advection of vorticity except for the meridional advection of planetary vorticity, βy , gives an expression for the dominant tropical vorticity balance, namely

$$\beta v = f \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial p}. \quad (2.6)$$

A schematic showing the features which result from combining Eqns. 2.6 and 2.4 is shown in Fig. 2.1. The vortex compression and stretching in the upper- and lower-layers, respectively, result from the vertical velocity response to the convective heating, Q_0 . The meridional advection which balances this effect combined with convective inflow and outflow can be interpreted as anticyclonic and cyclonic responses to the west as shown.

Figure 2.1: Approximation of the vorticity balance in the tropics in response to convective latent heating (anticyclones, A, and cyclones, C, are shown).

2.3 The Tropical Response Problem

Accurate modelling of the tropical climate system requires detailed knowledge of the interaction between the components of the climate system. In particular the link between the tropical SST field, boundary layer processes, convection and dynamics has long been at the centre of much GCM analysis. Obtaining the correct climatic response to even prescribed observed SSTs has proved difficult particularly in the area of seasonal forecasting of events such as ENSO and the Indian summer monsoon. In addition feedbacks from the atmosphere to the ocean make for a coupled system whose behaviour has proved difficult to predict.

At the air-sea interface there is a continual exchange of heat and moisture. Since the tropical atmosphere is predominantly transparent to incoming solar radiation, the majority of it goes directly into heating the upper 1 metre or so of the ocean directly, and the upper 50 metres indirectly through vertical mixing. The atmosphere, therefore, has its heat and moisture supplied from below and these are distributed in the vertical by convective processes. As stated previously the tropical atmosphere is conditionally unstable, and individual parcels which have sufficient energy can break through this stability barrier or level of free convection and begin to convect freely through the depth of the troposphere.

Observations show that the frequency and depth of convection and its effects are increased

strongly in regions where surface temperatures exceed about 27°C (Zhang, 1993). At and above SSTs of this magnitude the saturated vapour pressure increases more strongly for a particular incremental temperature increase than at lower SSTs. The heating from SSTs of this magnitude and greater provides sufficient energy for air parcels to overcome the conditional instability barrier and convect freely. The low-level supply of energy and moisture is provided by any in-situ evaporation and sensible heating anomalies, and the convergence of energy and moisture into the region.

The regions most susceptible to convection are thus over areas of high SST, but in addition to this the gradients in SST transmitted to the boundary layer air generate a surface pressure field which may contribute to convergent flows, thus supplying additional low-level moisture and energy. Therefore, it is important to consider the gradient and the magnitude of SST as contributing factors for convection.

Horizontal and vertical distribution of convection is vitally important in the tropics as the latent heat released within the deep cumulus towers acts to force the local circulation on short (minutes/hours) time scales through the action of the updraughts and downdraughts. On longer time scales the larger-scale dynamics responds to the net tropospheric heating distribution. It is vital, therefore, to represent the net thermodynamic effects of small scales and short time scale convective events in order to correctly determine the large-scale dynamics. This is the role of the closure used in convection schemes which parameterizes the effects of an ensemble of individual convective elements within each grid box in terms of the large scale model variables.

The next link in the system is to accurately model the global influence of this direct response to tropical heating. This involves teleconnections that operate between tropical and remote regions in the higher latitudes and in the tropics. Planetary or Rossby wave radiation and vertical circulations (local Hadley and Walker circulations) facilitate this teleconnective response.

There are many problems that prevent accurate modelling of the mechanisms involved in the whole tropical climate system, not least of which is the poor coverage and sometimes erroneous nature of observations, particular in the ocean. One of the most important and sensitive tropical regions is the eastern Pacific where surface fluxes vary considerably between ENSO events. Yet observational coverage in this region prior to the 1990s was one of

the most sparse on the globe. Satellite measurements provide some data, but it is no substitute for radiosonde ascents and surface observations of winds, temperature, pressure and humidity. Field campaigns such as the TOGA COARE (Webster and Lukas, 1992) helped enormously to fill gaps in knowledge involving subsurface characteristics, surface fluxes and dynamics of the response to SST (Trenberth *et al.*, 1998). The need for improved spatial coverage and monitoring of the equatorial Pacific led to an observational network of tethered buoys in the tropical Pacific known as the TAO (Tropical Atmosphere-Ocean) array. The data obtained from this observational network contributes greatly to the verification of remotely sensed data and numerical model results.

Attempts to model the system are therefore immediately hindered by errors in the initial model fields assimilated from the observed data. Even the smallest errors in surface fluxes or boundary layer buoyancy makes all the difference when considering whether an air parcel is able to convect and lead to latent heat release within cumulus clouds.

Even with accurate observations there are still considerable gaps in the knowledge of the individual components of the system and their interactions. Convective processes in particular are poorly understood in the climate system, and this is evident in the numerous different convection schemes currently being employed in climate models which use a wide range of criteria to diagnose convection and its effects on the large scale.

2.4 Simple Models

A common approach in dealing with the complex situation like that in the tropical atmosphere is to concentrate on particular processes using simplified models to investigate which parts are required in order to capture the gross structure. This type of study has tended to centre around how the tropical dynamics responds to the net latent heating from the cumulus convection.

Two main types of model have arisen from the need to understand the steady response to tropical heating. Firstly the response of the zonal mean Hadley circulation to some prescribed zonal mean heating has been investigated in many studies with primitive equation models, for heating centred both on and off the equator. Secondly, the fact that the tropical

circulation exhibits a first baroclinic mode structure has been utilised by using a simple two layer shallow water model to represent the horizontal upper- and lower-tropospheric parts of the tropical atmosphere. Variations on this approach have included one in which just a model boundary layer of varying thickness responds to variations in SST and convergence anomalies. An outline of a selection of these different models follows.

2.4.1 Axisymmetric Models

As a first approximation it may be considered that the zonally asymmetric motions dominant in the mid-latitudes are not as important in the tropics. Studies by Schneider and Lindzen (1977), Schneider (1977), and Held and Hou (1980) examine the linear and non-linear circulation in a model of the steady axially symmetric motions on a sphere where the fluid is sufficiently inviscid to almost allow angular momentum conservation within its interior. The original motivation for these studies was to test whether a realistic circulation was generated when the middle latitude baroclinic instabilities were artificially suppressed, by running the model in a zonal mean two-dimensional domain. Concentrating on the Held and Hou (1980) approach, the model primitive equations used are for a dry Boussinesq fluid on a hemisphere confined between the surface and a rigid lid at height H above the surface. The representation of the thermal forcing due to tropical convective heating is given by some relaxation of the tropospheric temperature, θ , to a specified *radiative equilibrium* temperature, θ_E . The only small scale mixing process is linear vertical diffusion of heat and momentum. Thus for a steady flow in this latitude height plane where $\mathbf{v} = (0, v, w)$ the equations of motion are:

$$0 = -\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{v}u) + fv + \frac{uv \tan \theta}{r_e} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\nu \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} \right), \quad (2.7)$$

$$0 = -\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{v}v) - fu - \frac{u^2 \tan \theta}{r_e} - \frac{1}{r_e} \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial \phi} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\nu \frac{\partial v}{\partial z} \right), \quad (2.8)$$

$$0 = -\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{v}\theta) - (\theta - \theta_E)\tau^{-1} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\nu \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial z} \right), \quad (2.9)$$

$$0 = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}, \quad (2.10)$$

$$\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial z} = g \frac{\theta}{\theta_0}, \quad (2.11)$$

where τ is a constant radiative damping time. θ_E is given the form:

$$\frac{\theta_E(\phi, z)}{\theta_0} = 1 - \frac{2}{3}\Delta_H P_2(\sin \phi) - \Delta_\nu \left(\frac{z}{H} - \frac{1}{2} \right), \quad (2.12)$$

which gives a zonal mean distribution of θ_E representative of that observed in the atmosphere. θ_0 is the global mean of θ_E . Δ_H and Δ_ν are the fractional change in potential temperature from equator to pole and from the top to the bottom of the fluid in radiative equilibrium respectively. P_2 is the second Legendre polynomial $P_2(x) = 1/2(3x^2 - 1)$. Solving the equations of motion with an inviscid approximation ($\nu=0$) it looks possible to obtain solutions with no meridional circulation and temperatures in radiative equilibrium ($\theta_E=\theta_0$). The zonal wind, u_E , must therefore be in thermal wind balance given by

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(f u_E + \frac{u_E^2 \tan \theta}{2} \right) = -\frac{g}{r_e \theta_0} \frac{\partial \theta_E}{\partial \phi}. \quad (2.13)$$

However, the effects of viscosity cannot be evaluated simply by looking for solutions to the equations for small values of ν by perturbing the inviscid solution. This is because the non-inviscid solution does not approach the inviscid solution as $\nu \rightarrow 0$. The reason for this can be seen by rewriting the zonal momentum equation (Eqn. 2.8) in terms of angular momentum, M :

$$0 = -\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{v}M) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \left(\nu \frac{\partial M}{\partial z} \right), \quad (2.14)$$

where

$$M = \Omega r_e^2 \cos^2 \phi + u r_e \cos \phi. \quad (2.15)$$

In the inviscid solution M can have a local maximum anywhere in the fluid interior, whereas when viscosity is considered M can only have a maximum at a point on the lower boundary. Only at this point can the diffusive loss of westerly momentum be balanced by a surface stress boundary condition, which means u must be less than or equal to 0 at this point. From Eqn. 2.15, M must be less than or equal to Ωr_e^2 everywhere in the fluid, implying u must also be less than or equal to

$$u_M \equiv \Omega r_e \frac{\sin^2 \phi}{\cos \phi}. \quad (2.16)$$

Therefore, in a near inviscid atmosphere the zonal mean flow is constrained by both angular momentum conservation and the need to satisfy thermal wind balance. This results in two distinctly different flow regimes depending upon the imposed pole to equator temperature gradient as we will see later.

Taking the argument further it is possible to determine the nature of the axisymmetric circulation, given the pole to equator temperature forcing, which was at the outset our primary aim, i.e. given the thermal forcing are the dominant large scale circulations reproduced in this simplified model framework?

The distribution of θ consistent with angular momentum constraints (θ_M) can be determined by combining an approximation for the vertical shear of zonal wind, and the relation describing the distribution of zonal wind consistent with angular momentum conservation (Eqn. 2.16). Assuming the zonal wind goes to zero at the surface, an approximation to the vertical zonal wind shear from angular momentum gives

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial z} \approx \frac{u_M}{H_T} \approx \frac{\Omega r_e \sin^2 \phi}{H_T \cos \phi}, \quad (2.17)$$

where H_T is a typical tropospheric depth. Combining this expression with the thermal wind relation (Eqn. 2.13), but for clarity ignoring the spherical geometry terms, results in

$$2\Omega \sin \phi \frac{\partial u}{\partial z} = \frac{2\Omega \sin \phi \Omega r_e \sin^2 \phi}{H_T \cos \phi} = -\frac{g}{r_e \theta_0} \frac{\partial \theta_M}{\partial \phi}. \quad (2.18)$$

This determines the latitudinal gradient of potential temperature:

$$\frac{\partial \theta_M}{\partial \phi} = \frac{2\Omega^2 \theta_0 r_e^2 \sin^3 \phi}{g H_T \cos \phi}, \quad (2.19)$$

that is the limiting case for a thermal wind which is consistent with angular momentum conservation. If the radiative equilibrium temperature distribution is steeper than the distribution given in Eqn. 2.19, which is true given the form of θ_E in Eqn. 2.12, then processes must act in order that angular momentum conservation is not violated. Given that θ_M and θ_E will differ at a particular latitude, an initial approximation of Eqn. 2.9 to

$$-w \frac{\partial \theta_M}{\partial z} = (\theta_M - \theta_E) \tau^{-1} \quad (2.20)$$

gives the vertical velocity field in response to the difference in θ_M and θ_E . Therefore, consistent with the latitudinal temperature distribution, a mean meridional circulation exists giving heating and ascent where $\theta_E > \theta_M$, and cooling and descent where $\theta_E < \theta_M$. Continuity predicts that convective meridional flow towards the equator at lower-levels and away from the equator at upper-levels will connect the ascent and descent regions. This picture is essentially the observed atmospheric Hadley circulation and suggests that such a circulation must exist between the latitudes where the latitudinal gradient of θ_E exceeds that of θ_M . Since parcels continually cycle around in the mean meridional circulation cells, then there must be no net heating implied after one full circuit, i.e. the cooling during ascent must balance the heating during descent, conserving potential temperature. This means the following condition must be satisfied

$$\int_0^{\phi_{HC}} \theta \cos \phi \, d\phi = \int_0^{\phi_{HC}} \theta_E \cos \phi \, d\phi, \quad (2.21)$$

which predicts the latitude of the poleward edge of the model Hadley cell, ϕ_{HC} , to be in the sub-tropics. Of course if a tropical latitudinal profile of θ_E is used which has a shallower gradient than θ_M , then a different regime will result. The flow will no longer continually force the temperature distribution back to that of θ_M and a mean meridional circulation will be absent.

The limiting case separating the two regimes is found by integrating Eqn. 2.19 and using the small-angle approximation applicable in the tropics, to give

$$\theta_M = \theta_{M0} - \frac{\Omega^2 \theta_0 r_e^2 \phi^4}{2gH_T}, \quad (2.22)$$

where θ_{M0} is the equatorial value of θ_M . We can now see that any latitudinal temperature distribution that falls off with a rate greater than the fourth power of latitude will necessitate a mean meridional circulation, in order to be consistent with angular momentum conservation. However, if the distribution of temperature falls off less steeply than this then the thermal wind implied from the radiative equilibrium temperature distribution does not violate angular momentum conservation, and hence there is no requirement for a mean meridional circulation. This model, therefore, predicts that the zonal wind has a latitudinal profile consistent with thermal wind balance as outlined in Eqn. 2.13.

A similar analysis can be performed within this model framework but instead using a θ_E profile which maximises off the equator. A study carried out by Lindzen and Hou (1988) examined the sensitivity of the atmospheric response to such a distribution of forcing. They found that the circulation was extremely sensitive to the latitude of maximum radiative equilibrium temperature. Numerical simulations revealed that for a displacement of the maximum θ_E to just 2°N the strength of the southern hemisphere Hadley cell was three times as large as the northern hemisphere cell. When this displacement is to 6°N then the southern hemisphere cell completely dominates. In addition the mean strength of each cell with maximum θ_E at 2°N and 2°S is greater than with the maximum at the equator. This implies that the response to annually averaged heating, say, is less than the average response to heating varying between the summer and winter solstice. Modelling the response to the annual mean heating could therefore underestimate many other aspects of the zonal mean circulation such as the surface evaporation, maximum strength of the sub-tropical jets, and the poleward transport of heat and angular momentum.

In summary, these simplified axisymmetric models of the atmosphere capture the gross structure surprisingly well given the simple representation of the convective heating and allow quantitative estimates of the strength and extent of the Hadley cells given the distribution of θ_E . They also elucidate the large sensitivity to SST forcing when the maximum is displaced even a small distance off the equator. There are also a number of short-comings in using such a model. In particular the distribution of heating does not compare well with that observed. Convection and therefore thermal forcing are intimately linked to SST and the zonal mean of SST is observed to be a maximum on or north of the equator in all seasons, which would make it difficult to envisage a strong Boreal winter Hadley cell, particularly in regions such as the east Pacific.

2.4.2 Two-Layer Models

Although the zonally averaged representation of the atmosphere provides many useful insights into the mechanisms governing the response to thermal forcing the tropics is far from zonally symmetric. Thermal forcing is localised in nature and particularly in non El Niño conditions there is significant asymmetry across regions such as the Pacific basin, with strong convection and heating in the west Pacific and much weaker heating in the central

and eastern Pacific. The atmosphere responds strongly to the western Pacific thermal forcing and many classes of wave disturbances are excited, some of which are able to propagate significant distances within the tropical wave guide.

One approach which has been frequently used to highlight the nature of the response to diabatic heating is to solve the dynamical equations describing the tropical circulation in a simplified framework. With a resting tropical basic state the atmospheric properties are a function of height only and as horizontal scales are large compared to vertical scales it is possible to separate the solution into two parts, one with height variation and one with horizontal and temporal variation. When considering the more relevant forced problem as we wish to do here, it is possible to represent the vertical distribution of diabatic heating as a series of modes and sum the solution over all the individual relevant modes. However, the nature of the vertical structure of diabatic heating in the tropics is such that it peaks in the mid troposphere and to a good approximation is described by just the first of these vertical modes. With such a simple vertical structure the vertical velocity distribution would be described by $\sin(\pi z/D)$, where D is the depth of the troposphere. Similarly the vertical distribution of pressure and horizontal velocity for this mode would be described simply by $\cos(\pi z/D)$. Therefore, the separation of the solution for this first mode allows the simple forced shallow water equations to be used to find the solution.

This type of approach is following that of Gill (1980) and the shallow water equations appropriate to finding the response to steady forcing (in the lower of the two layers) are:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} - \beta y v &= \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial x} \\ \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} + \beta y u &= \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial y} \\ \frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} + c_0^2 (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v}) &= -Q_0, \end{aligned} \quad (2.23)$$

where quantities are perturbations about a resting state. Q_0 is a representation of convective heating which in this problem is interpreted as a mass source in the lower layer and a mass sink in the upper-layer. $c_0 = \sqrt{gH_0}$ is the fundamental wave speed of the mode with an equivalent depth of H_0 . For the atmosphere typical wave speeds are 20-80 ms^{-1} corresponding to equivalent water depths of 40-640 m.

Analysis of linear perturbations to a resting state atmosphere on an equatorial β -plane by

Matsuno (1966) revealed several classes of waves supported by the shallow water equations (Eqns. 2.23). The dispersion relation from the wave equation appropriate to Eqns. 2.23 are summarised graphically in Fig. 2.2.

Forcing the shallow water equations with a symmetric (about the equator) heating distribution with a maximum in the mid-troposphere will give a reasonable representation of west Pacific thermal forcing due to warm pool convection and excite the dominant first baroclinic mode structure. However, as the large scale SST field and main convection regions vary on slow seasonal time scales, we are generally only interested in the response on long space and time scales and so many of the wave disturbances shown in Fig. 2.2, such as the fast gravity waves are not relevant here. Therefore, removing the time dependence from the problem and including frictional processes yields the steady version of Eqns. 2.23.

The steady modelled response to a forcing of this type is shown in Fig. 2.3 and reproduces many of the typical characteristics of the flow in the tropical Pacific and Indian ocean

Figure 2.2: Dispersion relation for the frequency and wavenumber of wave motions in an equatorial β -plane. Stippled region indicates the long wave quasi-steady response region (taken from Lau and Lim (1982)).

Figure 2.3: Modelled response to a symmetric heating distribution centred on the equator (where $x = 0$), (a) contours of w , solid contours indicate ascent and dashed descent, imposed on the lower layer horizontal velocity field; (b) lower layer perturbation pressure contours, negative everywhere, imposed on the lower layer horizontal velocity; (c) meridionally integrated flow along the equator; (d) lower layer perturbation pressure along the equator. Magnitudes are non-dimensionalised and length scales are subject to non-dimensionalisation by $(c/2\beta)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ such that 1 on the y -axis scales to about 10° in latitude. (Taken from Gill (1980))

regions. The most striking feature of the flow is the large east-west asymmetry in both the distance the disturbances propagate and the structure of the features. To the east lies a region of extensive zonal inflow towards the region of heating which maximises on the equator and reduces its magnitude with increased distance from the equator and the heat source. The sign of the flow variables in the upper-level is the reverse of that in the lower layer.

Referring back to the dispersion relation for frequency and wavenumber (Fig. 2.2), analysis of the steady response yields the eastward propagating Kelvin wave which is responsible for the flow to the east of the heating region. In a resting basic state the Kelvin wave disturbance has the following form:

$$u = u_0 \exp\left(-\frac{\beta y^2}{2c}\right) \exp ik(x - ct) \quad (2.24)$$

$$v = 0 \quad (2.25)$$

$$\Phi = \Phi \exp\left(-\frac{\beta y^2}{2c}\right) \exp ik(x - ct), \quad (2.26)$$

where the trapping scale of the equatorial wave guide, Y_L , is given by

$$Y_L = \left|\frac{2}{c\beta}\right|^{\frac{1}{2}} \approx 1000 \text{ km}, \quad (2.27)$$

which is also the equatorial Rossby radius of deformation. Therefore, the Kelvin wave has no meridional flow and is symmetric about the equator.

To the west of the forcing the flow structure is somewhat more complicated with a pair of cyclones in the lower-level, one either side of the equator, and centred westwards of the heating maximum. The dispersion relation, again at long wavelengths and long time scales, reveals that these waves are characteristic of westward propagating Rossby waves, of which the $n=1$ gravest Rossby wave gives the dominant response. This Rossby wave response is a consequence of the large-scale Sverdrup balance (cf. Fig. 2.1) described in Section 2.2 and can also be viewed as the gravest Rossby wave response with opposite signs in the upper- and lower-levels.

The structure of the Rossby wave response in the v field takes the following form:

$$v = 2^{-\frac{n}{2}} H_n \left(\left(\frac{\beta}{c}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}} y \right) \exp\left(-\frac{\beta y^2}{2c}\right) \exp ik(x - ct), \quad (2.28)$$

where H is a Hermite polynomial of order n . This has a somewhat more complex structure than the Kelvin wave but is still subject to decay in latitude over the Rossby radius of deformation. Solutions for u and Φ can also be derived from the wave equations in terms of parabolic cylinder functions and they also decay in latitude over the Rossby radius of deformation. Analysing the shallow water equations dispersion relationship, illustrated in Fig. 2.2, gives an expression for the wave speeds:

$$\left(\frac{\omega}{c}\right)^2 - k^2 - \frac{\beta k}{\omega} = \frac{\beta(2n+1)}{c}. \quad (2.29)$$

For the $n=1$ Kelvin wave mode the β terms cancel in the above equation and leave a non-dispersive eastward phase speed of $c = \omega/k = c_0$ which is the same as for a non-rotating

fluid. However for Rossby wave modes the frequencies are always small compared to other terms, such that ω^2/k^2 can be neglected in Eqn. 2.29. The phase speed for Rossby wave modes can then be approximated by

$$c = \frac{\omega}{k} = -\frac{\beta k}{k^2 + (2n + 1)\frac{\beta}{c_0}}. \quad (2.30)$$

In the limit of long-wave disturbances, $k \rightarrow 0$, this equation can be further approximated:

$$c = -\frac{c_0}{(2n + 1)} \quad (2.31)$$

For the $n=1$ Rossby wave the phase speed is westwards with a magnitude of $c = -c_0/3$, one third the speed of the Kelvin wave and in the opposite direction. With the simple linear representation of frictional processes in this model the Kelvin wave can travel three times the distance of the Rossby wave before the signal is damped by friction.

It is reasonable to ask whether these idealised steady wave modes mirror anything that is observed in the tropical atmosphere. The representation of the heating is highly idealised and the observed heating distribution is somewhat more complex than this, but the heating field in MAM and particularly DJF (Fig. 2.4(c)) has localised heating maxima on the equator in the west Pacific, not unlike that of the idealised distribution. The Kelvin wave mode certainly appears to have an observed counterpart in the guise of the Pacific overturning Walker cell (Fig. 2.4(a),(b)). The low-level (≈ 850 mb) easterly inflow along the equator is evident across the central and eastern Pacific and robust in all seasons. The upper-level westerly outflow counterpart is less robust being strong and confined more to the eastern Pacific in DJF but weak or non-existent during the rest of the year.

The observed tropical counterpart of the low-level Rossby wave response to the west of the heating maximum is more difficult to identify. There is some evidence of westerly inflow towards the heating region between Australia and Indonesia in DJF, however other seasons show no such flow patterns. Equally there is no obvious poleward flow at low-levels away from the heating region during any seasons. The upper-level flow structure reflects the presence of a Rossby wave mode with the existence of two elongating anticyclones straddling the equator to the west of the heating maximum, and with strong easterly outflow on the equator. This picture is robust in the annual average, but as with the Kelvin

Figure 2.4: Diagnostics from 1979-1989 ECMWF analyses (Hoskins *et al.*, 1989) for DJF season, (a) 150 mb horizontal wind vectors (ms^{-1}); (b) 850 mb horizontal wind vectors (ms^{-1}), and (c) 700-50 mb diabatic heating (calculated as a residual from the time averaged thermodynamic equation) (K day^{-1}).

wave/Walker cell structure, is most marked in the DJF season. Also of note is that the upper-level anticyclones are somewhat further east than the simple model would suggest giving equatorial westerlies over the heating region.

Given the simple framework of the model one would not expect to perfectly represent the observed tropical features. In fact there is no doubt that many of the differences between model and observations are due to the influence of processes deemed to be of second order importance and omitted. The absence of processes such as differential land-sea effects, non-linear advective processes and the influence of the mean flow will all contribute to errors in the solution. However the model is still successful in qualitatively reproducing many of the large-scale circulation features.

The representation of the heating in this model is somewhat arbitrary and specified in a diagnostic sense. Taking a step back in the argument and diagnosing the heating itself from known surface fields would increase the predictive power of the model without significantly increasing the complexity of the dynamics represented in the model. Diabatic heating is the result of convective events which themselves originate near the surface and so must be influenced by surface processes. This will be the subject of the next two sections where this simple model framework will be enhanced giving it greater diagnostic power.

2.4.3 Surface Forcing and Convective Heating

Many convective events with towering cumulo-nimbus cloud structures and latent heat release, can be expected to be triggered in the boundary layer. Air parcels in the boundary layer must acquire sufficient energy to become buoyant enough to overcome the conditional instability barrier which is typical of the time averaged tropical atmospheric structure. However, relating the diabatic heating of an ensemble of convective events to surface conditions and in particular the SST in such a model is more difficult than it would at first appear. One reason for this is that the latent heating depends on a feedback between the initial dynamic response of the system to the underlying SST and the actual latent heating. This has the implication that the steady latent heating response to SST forcing may be much stronger than the initial implied heating after consideration of feedbacks with the dynamics of the system.

A number of different approaches can be taken to relate the distribution of surface properties to the final heating distribution used to force a steady state model. Webster (1981) uses an iterative scheme in order to calculate the total diabatic heating anomaly response to an imposed SST anomaly. This response is made up of a sensible heating fraction, Q_S , and a latent heating fraction in the ascending air above the SST anomaly, Q_L . The initial ascent anomaly is related to the sensible heating anomaly, and then the diabatic heating anomaly is calculated using this ascent. This process then changes the total zonal mean heating and so the zonal anomaly heating anomaly has to be recalculated, thus requiring a number of iterations until equilibrium of the solution is achieved. The first few iterations take the following form:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Q_1 &= Q_S \\
 Q_2 &= Q_1 + Q_L = Q_1 - B\Delta\{w'_1\} \\
 Q_3 &= Q_2 - B\Delta\{w'_1\} \\
 \dots &= \dots.
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{2.32}$$

B is a constant of proportionality representing aspects of the large-scale flow.

The overall effect of this approach is to peak the initial heating distribution so that it is more intense over the centre of the SST anomaly but on a smaller spatial scale than the SST. This is consistent with observations and GCM results mentioned previously. Applying this methodology generates a more physically based heating function which can be readily calculated from the slowly varying tropical SST distribution and provides an estimate of the quasi-steady response to the SST.

Although the strength and distribution of diabatic heating may be strongly related to the underlying SST many studies have suggested that latent heating is more directly related to low-level moisture convergence as in CISK (Conditional Instability of the Second Kind) processes (Charney and Eliassen, 1964). In this framework moisture convergence directly increases the conditional instability of the atmosphere and contributes to convection and latent heating, at least on large-scales and in a diagnostic sense, of the mid-troposphere. This feedback was modelled in a similar way by Zebiak (1986). Again a simple two-layer model based on Gill (1980) was used with an iterative method for determining the steady state heating of this simple dynamical system. This was based on an earlier study by Zebiak

(1982) where a similar model was used to simulate surface wind anomalies in the equatorial Pacific during El Niño conditions. In this earlier study the heating distribution was assumed to be a function purely of surface evaporation anomalies, which are themselves a function of SST anomalies. The Clausius-Clapeyron equation is linearised about a mean state SST, \bar{T} , in order to obtain the evaporation anomalies, Δe , considered to be proportional to the heating anomalies, giving the following expression:

$$\Delta e \propto \Delta SST \left. \frac{de_s}{dT} \right|_{\bar{T}}. \quad (2.33)$$

By incorporating this parameterization scheme for the heating some success was achieved in reproducing surface wind anomalies, especially in regions of mean convergence. However there were serious deficiencies in regions with no mean convergence and also the magnitudes of heating anomalies were smaller than observed giving weak flow solutions. In the later study (Zebiak, 1986) a convergence feedback process was employed similar to that of Webster (1981) where the diabatic heating anomaly at each iteration depends on the low-level moisture convergence from the previous iteration and the initial heating anomaly is given by Eqn. 2.33. The influence of the mean wind is also included such that moisture convergence anomalies are only enhanced in the iteration process if the sum of the mean and anomalous convergence field is negative. This implies that a positive SST anomaly will not necessarily give enhanced convergence if the mean field is divergent. This iterative process is described mathematically below:

$$Q_{n+1} = \begin{cases} Q_0, & : \text{if } (\delta_M + \delta'_n) > 0, \delta_M > 0 \\ Q_0 - \gamma(\delta_M + \delta'_n), & : \text{if } (\delta_M + \delta'_n) \leq 0, \delta_M > 0 \\ Q_0 + \gamma(\delta_M), & : \text{if } (\delta_M + \delta'_n) > 0, \delta_M \leq 0 \\ Q_0 - \gamma(\delta'_n), & : \text{if } (\delta_M + \delta'_n) \leq 0, \delta_M \leq 0. \end{cases} \quad (2.34)$$

δ_M is the mean divergence, and δ'_n is the anomalous divergence at iteration n (this is found by solving Eqns. 2.23 for the heating at iteration n and then computing the divergence). The parameter γ can be thought of as an *efficiency parameter* for the feedback process relating the excess in convergence to an increase in diabatic heating. The inclusion of the convergence feedback mechanism and the effects of the mean convergence field improve both the scale of the response to SST anomalies and the magnitude such that there is closer agreement for the El Niño period in which they were tested. There are still some

significant disagreements with observations, but by taking a more accurate and physically based approach to determine the diabatic forcing distribution, the same dynamical equations as in the Gill problem produce a much improved steady state solution.

2.4.4 Simple Model of SST Induced Flow

The two level modelling approach has, thus far, considered that both the upper- and lower-level tropical circulations occur predominantly in response to the release of latent heat within convection. An alternative view also exists whereby the low-level flow is driven directly by boundary layer pressure gradients established in response to the SST distribution.

It is of interest to investigate what the flow contribution is from the boundary layer pressure field due to SST induced temperature gradients in the observed boundary layer flow field. Such an investigation was carried out by Lindzen and Nigam (1987). They use a single-layer approach as before but instead concentrate on the depth averaged flow just in the boundary layer which responds to the horizontal distribution of boundary layer zonal perturbation temperature.

The distribution of the perturbation temperature field in the boundary layer is taken to be correlated in the vertical such that the features of the 1000 mb temperature field are communicated through the boundary layer with some damping applied. The contribution of the zonal mean temperature throughout the boundary layer is taken to be the surface temperature minus some specified lapse rate, in agreement with observations. The three dimensional boundary layer temperature field is thus assumed to be completely described as a function of SST by

$$T(\lambda, \phi, z) = \bar{T}_s - \alpha z + T'_s \left(1 - \frac{\gamma Z}{H_{BL}} \right), \quad (2.35)$$

where \bar{T}_s is the zonal mean surface temperature, T'_s is the deviation from the zonal mean surface temperature, and α is the adiabatic lapse rate of the zonal mean temperature which from observations is typically 0.003 K m^{-1} . The decay of the perturbation with height is taken to be such that features at 700 mb retain about 70% of the magnitude of the surface features. H_{BL} is taken to be the mean height of the 700 mb surface and γ takes the value 0.3.

The boundary layer flow generated by the SST induced surface pressure field can be estimated by simplifying the horizontal momentum equations:

$$\begin{aligned} -fv &= \frac{1}{\rho a \cos \phi} \frac{\partial p}{\partial \lambda} - \epsilon u \\ fu &= -\frac{1}{\rho a} \frac{\partial p}{\partial \phi} - \epsilon v. \end{aligned} \quad (2.36)$$

With a specified boundary condition at the top of the boundary layer and a knowledge of the vertical density distribution, the hydrostatic equation can be used to determine the pressure distribution. From this the mass weighted vertical average of Eqns. 2.36 linearised about a state of rest yields the boundary layer perturbation flow (U', V').

The simplest upper boundary condition is given by taking the height of the 700 mb pressure surface to be a constant value of 3000 m. Therefore, substituting the expression for the pressure terms and a linear drag approximation for the stress terms into Eqns. 2.36 yields a solution for the vertically averaged cumulus boundary layer flow:

$$-fV' = -\frac{g}{a \cos \phi} \left[-\frac{nH_{BL}}{2} \left(1 - \frac{2\gamma}{3} \right) \frac{\partial T'_s}{\partial \lambda} \right] - \epsilon U' \quad (2.37)$$

$$fU' = -\frac{g}{a} \left[-\frac{nH_{BL}}{2} \left(1 - \frac{2\gamma}{3} \right) \frac{\partial T'_s}{\partial \phi} \right] - \epsilon V'. \quad (2.38)$$

Denoting the first two expressions on the RHS of Eqns. 2.37 and 2.38 by \tilde{T}_x and \tilde{T}_y respectively, the solution of these equations is:

$$U' = \frac{\epsilon \tilde{T}_x + f \tilde{T}_y}{\epsilon^2 + f^2} \quad (2.39)$$

$$V' = -\frac{f \tilde{T}_x - \epsilon \tilde{T}_y}{\epsilon^2 + f^2}. \quad (2.40)$$

The surface perturbation boundary layer flow field is directly related to the surface perturbation temperature field. The generation of flow by the surface eddy temperature distribution is then balanced by the Coriolis and drag terms. The cumulus boundary layer mean drag coefficient, ϵ , is taken to be $(2.5 \text{ days})^{-1}$. This is important on and near the equator where the Coriolis force is close to zero, and the dynamical balance is predominantly between the flow from the SST induced cumulus boundary layer pressure field and the linear drag.

A second and perhaps more realistic approach to the problem is to assume that the low-level

convergence forms some part of an implicit cumulus mass flux. The first representation does this in a sense but the redistribution of the convergent mass is instantaneous and has no perceptible effect on the circulation. By allowing a finite time to adjust to this convergent mass the depth of the local boundary layer is increased to accommodate it. It is possible to represent this effect by allowing the 700 mb surface near the top of the cumulus boundary layer to vary in height. In the steady state situation the mass flux associated with the low level convergence is given as

$$M'_c = - \int_0^{Z_T} \nabla \cdot \rho u dz = - \frac{H_{BL}\rho}{a \cos \phi} \left[\frac{\partial U'}{\partial \lambda} + \frac{\partial(V' \cos \phi)}{\partial \phi} \right]. \quad (2.41)$$

Continuity tells us that any horizontal mass convergence must be balanced by cumulus mass flux out of the boundary layer into the free troposphere occurring over some finite time scale τ_c . This balancing by cumulus mass flux can be expressed as an increase in the column density, requiring an increase in the 700mb height perturbation, h' , such that:

$$\rho \frac{\partial h'}{\partial t} = \tau_c \frac{\partial M'_c}{\partial t}. \quad (2.42)$$

Therefore, in equilibrium and combining Eqns. 2.41 and 2.42 this mass balance can be expressed as:

$$h' = -\tau_c \frac{H_{BL}\rho}{a \cos \phi} \left[\frac{\partial U'}{\partial \lambda} + \frac{\partial(V' \cos \phi)}{\partial \phi} \right]. \quad (2.43)$$

Here τ_c is the adjustment time, creating a so called *back pressure* which is conveyed through an increase in the height of the 700 mb surface. The resulting cumulus boundary layer flow can now be expressed both in terms of the surface temperature field and variations in the height of the 700 mb surface as

$$-fV' = -\frac{g}{a \cos \phi} \left[(2 - n[T_s] + n\alpha H_0) \frac{\partial h'}{\partial \lambda} \right. \quad (2.44)$$

$$\left. - \frac{nH_{BL}}{2} \left(1 - \frac{2\gamma}{3} \right) \frac{\partial T'_s}{\partial \lambda} \right] - \epsilon U'$$

$$fU' = -\frac{g}{a} \left[(2 - n[T_s] + n\alpha H_{BL}) \frac{\partial h'}{\partial \phi} \right. \quad (2.45)$$

$$\left. - \frac{nH_{BL}}{2} \left(1 - \frac{2\gamma}{3} \right) \frac{\partial T'_s}{\partial \phi} - \frac{nh'}{2} \frac{\partial [T_s]}{\partial \phi} \right] - \epsilon V'.$$

This model configuration, when forced with observed SSTs, recreates much of the observed distribution of the boundary layer flow field. A large part of the tropical mass convergence is found to be forced as a direct consequence of the surface temperature distribution, without inclusion of any latent heating processes.

2.5 Comparison of Simplified Models

The simple linear steady state β -plane models of both Gill (1980) (hereafter denoted G) and Lindzen and Nigam (1987) (hereafter denoted LN) give flow solutions which are of the correct magnitude and spatial coherence compared to observations. These models are very similar in their dynamics but very different in the way they specify the forcing, so it is somewhat surprising their results agree and are quite realistic. In particular values of damping applied to the thermodynamic variables differ dramatically such that the formulation of LN gives a relaxation time scale of 30 minutes on the boundary layer height whereas that of G is a damping of $(2.5 \text{ days})^{-1}$, the same as the dynamical friction time scale. References to height, H_0 , in G pertain to an equivalent depth of a particular vertical mode in a shallow water system, i.e. the first baroclinic mode, whereas in LN references to height, H_{BL} , pertain explicitly to the depth of the boundary layer. Additionally the forcing in G is applied to the height or thermodynamic equation whereas in LN the forcing is applied to the momentum equations.

Analysis of the similarity of the simplified models used in numerous modelling studies was carried out by Neelin (1989) and Battisti *et al.* (1999). It was found to be possible to cast both models in a similar mathematical way such that the major differences could be highlighted, even though the physical interpretation of the models differ markedly. This is done essentially, by making the momentum equation in LN equivalent to that of G:

$$\epsilon_D \mathbf{U} + \beta y \mathbf{k} \times \mathbf{U} = -\nabla \Phi_{LN}, \quad (2.46)$$

allowing the forcing terms to be applied to the thermodynamic equation. Again casting the thermodynamic equation in the same way as the low-level form of G yields the following

expression

$$\epsilon_D \Phi_{LN} + c_{LN}^2 \nabla \cdot \mathbf{U} = -\epsilon_D \Gamma_{LN} T'_v(x, y), \quad (2.47)$$

where

$$c_{LN}^2 = g H_{BL} \left(1 + \frac{\alpha H_0}{\bar{T}_s} \right) \frac{\epsilon_D}{\tau_c} \simeq g H_0 \frac{\epsilon_D}{\tau_c} \equiv c_{BL}^2 \frac{\epsilon_D}{\tau_c}. \quad (2.48)$$

Differences between the G and LN formulation can be seen in the basic wave speed of the disturbances and the form of the thermodynamic forcing. The phase speed for the LN model, C_{LN} , is then essentially the phase speed of a shallow water mode with an equivalent depth, H_{BL} , but then scaled by the ratio of the momentum and thermodynamic time scales. There are some unanswered questions as to how to interpret the response of the two formally equivalent shallow water equation models. The formulation of G assumes that the flow is driven entirely in response to latent heating with the vague assumption that the position and strength of this heating is related to the underlying SST. In LN, however, any latent heating that occurs above the boundary layer in response to anomalous convective venting from the top of the boundary layer drives the tropospheric circulation and has no effect on the boundary layer flow. The boundary layer flow is then essentially decoupled from the tropospheric flow and the extremely rapid venting time, τ_C , is compensated for by a reduced gravity wave speed c_{BL} .

In both the G and LN models the relaxation time scale applied to the thermodynamic or height equation does not depend on whether or not a region is convecting. This should be an important consideration as non-convective regions are governed more by slower time scales associated with radiative processes and mixing out of the tropical boundary layer by inefficient entrainment. Therefore, a relaxation time scale for the depth of the boundary layer should be based upon a pre-diagnosis of whether convection is occurring. A scheme such as this is developed in Battisti *et al.* (1999) where rapid venting to the troposphere in a reduced gravity model exists in the presence of convection, whereas in non-convecting regions restoration of the boundary layer height is assumed to be by slower entrainment processes. The boundary layer model is able to reproduce characteristics of the observed flow but with much more realistic parameter values, unlike the values used in G and LN.

2.6 Mechanisms for Remote Forcing

The previous section concentrated primarily on the direct response to tropical thermal forcing, that is tropical circulation anomalies resulting from the large-scale adjustment to the effects of tropical convection in the environment of an equatorial β plane. However, as discussed in Chapter 1, many disturbances are able to propagate out of the tropics and influence regions remote from the original tropical forcing. Addressing this problem requires consideration of global scales and the effect of the mean flow of the atmosphere which is stronger in the mid-latitudes than in the tropics in addition to being predominantly westerly rather than easterly.

The first step in understanding any tropical-extratropical interaction is to determine whether tropical anomalies are actually able to even reach and influence the sub-tropics. The upper-tropospheric divergence which usually results from many tropical convective events can be thought of as forcing the vertical component of absolute vorticity, as given in the approximate vorticity equation:

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla\right) \zeta = -\zeta D. \quad (2.49)$$

Splitting the velocity vector \mathbf{v} into its rotational and divergent components, $\mathbf{v}_\psi + \mathbf{v}_\chi$, allows the rotational part of the flow, which is the dominant component of forced Rossby waves, to be determined in terms of a forcing by the divergent part of the flow, which is the dominant component of the convective outflow:

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v}_\psi \cdot \nabla\right) \zeta = -\zeta D - \mathbf{v}_\chi \cdot \nabla \zeta = RWS. \quad (2.50)$$

RWS is the Rossby wave source and gives a quantitative assessment of the effectiveness of an area of upper-tropospheric divergence in generating planetary Rossby wave disturbances. The first term on the right hand side of Eqn. 2.50 includes the expression $-\zeta D$ which is the simple dominant vorticity balance as outlined in Section 2.2. However, the effect of relative vorticity is also included through the term $-\xi D$, and depending on the sign and magnitude of the relative vorticity, may enhance or reduce the Rossby wave source. The second term on the RHS of Eqn. 2.50 predicts a strong forcing of rotational flow if the poleward divergent flow is embedded in a region of strong poleward gradient of absolute

vorticity, which results predominantly from a strong subtropical westerly jet. Another interpretation is that the divergent flow advects the absolute vorticity contours poleward to strengthen the sub-tropical jet. Therefore if the upper-tropospheric tropical divergence is able to penetrate into the sub-tropical jet regions then the possibility of Rossby wave radiation out of the tropics is increased.

Sardeshmukh and Hoskins (1988) investigated the effect of Rossby wave generation from tropical divergence by examining the Rossby wave source which resulted from a specified tropical heating embedded in a steady three dimensional flow. They found that the Rossby wave source perturbation due to this heating extended over a much larger region than the heating itself and, as predicted from the above theory, was strongest in regions of strong and sharp westerly jets. Also of note was the hemispheric symmetry of the Rossby wave source even for an asymmetric tropical heating. The strongest sub-tropical Rossby wave source occurs on the tight absolute vorticity gradients of the quasi-steady east Asia jet and so is relatively insensitive to the position of the tropical heating anomaly in the western and central Pacific.

The correct specification of the Rossby wave source is crucial if the tropical effects on the extra-tropics are to be modelled accurately, and also if there is to be longer term predictability in the extratropical atmosphere then mechanisms for tropical-extratropical interaction will become a major priority. The nature of the Rossby waves which do and do not propagate out of the tropics have also been the subject of many studies, and depend crucially on the prevailing mean flow. In particular as mentioned in Section 2.1, the variation of coriolis parameter in the tropics acts as a wave guide trapping certain classes of waves excited in the tropics. However some waves are able to strongly propagate out of the tropics and impact the extra-tropical climate.

In order to understand the propagation characteristics of planetary Rossby waves emanating from the tropics, it is necessary to look at the wavenumber-frequency characteristics of these waves. Since this wave propagation has a barotropic character, like the equivalent barotropic structure of stationary extra-tropical waves where circulation perturbations are similar throughout the depth, then it is useful to look at this propagation in a barotropic framework.

The steady barotropic vorticity equation linearised about a zonal mean flow, U , in the

absence of any forcing can be written as

$$\frac{\partial \xi'}{\partial t} + U \frac{\partial \xi'}{\partial x} + \beta \frac{\partial \psi'}{\partial x} = 0, \quad (2.51)$$

where prime quantities are perturbations to the mean flow. Seeking solutions of the form

$$\xi' = \xi_0 \exp i(kx + ly - \omega t), \quad (2.52)$$

yields an expression for the dispersion relationship

$$\omega = Uk - \frac{\beta k}{K^2}, \quad (2.53)$$

which pertains to propagating Rossby waves. It therefore follows that the phase speed is given by

$$c = \frac{\omega}{k} = U - \frac{\beta}{K^2}, \quad (2.54)$$

showing that the longest waves propagate fastest and westwards relative to the basic flow. For stationary Rossby waves the stationary total wavenumber is given by

$$K_s = \left(\frac{\beta}{U} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}}. \quad (2.55)$$

The group velocity vector $\mathbf{C}_g = (\partial\omega/\partial k, \partial\omega/\partial l)$ describes the speed and direction of the wave energy propagation of stationary waves and using Eqn. 2.53 and Eqn. 2.55 can be written as

$$c_{gx} = \frac{2\beta k^2}{K_s^4} = \frac{2Uk^2}{K_s^2} \quad (2.56)$$

$$c_{gy} = \frac{2\beta kl}{K_s^4} = \frac{2Ukl}{K_s^2}. \quad (2.57)$$

Then the direction of planetary wave propagation makes an angle with the zonal direction of $\tan^{-1}(c_{gy}/c_{gx}) = \tan^{-1}(l/k)$. Concentrating on stationary waves where the phase speed is zero and applying the WKBJ approximation, where the waves are considered to be locally plane waves propagating in a slowly-varying medium, we can gain a greater insight into their evolution. By making the problem longitude independent it then becomes a case where k

is conserved and l varies with latitude.

As Rossby waves propagate polewards they move into a region of lower β so that, from Eqn. 2.55, K_s decreases. This implies an associated decrease in l , which implies an increased meridional scale for the wave. The direction of wave propagation is also effected such that, from Eqn. 2.57, the direction becomes more zonal. This process is continued and a so called turning point is reached where the waves become completely zonally oriented where $K_s = k$ and $l = 0$. Further propagation will see these waves propagate back into the tropical region and the ray paths of these waves approximately follow great circles.

For latitudinally varying zonal flows a critical point exists in the zonal flow field where the speed of the zonal jet equals the phase speed of the waves. For stationary waves this therefore occurs at $U = 0$. As the waves propagate into this region K_s , and therefore l , approach infinity which implies that the direction of propagation becomes meridional and the group velocity tends to zero. In this region linear theory breaks down.

Hoskins and Karoly (1981) examine the global response to an idealised tropical heating in a linearised steady state five-layer baroclinic model. They found that for a low-latitude tropical heat source embedded in a climatological 3-D flow the shorter wavelength propagating features were, as predicted, trapped in the tropical wave guide equatorwards of the poleward flank of the sub-tropical jet. However, long wavelength disturbances were able to propagate polewards and eastwards out of the tropical region to give the equivalent barotropic stationary Rossby wave trains that are often observed downstream from tropical heating sources. Simple barotropic ray tracing experiments also reveal the separation of scales with disturbances of zonal wave numbers 1 to 3 able to propagate out of the tropics into higher latitudes, but at a smaller group velocity than disturbances of zonal wavenumber 4 and greater, which remain trapped and propagate predominantly eastwards and back towards the equator.

2.7 GCM Experiments

Recently GCMs have been used to model and predict the remote response to tropical SSTs. In particular, understanding the response to patterns of SST associated with the ENSO

phenomena has been the thrust of numerous modelling studies both in terms of the tropical-extratropical teleconnections (Hoerling *et al.*, 1997, Livezey *et al.*, 1997), and tropical-tropical teleconnections (Ju and Slingo, 1995, Soman and Slingo, 1997). In the tropical regions the emphasis has been on the pattern of rainfall suppression and enhancement associated with ENSO SST distributions.

Ju and Slingo (1995) show how the evolution of the Asian summer monsoon is sensitive to both the direct and indirect response to ENSO SST anomalies. As with other studies such as Hoerling *et al.* (1997) there is considerable non-linearity in the response to El Niño and La Niña conditions. They find that during El Niño conditions the mechanism that leads to weakening of the Asian summer monsoon rains results because of modulation of the Pacific basin Walker circulation. The enhanced convection in the central Pacific leads to anomalous subsidence in the Asian monsoon region. During La Niña conditions, however, the reverse of these circumstances does not seem to occur. Such studies suggest a strong role for Walker type circulations in communicating a remote response to SST anomalies throughout the tropics.

An alternative approach to understanding the mechanisms which determine a GCMs response to observed SST anomalies has been performed in studies such as Branstator (1985), where a linear non-divergent barotropic vorticity model is forced with a realistic vorticity source in the tropics, representative of the local upper-tropospheric response to realistic SST anomalies. Much of the dominant GCM response can be reproduced in such a simplified model.

The importance of an accurate climatology is also revealed by GCM sensitivity experiments in studies such as Palmer and Mansfield (1986), where differences such as including envelope or mean orography result in different interactions with the mean flow. In the former case the PNA pattern is established whereas in the latter the PNA pattern is absent.

GCM experiments also serve to reveal inadequacies of simpler models. One such inadequacy is that GCMs generally reveal a non-linear relation between the magnitude of a heating anomaly and the associated response, whereas simpler theory assumes more linearity. Another difference is that the position of the response pattern does not simply shift with the position of the heating region. This result also comes out of some simpler modelling studies (e.g. Sardeshmukh and Hoskins, 1988).

2.8 The Unified Model

The main thrust of this thesis is the analysis of experiments using the UKMO Unified Model (UM) (Cullen, 1993) in its atmosphere only configuration. This is the system used for both the operational and climate forecasts at the UKMO and is a state of the art global numerical general circulation model. The version of the model used is referred to as HadAM2B.

2.8.1 General Setup and Parameterizations

The model integrates the hydrostatic primitive equations of motion, using approximations which are accurate on planetary scales, and solves them in grid point space on an Arakawa 'B' grid using spherical polar coordinates. The horizontal resolution is 3.75° longitude by 2.5° latitude, giving 73 regular spaced grid-points in latitude and 96 in longitude. This translates to a spatial resolution of about 400 km by 300 km on the equator. The vertical resolution is 19 hybrid levels which are terrain following in the lowest levels, a multiple of pressure at upper-levels, and a combination of both in the intermediate levels.

A split-explicit finite-difference scheme is used, with three adjustment steps per advection step. In each adjustment step the pressure, temperature, and winds are updated using the pressure gradient. The average horizontal wind over the adjustment step is used in the Heun advection scheme which conserves mass-weighted linear quantities and mass-weighted second moments of advected quantities. The scheme is fourth-order accurate at low wind speeds and second-order accurate at high wind speeds in order to ensure stability.

As with all climate GCMs the large horizontal grid spacing means that many processes cannot be resolved explicitly and representation or parameterization of these processes by grid-point variables has to be carried out. A brief description of the main parameterizations in the Unified Model relevant to this study are described here.

Convective processes are parameterized using a penetrative mass flux convection scheme which incorporates dry and moist convection and all convective cloud types (Gregory and Rowntree, 1990). A bulk cloud model is used to represent an ensemble of convective clouds and the initial mass flux from layer k to $k+1$ is related to the stability of the initial convecting

layer such that

$$M_I = \frac{3.33 \times 10^{-7} p_*^2 ((\theta_V^{PMOIST})_{K+1} - (\theta_V^E)_{K+1} - b)}{\Delta p_{k+\frac{1}{2}}} \quad (2.58)$$

where $(\theta_V^{PMOIST})_{K+1}$ is the virtual temperature of the ascending parcel at the next level, $(\theta_V^E)_{K+1}$ is the virtual potential temperature of the convecting environment, also at the next layer and b is the buoyancy excess (usually 0.2 K). Therefore the mass flux is proportional to the temperature excess between the convecting parcel and the environment, above and beyond b , on being lifted from level k to $k+1$. The scheme also represents the effects of entrainment of environmental air and the detrainment of convecting air, in addition to the effects of downdraughts.

The surface scheme as described in Smith (1993) represents the mean vertical surface turbulent flux, between the surface (level 0) and model level 1, of any conserved quantity, Γ , by the bulk transfer formulation

$$\frac{F_{*x}}{\rho_*} \equiv (\overline{w'\Gamma'})_* = -c_x |\mathbf{v}_1 - \mathbf{v}_0| (\Gamma_1 - \Gamma_0), \quad (2.59)$$

where c_x is the turbulent surface exchange or bulk transfer coefficient which is a function of stability, surface roughness, and other surface characterising parameters. The turbulent fluxes and increments due to turbulent mixing above the surface in the boundary layer are represented using the standard local mixing type scheme. Here the turbulent flux of a conserved quantity is parameterized using a first-order turbulence closure of the form

$$\frac{F_x}{\rho} \equiv (\overline{w'\Gamma'}) = -K_\Gamma \frac{\partial \Gamma}{\partial z}, \quad (2.60)$$

where K_Γ is the turbulent mixing coefficient for Γ which is a function of mixing length, the local wind shear and stability.

In the UM radiation scheme (Ingram, 1995) seven spectral divisions, grouped into six bands, are used to calculate the long-wave radiative properties of three gases: water vapour (in its three phases), ozone, and carbon dioxide. Clouds are interactive with the scheme by emitting long-wave radiation at the temperature of the cloud top and cloud bottom for optically dense clouds, with contribution from the cloud depth in optically thin clouds. The

short-wave scheme represents interaction of radiation with the same three gases as the long-wave scheme, but this time in 4 spectral bands. Again clouds are interactive, with their radiative properties being a function of liquid water path and the equivalent radius of the drop size distribution. In both radiation schemes clouds in different layers are assumed to overlap randomly if there exists cloud-free layers between them. In the long-wave scheme when clouds exist in adjacent layers an assumption of maximum vertical overlap is assumed, whereas the short-wave scheme retains a random overlap approximation.

2.8.2 An Aqua-Planet Version of the UM

Throughout this chapter a wide range of methodologies, models and diagnostic tools have been described. Each approach to modelling the tropics explains individual components of the system and elucidates different processes and mechanisms responsible for the climate interactions of the tropics. They vary from a simple conceptual model of the direct response to a simple forcing configuration, to state of the art GCMs with full physical and dynamical representations of the atmosphere responding to climatological SSTs. The simplest approach isolates a particular mechanism which is relevant to that particular framework, but does not tell the whole story as interactions with other mechanism may dramatically change its nature. On the other hand a full GCM includes these important interactions but the complexity of the model and boundary conditions makes it problematic to pin down the role of particular processes and the cause and effect interactions which exist.

It becomes apparent, therefore, that a gap exists in the suite of approaches that are generally used to investigate the tropical climate mechanisms. Ideally, as an intermediate approach one would like the simple boundary conditions and forcing functions that generally exist in the more simplified models, but with the more numerous processes and process interactions represented in an atmospheric GCM.

With this in mind a simplified version of the UM is used in this study with experiments designed to investigate some of the problems outlined and questions posed in Chapter 1. The model is used in an aqua-planet configuration with all the land points being replaced by ocean points such that the surface drag coefficients, albedo and evaporation characteristics are homogeneous over the globe. Land points are retained at each pole which is necessary in order to satisfy the current requirement in the UM that there must be at least one land

Figure 2.5: Zonally averaged daily mean insolation (in Wm^{-2}) at the top of the atmosphere for the aqua-planet experiments. Values are fixed at equinoctial March 19th conditions.

point in the model domain, so that problems do not arise with data array sizes in the numerical code.

A further simplification is obtained by fixing the solar radiation at a particular date. This then removes much of the complication due to solar forced variability. The date at which the insolation becomes fixed is at the spring equinox on 19th March, which puts the sun overhead at the equator as shown in Fig. 2.5. Additionally this produces another desirable simplification by providing approximate hemispheric symmetry of insolation forcing.

The approach of all the experiments is to investigate the response to different SST distributions which emphasise, but in a more simplified and obvious way, various aspects of the observed tropical SST. This includes varying the pole to equator SST gradient and including tropical SST anomalies which vary in size, magnitude, position, and shape. By performing such simplified experiments, but in a complicated non-linear framework, it should be possible to get a much clearer signal of the atmospheric response to SST both in terms of the mean response and the variability of the response.

In the past such simplified GCM experimentation would have proved too costly to perform, but recent increases in computing power and decreased cost of CPU time allow many experiments of this type to be carried out at reasonable cost.

Much of the investigation and analysis of the experiments performed will centre strongly around the response of tropical convection to SSTs and the role of organised convection in the resulting atmospheric circulation. This means that the convection scheme used in the UM will be taken to be an accurate representation of convection in the real atmosphere, but

this is by no means certain. In fact the parameterization of convection is one of the most uncertain and least understood processes in most GCMs and is reflected in the number of fundamentally different schemes used in GCMs at institutes around the globe. However, although it will not form part of this study, an aqua-planet GCM such as this provides an ideal test bed in which different parameterization schemes, not just for convection, can be inter-compared.

Chapter 3

The Zonally Averaged Circulation

3.1 Introduction

In general the largest spatial variation of atmospheric quantities occurs in the vertical and meridional directions. Analysis of the zonal mean circulation is therefore a useful exercise and provides an insight into the dominant large-scale circulations, in particular the Hadley circulation. To a first approximation the tropical zonal mean circulation can be understood without knowledge of any zonal variations, such as the effects of large-scale eddies in the mid-latitudes or the land-sea distribution.

Since insolation from the sun heats the tropics more than the poles then the simplest interpretation of the Hadley circulation is the rising of warm air near the equator and the descent of cold air towards the poles with connecting equatorward flow near the surface and poleward flow aloft. This circulatory response was first proposed as the reason for the equatorward trade winds in the tropics by Halley (1686) and then Hadley (1735) who realised that the eastward component of the trade winds was due to angular momentum conservation. Even this simple description of the flow gives rise to a mechanism by which the atmosphere maintains a quasi-steady meridional temperature distribution in the presence of differential heating. Differences between the hemispheres such as seasonality and the land sea distribution are reflected in the zonal mean circulation. The complete picture is somewhat more complicated than this but the zonally averaged climate gives a reasonable first approximation to the global circulation.

3.2 Determining the Nature of the ITCZ

The upward branch of the Hadley circulation is co-located with the mean position of the ITCZ and considered by many to be the driving force responsible for the Hadley circulation. The time-mean ITCZ is formed due to the net effect of many small scale convective events occurring on time scales of hours. This gives rise to two possible concepts of the Hadley Circulation/ITCZ system. Firstly, that the ITCZ and Hadley circulation can only be considered in a mutually balanced sense on long time scales. This is the idea employed by Schneider and Lindzen (1977), Schneider (1977), Held and Hou (1980) and in the aqua-planet experiments of Hess *et al.* (1993). Secondly, that the individual synoptic convective events generate their own individual circulation which can be considered to be a local Hadley circulation. These convective events are often observed to exist on shorter time scales in a larger scale organisation identifiable as an ITCZ. However, emphasis will be put on the larger time scale maintenance of the ITCZ and Hadley circulation identifiable in the seasonal zonal mean.

3.3 Representation of Convection

Convection in the tropical atmosphere is important in many respects. The release of latent heat within cumulus clouds contributes to driving tropical circulations on time and length scales much greater than that of the individual cloud. The role of convection is to stabilise the tropical atmosphere, and in the process transport moisture, momentum, and heat high into the troposphere. Cumulus convection modifies the large-scale temperature and moisture fields through detrainment and induced subsidence in the environment. For these reasons and many others it is vital that the effects of convection are accurately represented in climate GCMs in order to obtain realistic atmospheric structures, rainfall rates and forced circulations.

At present computational power constraints limit the horizontal grid spacing of GCMs to ≈ 100 km at best. Since individual convective elements are of the order 0.1-10 km in horizontal scale then GCMs are not able to explicitly resolve convection. It is, therefore, necessary to parameterize convection occurring within each model grid box and represent its effects in

terms of changes to the large-scale variables of each grid box. Parameterizing convection in this way allows the model to retain a realistic vertical profile of temperature and moisture in addition to preventing whole grid box saturation and unrealistic temperature and moisture profiles.

Ideally a convection scheme should accurately represent the large-scale effects of convection but, at the same time, be as physically based as possible. This is not always possible and a certain amount of tuning is performed with schemes to ensure close agreement with observations. Many theories have been proposed in order to understand the mechanisms which initiate and maintain convection. A review of cumulus convection parameterization appears in Frank (1983) and a short summary of different convection schemes will be given here.

Parameterization schemes vary from the simplest adjustment scheme of Manabe *et al.* (1965) to the much more complex quasi-equilibrium and cloud spectra schemes of Arakawa and Schubert (1974). The whole approach to the parameterization of convection is divided into two areas. Firstly how is convection triggered initially releasing convective available potential energy in the process. Secondly, what is the vertical distribution of this released energy within cumulus clouds, and its effect on the large-scale variables at each level of the model.

The early adjustment scheme of Manabe *et al.* (1965) was intended to provide the simplest representation of convection, without representing any explicit physical mechanisms, in order to constrain the model to something close to reality. The closure is given by changes in the vertical lapse rate at a grid point such that dry convection adjusts the temperature profile to a dry adiabat and moist convection adjusts the saturated temperature profile to a constant equivalent potential temperature (θ_e) adiabat in a specified time (<1 hour). The drawbacks of this scheme are that a moist adiabat is rarely observed in the tropics and it is not a good scheme for investigating interactions between convection and the large-scale. Another approach is to use a closure based upon total column moisture convergence. Charney and Eliassen (1964) used this closure in their theory of Conditional Instability of the Second Kind (CISK), where the convective elements provide heating to drive the larger-scale circulation while larger-scale frictional convergence at low-levels within the larger-scale system provides moisture to maintain the cumulus convection. Kuo (1974) developed

a similar scheme where a proportion of the column moisture convergence and grid-box evaporation is rained out of the column, with the remaining proportion being distributed throughout the column by the use of a cloud model. However, this partitioning of moisture convergence between moistening and rainfall is arbitrary and tends to be tuned to agree with observations, as well as being grid-scale dependent.

A further more sophisticated scheme was developed by Arakawa and Schubert (1974), who employed a quasi-equilibrium closure hypothesis. The cloud model employs a spectral representation of the different cloud types within each grid box. The quasi-equilibrium hypothesis assumes that the whole cloud ensemble adjusts to changes in the grid-scale flow such that changes to a calculated variable called the cloud work function are minimised. This cloud work function represents the efficiency of kinetic energy generation and by minimising its value a realistic conditionally unstable profile is maintained at each convecting grid point. The assumption is also scale dependent with increasing accuracy for large grid spacing. This scheme is probably the most complex existing convection scheme and is used in the UCLA general circulation model.

More recent schemes have started to take a simpler approach to the cumulus parameterization problem by ensuring that the vertical structure of temperature and humidity are as realistic as possible. This was the approach taken by Betts (1986), who again uses a quasi-equilibrium hypothesis similar to that of Arakawa and Schubert (1974) but performs a relaxation similar to Manabe *et al.* (1965). The moisture and temperature fields are relaxed towards an observed quasi-equilibrium thermodynamic structure, but over a period of about 2 hours and not within a model time-step. This observed thermodynamic structure is partly specified and partly internally determined. This scheme has in a sense a reduced physical representation of convection by including observed thermodynamic structure but it does ensure a more accurate end result of the convective processes. Unfortunately when used in climate models it is not clear what the specified part of the thermodynamic structure should be.

These different theories for the representation of convection in GCMs are presented in order to illustrate the uncertain and difficult nature of the subject. In particular, using a different scheme than the one used in the aqua-planet will almost certainly lead to quantitatively and possibly qualitatively different results.

The convection scheme incorporated into the UM is based upon a scheme proposed by Gregory and Rowntree (1990). It is a mass flux convection scheme employing parcel theory and aims to represent the whole range of cumulus clouds through the use of a bulk cloud model. The cloud model represents the bulk properties of an ensemble of clouds by incorporating vertical profiles of entrainment and detrainment properties. The closure assumption is based upon achieving a threshold buoyancy equivalent to a temperature excess above that of the environment of 0.2 K, on being lifted from one model level to the next. The initial mass flux associated with a triggered ascending parcel is proportional to the excess buoyancy over the environment.

3.4 Zonal Mean Observations

As mentioned in Section 3.2, an insight into the dynamical processes dominant within the global circulation can be gained just by examining the observed zonal mean climate. Fig. 3.1 shows the zonal mean zonal wind and temperature as determined from 15 years of ERA data (Gibson *et al.*, 1997). The first obvious point of interest is the asymmetry between hemispheres both in the seasonal averages (a), (b) and in the annual average (c). As well as the asymmetric nature of the solar forcing this emphasises the different land/sea contrasts and therefore surface heat capacity distribution within each hemisphere. The vertical structure of the mid-latitude part of the westerly jet in the southern hemisphere is more barotropic in nature than the northern hemisphere. This is arguably a consequence of the reduced drag over the predominantly ocean covered southern hemisphere mid-latitudes, leading to stronger near surface winds.

The variation in the structure of the sub-tropical jets between the solstice seasons is also markedly different in each hemisphere. The southern hemisphere jet has a distinctly different structure in each season with the maximum zonal wind moving between 46°S and 29°S with a double jet in winter, whereas the northern hemisphere jet retains the same structure between seasons with the jet maximum only moving between 44°N and 33°N.

In the annual mean, surface easterlies extend between 30° north and south with mainly surface westerlies poleward of these latitudes. This gives easterlies and westerlies covering approximately equal areas of the globe, which is consistent with the long term necessity

Figure 3.1: 15 year climatology (1979-1993) from the ECMWF Re-Analysis (ERA) project of zonal mean zonal wind (heavy contours, interval 5 ms^{-1}) and temperature (light contours, zero contour heavy, interval 5° C) for (a) December, January, February (DJF); (b) June, July, August (JJA); (c) annual mean.

that there be no net torque applied to the earth from the atmosphere.

Of particular note is the tropical zonal wind in the Indian monsoon season (JJA) where the intense tropical easterly upper-tropospheric jet and low-level monsoon westerlies north of the equator at 7°N are seen in the zonal mean for this period. The asymmetric stratospheric circulation can also be identified in JJA with the strong westerly polar night jet in the southern hemisphere maximising at 60°S and an easterly jet in the northern hemispheric stratosphere. A reversal of sign between hemispheres occurs in DJF.

Inspection of the annual average zonal mean temperature reveals the impact of the greater northern hemispheric land mass and lower surface heat capacity. The near surface temperature is maximised slightly in the northern hemisphere representing the large surface land temperatures attained over the extensive land area in the sub-tropics during northern summer (JJA).

The coldest temperatures in all seasons are seen near the tropical tropopause at around 120mb. These fall below -75°C in both solstice seasons and are a consequence of the intense deep convection in the tropical region.

Examination of the zonally averaged zonal wind and temperature reveals that the regions of largest latitudinal gradient in temperature are coincident with those of the largest vertical gradient of zonal wind. It can be shown that the two fields are indeed close to a state of *thermal wind balance* given by,

$$\frac{\partial[u]}{\partial z} = -\frac{g}{fT} \frac{\partial[T]}{\partial y}, \quad (3.1)$$

to within a few degrees of the equator.

Another aspect of the observed zonal mean climate is the mean meridional circulation of the atmosphere (Fig. 3.2) which illustrates the mass transport of the axisymmetric circulations of the atmosphere. The circulation in each solstice season is dominated by a single Hadley circulation cell in the winter hemisphere. The meridional wind vectors show that each cell has ascent in the summer hemisphere coincident with the climatological position of the ITCZ along with low level inflow crossing the equator. This is particularly strong in northern winter reflecting the large low-level cross equatorial mass flow in the

Indian monsoon region during this period. Theory presented in Lindzen and Hou (1988) predicts that when the region of ascent and convective heating is off the equator this will force a wider and much more intense Hadley cell on the winter hemispheric side of the ascent. Analysis shows that the Hadley cells can be viewed as the action of the atmosphere trying to force the tropospheric temperature away from a radiative equilibrium temperature profile set by the latitudinal variation of solar heating (Held and Hou, 1980). This effect is greater in the winter hemisphere where the difference between the observed and radiative equilibrium temperature is larger. This mechanism will be investigated further. Thermally indirect mid-latitude Ferrel cells are observable poleward of about 30°N and S, but their mass transport is an order of magnitude smaller than the Hadley cells.

In the annual mean the single Hadley cells which dominate the solstice seasons cancel somewhat to give a more symmetric picture with a weaker cell in both hemispheres. The circulation is not perfectly symmetric about the equator as the ascent is centred at about 7°N . This is coincident with the mean position of the ITCZ which, particularly over the oceans, has a propensity to remain north of the equator throughout the year. Over land, however, the ITCZ tends to follow the seasonal march of the sun. Fig. 3.3 shows the zonal mean precipitation (taken from the Xie and Arkin (1996) 16 year climatology) for the two solstice seasons and the annual mean. The most striking feature is the absence of a precipitation maximum over the equator during any period even in the annual mean, which has a maximum at about 6°N consistent with the position of maximum ascent.

3.5 Aqua-Planet Model Studies

Previous to this study there have been several studies investigating the zonal mean climatology of GCMs and simpler models in an aqua-planet configuration. The study of Goswami *et al.* (1984) uses a two dimensional zonally symmetric aqua-planet version of the Goddard Laboratory for Atmospheric Sciences (GLAS) GCM with an earlier version of the Arakawa and Schubert (1974) convection scheme, to investigate the mechanisms which determine the position and strength of the ITCZ. A certain amount of tuning is performed to ensure a steady state solution is achieved which limits the model somewhat. This includes increasing the eddy viscosity and diffusivity coefficients as well as switching off the interactive cloud radiative feedback calculations. The response to imposed SST distributions and prescribed

Figure 3.2: 15 year ERA climatology of mean meridional circulation (contour interval $2 \times 10^{10} \text{ kg s}^{-1}$) and meridional wind vectors (meridional wind scale is ms^{-1} and vertical wind scale is $2 \times \text{mb hr}^{-1}$) for (a) December, January, February (DJF); (b) June, July, August (JJA); and (c) annual.

Figure 3.3: 16 year Xie-Arkin climatology of zonal mean precipitation for the annual mean (solid line), JJA (long dash), and DJF (short dash) (in mm day^{-1}).

latent heating is investigated, with emphasis on the contrasting roles of SST forcing and CISK. In general, SST is responsible for placing a single ITCZ over the warmest water, whereas CISK processes are responsible for giving the narrowest possible meridional scale for the ITCZ of just one model grid point in width. Mass flux within the mean meridional circulation is three times that seen in observations and 80-90% of this mass is transported towards the equator above the boundary layer.

The study by Hayashi and Sumi (1986) uses a zonally symmetric SST distribution, typical of April climatological conditions, in a full three dimensional GCM integration with a Kuo type cumulus parameterization. Their results show two split ITCZs off the equator even with a maximum in SST on the equator.

Swinbank *et al.* (1988) used an earlier version of the UKMO climate model in an aqua-planet configuration to investigate its ability to support a MJO type circulation. In their experiments there is a split double ITCZ feature straddling the equator at 15°N and 15°S , with a maximum in precipitation of 6.3 mm day^{-1} . They also note that the position and strength of the Hadley cells are largely determined by the transient eddy activity. In a similar study by Lau *et al.* (1988) an MJO investigation is undertaken with a simplified GCM forced by a fixed SST profile. This SST profile has a broad maximum of 304 K at the equator, but still gives a single ITCZ over the warmest water on the equator with a precipitation maximum of 5.2 mm day^{-1} .

Numerical experiments performed by Numaguti (1993,1995) use a spectral model with a Kuo cumulus parameterization scheme. He shows that for a flat equatorial meridional SST distribution twin ITCZs are found either side of the equator at 7°N and 7°S . In these

circumstances evaporation is found to be reduced on the equator due to the low wind speeds found there. By removing the wind speed dependence of evaporation the ITCZ is found to collapse to a single precipitation maximum on the equator. However, he repeated the experiment with a moist convective adjustment cumulus parameterization scheme and found that there was a single precipitation peak on the equator, whether the wind speed dependence for evaporation was included or not. The sensitivity to low latitude SST was also examined. In particular, it was found that with a maximum in SST just off the equator a precipitation peak occurred on the opposite (winter) side of the equator. The distribution of the precipitation peak was found to be related to the SST induced convergent flow in the boundary layer, the net supply of moist static energy and the vertical stratification of the atmosphere which is partially determined by the SST.

A comprehensive study of the zonal mean climate of an aqua-planet is carried out in Hess *et al.* (1993). Integrations are performed using an aqua-planet version of the NCAR Community Climate Model (CCM1) to investigate how surface boundary conditions and cumulus adjustment processes affect aspects of the ITCZ and the large-scale circulation. They find that it is the position of the ITCZ that determines the position and strength of the subtropical jets, rather than the strength of the ITCZ precipitation. Using a moist convective adjustment cumulus parameterization scheme gives a single ITCZ on the equator for an observed zonal mean March SST distribution with a precipitation maximum of 14.5 mm day^{-1} . The use of a moisture convergence scheme with the same SST distribution gives twin ITCZs straddling the equator at 6°N and 6°S with a precipitation maximum of 8.5 mm day^{-1} .

The aqua-planet studies clearly demonstrate how the choice of convection scheme strongly influences model results. In particular, the tropical circulation can be altered just by changing the convection scheme. From the studies described this can be as dramatic as a change from a single ITCZ on the equator to twin ITCZs well away from the equator.

In the present study experiments are performed using only the convection scheme of Gregory and Rowntree (1990). However, interpretation of results are carried out knowing full well that it is one possible response to the specified SST forcing, and in no way does it represent any absolute truth. The dependence on the model convection scheme is analysed further in Chapter 7.

3.6 Description of Experiments

3.6.1 Hemispherically Symmetric

The aim of the zonally symmetric experiments is to answer the following questions.

- How is the position and strength of the ITCZ related to the underlying SST?
- Under what circumstances does the model atmosphere prefer a single or double ITCZ feature?
- What are the resulting effects on the large-scale circulation that can be attributed to the characteristics of the ITCZ?

To address these questions a series of three experiments has been performed. These aim to emphasise the roles of SST and SST gradients in forcing the large-scale flow and the ITCZ. As discussed previously the 3-dimensional GCM experiments are forced by a constant SST profile, varying in latitude (ϕ) only, as a lower boundary condition. Each is symmetric about the equator and decays from 300 K there to 273 K at latitude 60°. From 60° to the pole the SST is constant. The three profiles are shown graphically in Fig 3.4 and defined by:

- **EXPERIMENT 1** : SST behaves like ϕ^2 near the equator. This will be referred to as the *Control* profile.

$$SST(\phi) = \begin{cases} 300 K + (273 - 300) \sin^2\left(\frac{3\phi}{2}\right) K & : -\frac{\pi}{3} < \phi < \frac{\pi}{3} \\ 273 K & : \textit{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.2)$$

- **EXPERIMENT 2** : SST decreases linearly from the equator. This will be referred to as the *Peaked* profile.

$$SST(\phi) = \begin{cases} 300 K + (273 - 300) \frac{3\phi}{\pi} K & : -\frac{\pi}{3} < \phi < \frac{\pi}{3} \\ 273 K & : \textit{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.3)$$

Figure 3.4: Zonally averaged SST distributions used to force the GCM in the hemispherically symmetric experiments (in K). Control (solid line), peaked (long dash), flat (short dash).

- **EXPERIMENT 3 :** SST behaves like ϕ^4 near the equator. This will be referred to as the *Flat* profile (although strictly speaking it is only flat at the equator).

$$SST(\phi) = \begin{cases} 300 \text{ K} + (273 - 300) \sin^4\left(\frac{3\phi}{2}\right) \text{ K} & : -\frac{\pi}{3} < \phi < \frac{\pi}{3} \\ 273 \text{ K} & : \textit{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.4)$$

3.6.2 Hemispherically Asymmetric

As the oceanic ITCZ is often observed to be situated off the equator in the northern hemisphere, along with the underlying SST maximum, further experiments have been performed with either the equatorial SST maximum or the insolation maximum positioned off the equator. The asymmetry of the response in the large-scale Hadley circulation is marked when the ITCZ is furthest off the equator, as is the case in the solstice seasons. The questions being addressed in performing these experiments are therefore the following:

- To what extent, if any, would the model ITCZ move off the equator if the SST maximum were no longer on the equator?
- What role does the off equator SST maximum and, associated with this, the meridional SST gradients on the equator have in the asymmetry of the large-scale response?
- Is the ITCZ more sensitive to the position of the SST maximum or the position of the insolation maximum?

Three further experiments have thus been performed, again using SST forcing which varies in latitude only. Two of the experiments no longer have the SST maximum situated on the equator. The SST profiles are each based on the control profile (Eqn. 3.2), behaving like $(\phi - \phi_0)^2$ near its maximum at ϕ_0 and decreasing to zero at 60°N and S. They are shown graphically in Fig. 3.5 and defined by:

- **EXPERIMENT 1** : SST peaks at 5°N . This will be referred to as the *Control-5°N* profile.

$$SST(\phi) = \begin{cases} 300 K + (273 - 300) \sin^2 \left(\frac{90}{55} \left[\phi - \frac{\pi}{36} \right] \right) K & : \frac{\pi}{36} < \phi < \frac{\pi}{3} \\ 300 K + (273 - 300) \sin^2 \left(\frac{90}{65} \left[\phi - \frac{\pi}{36} \right] \right) K & : -\frac{\pi}{3} < \phi < \frac{\pi}{36} \\ 273 K & : \textit{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.5)$$

- **EXPERIMENT 2** : SST peaks at 10°N . This will be referred to as the *Control-10°N* profile.

$$SST(\phi) = \begin{cases} 300 K + (273 - 300) \sin^2 \left(\frac{90}{50} \left[\phi - \frac{\pi}{18} \right] \right) K & : \frac{\pi}{18} < \phi < \frac{\pi}{3} \\ 300 K + (273 - 300) \sin^2 \left(\frac{90}{70} \left[\phi - \frac{\pi}{18} \right] \right) K & : -\frac{\pi}{3} < \phi < \frac{\pi}{18} \\ 273 K & : \textit{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (3.6)$$

- **EXPERIMENT 3** : SST is the control profile peaking at the equator Eqn. (3.2), but forced by perpetual June 21st insolation. This will be referred to as the *Control-June 21st* profile.

The climatology of the control experiment will first be described and similarities with and differences from the observed annual zonal mean climatology will be noted. This will then be followed by discussion of the difference in response between experiments with different near equator SST gradients and maximum SST position to investigate how the precipitation and zonal mean circulation responds to these changes.

Figure 3.5: Zonally averaged SST distributions (in K) used to force the GCM in the hemispherically asymmetric experiments. Control-June 21st (solid line), control-5°N (long dash), control-10°N (short dash)

Figure 3.6: Zonally averaged convective precipitation for integrations with the control profile (solid line), peaked profile (long dash), and the flat profile (short dash) in mm day^{-1} .

3.7 Control Climatology

We are primarily interested in the major differences between the regimes of the different experiments and any similarities with observed magnitudes will be a secondary consideration. In short, the aqua-planet is intended as a tool for understanding the response to SST and the underlying mechanisms responsible for the ITCZ and associated large-scale circulation, not for trying to reproduce the observed climate.

Fig. 3.6 shows the zonally averaged precipitation for each of the three experiments. The control experiment gives a single precipitation peak essentially on the equator, the maximum value being 16.5 mm day^{-1} . This compares with a peak of 7 mm day^{-1} for the observed annual mean (Fig. 3.3). The width of the ITCZ stretches from about 8°N to 8°S which is less confined in latitude than the observed northern hemisphere summer precipitation maximum but more confined than the observed southern hemisphere winter precipitation

maximum.

The zonal mean circulation in the control experiment shows near symmetry between the hemispheres but with some asymmetries present, probably due to the limited length of the one year integration period and insolation forcing which is not exactly hemispherically symmetric. If the experiments were integrated for longer one would expect the climate to become increasingly more symmetric between hemispheres. The zonal wind for the control (Fig. 3.7(a)) has a much stronger than observed (in the annual or seasonal mean) sub-tropical jet with a maximum of 68 ms^{-1} . Its position is equatorward of the annual mean observed position but at the same height, about 200mb. The distribution of surface easterlies and westerlies are also different from observed. The control easterlies are stronger but only extend between 16°N and S, whereas the observed distribution is between 32°N and S. The surface westerlies are stronger than observed, even in the southern hemisphere, consistent with the absence of any continents and extend from 16° to 47° , N and S.

The overall response is, therefore, a pattern of stronger easterlies and westerlies throughout the depth of the troposphere which is squeezed much nearer the equator than observed. This is due to the lack of zonal asymmetric forcing which, in the observed zonal mean, tends to reduce and spread out the strength of the jets in response to the variable strength and position of the Hadley circulation and mid-latitude baroclinicity at different longitudes. The sub-tropical jets in the control experiment are more characteristic of the observed southern hemisphere jet than the northern hemisphere jet. This would probably be expected as the large expanse of ocean and reduced surface drag here is more like the aqua-planet. Therefore, stronger near-surface westerlies in the quasi-barotropic part of the jet, situated poleward of the more baroclinic part of the jet, loosely matches the nature of the observed southern hemisphere jet.

The mean meridional circulation also shows the differences in circulation strength between the control (Fig. 3.8(a)) and observed (Fig. 3.2). The magnitude of the rate of mass transport is some 2.5 to 3 times larger than observed annual mean values. However the magnitude is similar to the dominant cell in JJA which ascends in the northern hemisphere (forming the ITCZ) and descends in the southern hemisphere. The width of the cells are narrower than both the seasonal and annual observed, with the ITCZ ascent region confined nearer to the equator and the subtropical descent region of a similar latitudinal extent to

Figure 3.7: Zonally averaged zonal wind (11 month average, contour interval 5 ms^{-1}) for integrations with (a) control profile; (b) peaked profile; (c) flat profile.

the observed, but which is on the whole closer to the equator.

Briefly, the mid-latitudes exhibit a Ferrel cell in the control which is only 50% stronger than the observed situation in the southern hemisphere, but the maximum is some 10° closer to the equator. Again this demonstrates the very intense axisymmetric circulation due to the latitudinal confinement of zonal asymmetries, and the nature of the equator to pole SST distribution being used to force the model.

3.8 Hemispherically Symmetric Experiment Results

3.8.1 Precipitation

As seen in Fig. 3.6, the results from the peaked and flat experiments when compared with the control experiment, reveal both quantitative and qualitative differences. The peaked profile experiment gives a precipitation maximum also centred on the equator, but the maximum precipitation rate is considerably higher at 31.5 mm day^{-1} and the latitudinal extent is considerably narrower than in the control integration. Although the peak SST on the equator takes the same value in each case, significantly different rainfall distributions and rainfall rates result emphasising the importance of the response to the latitudinal profile of SST. The integrated convective precipitation in the flat experiment is some 10% greater than the control or peaked experiment. This reflects the higher mean SST in the flat experiment which leads to a greater moisture holding capacity of the atmosphere. The strong confinement of the ITCZ in the peaked experiment results due to a redistribution of moisture by the low-level equatorward flow. This can be seen in Fig. 3.9 which shows the zonal mean precipitation and evaporation for the three experiments. Although locally near the equator there is a slight increase in evaporation compared to the control the evaporation within the sub-tropical dry regions is less. The large peak in precipitation is therefore supplied by much stronger moisture convergence centred on the equatorial point which has a precipitation rate twice that of the control.

From inspection of the convective precipitation in the flat experiment it is immediately obvious that not only are the precipitation values different, compared to the control and peaked case, but there is a transition to a completely different regime.

Figure 3.8: Mean meridional mass streamfunction (11 month average, contour interval $2 \times 10^{10} \text{ kg s}^{-1}$) for integrations with (a) control profile; (b) peaked profile; (c) flat profile.

Figure 3.9: Zonal mean convective precipitation (solid line) and evaporation (dashed line) for (a) control; (b) peaked; and (c) flat experiments (in mm day^{-1}).

Firstly, there is no equatorial precipitation maximum and the precipitation rates between 10°N and S are only of the order 4 mm day^{-1} . The precipitation in this region seems to be a mostly local response since the precipitation approximately balances the local evaporation (Fig. 3.9(c)), so there is no supply of moisture from higher latitudes to provide moisture convergence in a preferred region. The atmosphere in this region would therefore seem to be in a state of near local radiative-convective equilibrium where convection periodically acts to stabilise the troposphere, and does not force or respond to a larger-scale circulation.

Secondly, there are two slight peaks in precipitation either side of the equator at 15°N and S with a magnitude of 6.5 mm day^{-1} . One possible interpretation of this is a split ITCZ feature similar to the ITCZ/SPCZ split that can occur in the western and central Pacific. However, these peaks are a considerable distance poleward and may result, at least in part, to interactions with mid-latitude synoptic disturbances. This will be investigated further in Section 3.8.3.

3.8.2 Circulation

Considerable differences also occur in the zonal mean circulation between the three zonally symmetric experiments, consistent with the changes in precipitation. Inspection of the zonal wind (Fig. 3.7) reveals that the peaked experiment does not differ significantly from the control. The upper-level sub-tropical jet maximum is displaced slightly equatorward by some 5° and the magnitude is reduced by $3\text{--}4 \text{ ms}^{-1}$. This is consistent with angular momentum conservation since the latitudinal distance from the poleward edge of the tropical

easterlies to the sub-tropical jet maximum is less in the peaked case. The distribution of surface zonal wind is little changed from the control but the magnitudes are reduced slightly.

The mean meridional circulation (Fig. 3.8) shows the intense dynamical confinement of the ITCZ ascent region, consistent with the narrow precipitation maximum. The maximum value of the mass circulation in the peaked experiment is some 25% greater than the control and also situated at least 2.5° closer to the equator. Integrated tropical precipitation is slightly greater in the peaked experiment than in the control, but the difference is not large enough to be strongly associated with the greater mass circulation in the peaked experiment. Clearly the more intense response in the peaked experiment is due predominantly to the narrow dynamical confinement near the equator and, to a lesser extent, the cycling of a greater mass of air through the Hadley circulation.

The pattern of zonal wind in the flat experiment is, as with the convective precipitation, distinctly different. The sub-tropical jet maxima have migrated poleward to about 48°N and S reaching a much lower magnitude of 42 ms^{-1} . When considering the angular momentum conserving zonal wind between the edge of the tropical easterlies, ϕ_0 , and the westerly jet maxima, ϕ , given by:

$$u = r_e \Omega \frac{\cos^2 \phi_0 - \cos^2 \phi}{\cos \phi}, \quad (3.7)$$

one might expect the sub-tropical westerly jet maxima to be stronger than in the peaked and control experiments. However, this is not the case suggesting that there is less angular momentum conserving poleward outflow emanating from the tropical upper-troposphere in the flat experiment.

The mean meridional circulation for this experiment (Fig. 3.8(c)) confirms this. Between 15°N and S there exists no large-scale Hadley circulation with the associated regions of strong ascent and low-level equatorward flow. This is consistent with there being no preferred region for convection and the local balance of convection and evaporation in this experiment. Associated with this there is virtually no upper-level poleward flow from the tropics which explains the absence of the intense baroclinic part of the sub-tropical jet. Instead the jets are more equivalent barotropic in nature, with the upper-tropospheric maxima at the same latitude as the surface maxima. In fact the surface westerlies in this region are

Figure 3.10: Average taken over one day towards the end of the flat experiment showing (a) convective (black contours) and dynamic (blue contours) precipitation (mm day^{-1}); (b) 850 mb eddy temperature (K); (c) eddy mean sea level pressure (mb); and (d) 850 mb eddy meridional wind (ms^{-1}). The dashed black box encompasses a typical tropical–extra-tropical interaction event.

stronger than in the peaked and control experiments, probably as a response to the increased eddy convergence of westerly momentum due to the increased baroclinic activity, which is a consequence of the larger mid-latitude SST gradient with this profile. This suggestion is supported by the larger eddy driven thermally indirect Ferrel cell in mid-latitudes. Finally in the flat experiment an upper-tropospheric equatorial easterly jet, in excess of 22 ms^{-1} , is generated increasing the vertical shear on the equator. This easterly jet probably results in response to angular momentum conservation in weak equatorward flowing air from the top of the convective maxima at 15°N and S. From Eqn. 3.7 this can be interpreted as a movement of the zero zonal wind line at ϕ_0 from the equator, in the control and peaked experiments, to 15°N and S in the flat experiment.

Summarising this comparison of the three experiments, it is clear that the near-equator latitudinal SST gradient is the crucial component in determining the large-scale distribution and, to a certain extent, the magnitude of the tropical precipitation features in addition to

the resulting zonal mean circulation.

3.8.3 Synoptic Structure

Although the model climate is very hemispherically symmetric in the time-mean there are considerable zonal asymmetries in the flow on shorter time scales. These asymmetries differ in nature between the hemispherically symmetric experiments and contribute to the zonal mean in different ways.

In the control and peaked experiments the tropical precipitation disturbances are mostly isolated from the extra-tropical disturbances. However, on occasion the extra-tropical systems impact strongly on the tropical convective precipitation. These occurrences are infrequent in the peaked experiment, but in the control experiment there is at least one such event happening around the globe at any one instant in time. A typical individual event consists of a strong mid-latitude synoptic system which has an associated trailing cold front. The equatorward edge of the cold front moves into the sub-tropics behind which equatorward flowing colder air is able to trigger convection over the warmer waters due to destabilising sensible and latent heat fluxes into the lower-troposphere. The convection then appears to pulse along the trailing cold front apparently drawing the convection away from near the tropics and creating a tropical convective minimum immediately afterwards, which recovers over the next day or so.

Although these events are significant on these shorter time scales they do not appear to have a significant impact on the time-mean distribution of convective precipitation. In the flat experiment this is not the case as the mid-latitude synoptic systems organise much of the precipitation in the two convective maxima at 15°N and S. Fig. 3.10(a) shows a typical system interacting with the tropics in the flat experiment. The dashed box region shows the system of interest. Associated with the trailing cold front is a region of dynamically forced precipitation from large-scale processes. On its equatorward edge strong convective precipitation has developed and moved poleward. Comparing Figs. 3.10(b), (c) and (d) the nature of the interaction becomes clearer. A low-pressure anomaly has moved further equatorward from the extra-tropics than at any other longitude. Associated with this is a meridional low-level flow pattern which is advecting cold temperature anomalies equatorward behind the low centre, and warm temperature anomalies poleward drawing the

convection along the cold front region. Therefore, a constant succession of these events enhances the precipitation on the poleward edge of the tropical precipitation region. This gives the impression of a split ITCZ in the time-mean.

3.8.4 Communication of SST

The vertical profile of temperature and moisture within the tropical atmosphere is strongly constrained by radiation and convection. Fundamentally the profile is related to the underlying surface conditions and it is often hypothesised that convection is determined by the surface and boundary layer conditions rather than the convection and large-scale circulation being self supporting (e.g., Emanuel *et al.*, 1994). This means that the vertical temperature profile as opposed to the heating is controlled by the convection. In the free troposphere the vertical temperature profile often follows a moist adiabat that reflects the boundary layer equivalent potential temperature, θ_E , if the region is convectively active. Therefore, the magnitude of the SST should be reflected in the tropospheric temperature such that in the presence of convective activity regions with the same SST should have similar upper-tropospheric temperatures. After all the role of convection is to communicate the SST distribution through the depth of the troposphere.

These theoretical considerations have been compared with the results from the three zonally symmetric experiments. Fig. 3.11 shows a tephigram of the time-mean zonally averaged temperature profiles on the equator for the three experiments. Although all three experiments have a SST of 300 K on the equator the tropospheric temperature differs by some 4 K at 200 mb. The control experiment best communicates the SST into the troposphere with the vertical temperature profile following the 21.7°C moist adiabat, but this is some 5.3°C lower than the underlying SST. A large part of this temperature loss occurs between the surface and the lowest model level, in a super-adiabatic layer. Such super adiabatic surface layers were observed during the TOGA-COARE field campaign (Saxen and Rutledge, 1998). For mesoscale convective system scale events air-sea temperatures differences were as high as 4°C during the most intense precipitation phase. Unlike the aqua-planet such a large air-sea temperature difference is not seen in time-mean observations, however the idealised nature of the experiments makes it difficult to say whether or not this large temperature difference is highlighting a model error. Super-adiabatic layers are also evi-

Figure 3.11: Tephigram showing the zonally averaged vertical temperature profile on the equator for each of the three hemispherically symmetric integrations (note the super adiabatic layer between the sea surface and the lowest model layer).

dent, but to a much greater extent, in the peaked and flat experiments where there is a steeper super-adiabatic layer and larger cold bias throughout the troposphere compared to the control experiment.

The temperature profile in the peaked experiment follows a moist adiabat of about 19.7°C in the mid- to upper-troposphere. One might expect this experiment to give the best representation of the boundary layer θ_e in the vertical temperature distribution, since examination of the precipitation on synoptic time scales reveals that there is intense convection virtually all the time on the equatorial model grid points. Lack of SST communication to the boundary layer and the resulting tropospheric cold bias is most acute on the equator but does also exist to a lesser extent just off the equator. It is difficult to say whether this is an actual model error or a valid response of the system.

One reason for the possibly excessive air-sea temperature difference may lie in the modelling of localised evaporation in the presence of intense convective events. Moisture supply for convection is a combination of local evaporation from the sea surface and convergence of moisture into the convective region from non-local evaporation. Fig. 3.9 shows this is certainly the case for the control and peaked experiments, where there is a local moisture deficit in the tropics and surplus in the sub-tropics. Therefore, incorrect modelled winds both local and non-local would result in errors in the convective moisture supply.

Locally the parameterization of surface evaporation in GCMs is given by a bulk formulation such that:

$$-\frac{E}{\rho} = C_Q |\mathbf{U}_1| (q_1 - q_s), \quad (3.8)$$

where E is the evaporation, ρ is the air density, C_Q is the transfer coefficient for moisture, \mathbf{U}_1 is the horizontal velocity vector at the lowest model level, q_1 is the specific humidity at the lowest model layer and q_s is the specific humidity at the surface (saturation value at SST).

A study by Miller *et al.* (1992) looked into the sensitivity of the ECMWF forecast model to the parameterization of evaporation from tropical oceans and found that the evaporation parameterization being used resulted in extremely weak coupling between the atmosphere and ocean at wind speeds lower than 5 ms^{-1} . In addition they found an upper-tropospheric

cold bias that reached in excess of 2 K compared to the analysis. It is conceivable, therefore, that during convective events evaporation is underestimated in low mean wind conditions and there must be sub-grid scale gustiness in response to the convection which would give increased evaporation above that implied by the grid box mean wind. The aqua-planet experiments certainly show a minimum in evaporation on the equator (see Fig. 3.9) and a minimum in both components of the time-averaged wind. The meridional component is virtually nil due to the symmetric nature of the hemispheres. The zonal component is $< 10 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ in the peaked experiment and $< 5 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ in the control and flat experiments.

In response to these problems at low wind speeds the ECMWF bulk formulation for evaporation was adjusted by Miller *et al.* (1992) to include the effects of evaporation at low wind speeds and in the presence of convection. The wind dependence is changed to include the surface buoyancy flux, which is large in convective regions, so that the evaporation can now be expressed as:

$$-\frac{E}{\rho} = C_Q \{ |\mathbf{U}_1|^2 + w_*^2 \}^{\frac{1}{2}} (q_1 - q_s) \quad (3.9)$$

where

$$w_* = \left\{ -z_i g \frac{(\overline{\rho'w'})}{\rho} \right\}^{\frac{1}{3}}, \quad (3.10)$$

z_i is the boundary layer height and $g(\overline{\rho'w'})/\rho$ is the buoyancy flux at the surface. Therefore the evaporation is now related to the sub-grid scale convective processes generating sub-grid scale surface winds.

Inclusion of such a scheme in the UM might be expected to lead to increases in the tropical evaporation and temperature in these aqua-planet experiments particularly where there is intense convection, as in the peaked experiment, and low wind speeds, as in the flat experiment. This experiment has not been performed at this time.

3.8.5 Comparison with a Zonally Averaged Model

It is apparent that there exists two distinct regimes appearing in the three hemispherically symmetric experiments. A single ITCZ regime on the equator (control and peaked), and a regime with no preferred tropical convergence region (flat). This regime split results in significantly different circulations due only to changes in the axisymmetric forcing. This raises two main points. Firstly can theory account for these differences, and secondly what aspects of the zonally averaged circulation can be accurately predicted from theory?

There have been many studies to investigate what aspects of the zonally averaged global three dimensional circulation can be accounted for just by consideration of dynamics in a zonally symmetric two dimensional model. The approach taken here is a simplified version of that taken by Held and Hou (1980). They use an axially symmetric stably stratified model of a rotating Boussinesq fluid on a sphere with the important restriction that the fluid is nearly inviscid. This gives the fundamental property of absolute angular momentum conservation within the interior of the fluid such that for a steady state the zonal momentum equation is given by

$$\nabla[M] = 0 \quad (3.11)$$

where

$$M = \Omega a^2 \cos^2(\phi) + [U]_M a \cos(\phi). \quad (3.12)$$

Using the condition of zero zonal wind at the equator, which is a reasonable but not ideal boundary condition, gives a value for M of Ωa^2 at the equator. This allows Eqn. 3.12 to be re-written to give an expression for the zonal wind if absolute angular momentum is conserved in upper-tropospheric air moving poleward:

$$[U]_M = \Omega a \frac{\sin^2(\phi)}{\cos(\phi)}. \quad (3.13)$$

So air parcels moving away from the equator lead to acceleration of the zonal wind.

In addition to angular momentum conservation the zonally averaged circulation is constrained to be in thermal wind balance which, to within a few degrees of the equator, is a

good approximation. Rewriting Eqn. 3.1 but defining atmospheric layer mean quantities gives

$$[U]_{TW}(z = H_{trop}) - [U]_{TW}(z = 0) = -\frac{gH_{trop}}{fT_o} \frac{\partial [T]}{\partial \phi}, \quad (3.14)$$

where $[U]_{TW}(z = 0)$ is taken to be zero because of surface friction. The simplest approach in finding the thermal wind as a function of the boundary SST forcing is to assume that the surface exchange and convective processes allow the SST to be communicated to the atmosphere such that:

$$\frac{\partial SST}{\partial \phi} = \alpha \frac{\partial [T]}{\partial \phi}. \quad (3.15)$$

A first order approximation would be to take $\alpha = 1$ giving an expression for the depth averaged zonal thermal wind in terms of the underlying meridional SST distribution:

$$[U]_{TW} = -\frac{gH_{trop}}{fT_o} \frac{\partial SST}{\partial \phi}. \quad (3.16)$$

We can now take the equations which describe the latitudinal distribution of SST for all three experiments (Eqns. 3.2-3.4) and substitute into Eqn. 3.16. This will determine a theoretical radiative equilibrium zonal wind associated with each experiment, i.e. if the SST gradients are communicated exactly to the entire troposphere then what is the thermal wind consistent with such a temperature distribution. Fig. 3.12 shows this radiative equilibrium zonal wind, the zonal wind consistent with angular momentum conservation and the 500 mb zonal wind from each experiment. In the control experiment (Fig. 3.12(a)) the predicted tropospheric radiative equilibrium zonal wind from the SST field is clearly much larger than the angular momentum conserving zonal wind near the equator. Therefore, the radiative equilibrium wind consistent with the gradient of SST is not an attainable balanced state and violates angular momentum conservation. The observed 500 mb zonal mean zonal wind shows that the tropospheric temperature gradients are flattened out in latitude in order that the predicted radiative equilibrium zonal wind does not violate angular momentum conservation. In each case the magnitude of the model 500 mb zonal wind is less than the angular momentum conserving zonal wind. This is mainly due to the zero zonal wind line not being at the equator as is assumed to be the case in theory.

Figure 3.12: Distribution of zonal mean wind at 500 mb for each model run (black lines) compared with a theoretical zonal mean wind derived from angular momentum constraints (blue lines) and a zonal mean wind calculated from radiative equilibrium considerations (green line) using (a) control profile; (b) peaked profile; (c) flat profile.

The mean meridional circulation is thus the process by which the tropospheric temperature gradient is flattened out as summarised in Section 2.4.1. To first order the difference between the strength of the mean meridional circulation is determined by the difference between the zonal wind consistent with angular momentum conservation and the radiative equilibrium wind consistent with the gradient of SST. The greater this difference, the stronger the mean meridional circulation.

In the peaked experiment (Fig. 3.12(b)) the SST gradients are very strong near the equator which, when compounded with the small value of Coriolis force there, results in a large radiative equilibrium zonal wind. Therefore, the mean meridional circulation is the strongest of all axisymmetric experiments and centred closer to the equator. Consistent with this is the intense ITCZ confined very close to the equator. The differences between the zonal mean zonal wind, meridional circulation and convective precipitation in the control and peaked experiments can thus be attributed to differences in the degree of adjustment of the latitudinal temperature gradient in order to maintain angular momentum conservation within the tropics.

In the flat experiment (Fig. 3.12(c)) the radiative equilibrium wind consistent with the gradient of SST does not exceed the zonal wind due to angular momentum conservation at any latitude. This allows the troposphere to retain a similar latitudinal temperature gradient to the SST in the tropics. Therefore, the gradient of observed zonal wind matches that of the theoretical radiative equilibrium zonal wind and there is no requirement for a mean meridional circulation.

The differences in the zonal mean climate between the control and peaked experiments and the flat experiment are consistent with the theoretical considerations described in Section 2.4.1. In particular the limiting case for the existence of a mean meridional circulation (Eqn. 2.22) is reflected in the aqua-planet experiments. For tropical SST forcing with a meridional gradient greater than the fourth power of latitude (control and peaked experiments) a mean meridional circulation results, whereas a gradient equal to or shallower than the fourth power of latitude (flat experiment) does not produce a mean meridional circulation. However, this limiting case may be dependent on processes in the model. For example using a different convection scheme may result in a change in the transition SST gradient, such that the limiting case may occur for a stronger or weaker tropical SST gradient than the fourth power of latitude.

3.9 Hemispherically Asymmetric Experiment Results

Analysis of these experiments will focus on the relative roles of hemispherically asymmetric SST forcing and insolation forcing in generating an asymmetric response. In addition the sensitivity of the model to the strength of the asymmetric SST forcing and the agreement with simpler modelling studies will be highlighted.

3.9.1 Precipitation

Of the three hemispherically asymmetric experiments the control-June 21st experiment shows the least change compared to the control. The zonal mean convective precipitation (Fig. 3.13) is still almost symmetric about the equator, but now peaks slightly into the southern hemisphere rather than the northern hemisphere as seen in the control. This is

Figure 3.13: Zonally averaged convective precipitation (in mm day^{-1}) for integrations with the control-June 21st profile (solid line), control-5°N profile (long dash), and the control-10°N profile (short dash).

a robust change as it is seen in each individual monthly mean field for the experiment. The magnitude of the peak precipitation is about 1 mm day^{-1} less than in the control. Therefore, solstice insolation does not impact on the atmosphere enough to significantly move the convective maximum into the northern hemisphere. Possibly the only effect on the precipitation is the ability of the subtropical descent region to cool more effectively in the southern hemisphere than in the northern hemisphere. This then slightly enhances the strength of the Hadley cell and increases the ITCZ precipitation on the southern side of the equator giving the observed peak.

Moving the peak SST off the equator has a more substantial effect on the precipitation. In particular a single precipitation maximum is replaced by two maxima separated by a local minima. The control-5°N experiment has a maximum of 12 mm day^{-1} on the equator and a second maximum of the same magnitude at 10°N. Surprisingly, over the maximum SST at 5°N there is a local minimum of 10.5 mm day^{-1} . Since a double maxima is observed in individual monthly means the maxima are not simply a bimodal state of the climate system, whereby the maximum alternates between the equator and 10°N. In latitude-longitude time-series animations of precipitation the two maxima can clearly be seen as synoptic-scale events propagating predominantly westwards on the mean tropical easterly flow. The events which give the equatorial time-mean precipitation maxima are more frequent and less intense than the events which give the maxima at 10°N. At this latitude the events are strongly influenced by trailing fronts of mid-latitude systems as seen in the control experiment. However, the interaction with the mid-latitudes in the northern hemisphere is much more frequent than in the control.

A similar precipitation pattern occurs in the control-10°N experiment. Again there are two maxima, one at 2.5°N and a second at 15°N with a minimum near the SST maximum at 7.5 °N. The maxima reach about 10.5 mm day⁻¹ and the minima about 8 mm day⁻¹. A consequence of the twin maxima is an increase in the latitudinal extent of the ITCZ region. In the control experiment the tropical precipitation region of more than 2 mm day⁻¹ stretches from 10°N to 10° S covering 20° in latitude. In the control-5°N experiment this latitudinal coverage increases to 22° and then to 26° in the control-10°N experiment. However, the integrated precipitation remains the same between these two experiments and the control.

On synoptic time scales the characteristics of the precipitation organisation in the control-10°N experiment are similar to the control-5°N experiment, but with the whole pattern moved further into the northern hemisphere. The northern most precipitation maximum at 15°N is made up of very intense infrequent events with magnitudes often reaching in excess of 80 mm day⁻¹. The frequent interaction with mid-latitude systems resembles that seen in the flat experiment where precipitation totals were greatest on the flank of the tropics associated with mid-latitude systems impinging near the tropics.

The changes in precipitation associated with a movement of the SST maximum off the equator clearly demonstrates that processes which determine the distribution of tropical precipitation cannot be considered in isolation from the mid-latitudes.

3.9.2 Circulation

In the control-21st June experiment only minimal changes from the control experiment are observed. The zonally averaged zonal wind changes in the tropics (Fig. 3.14(a)) are consistent with the slight shift of the convective maximum and the centre of convective outflow into the southern hemisphere. This can be explained in terms of angular momentum conservation whereby the zero zonal wind line is further south than in the control, and by Eqn. 3.7 gives a weakened zonal wind in the southern hemisphere and a stronger zonal wind in the northern hemisphere.

More significant differences in the zonal averaged zonal wind occur in the lower-stratosphere within the extra-tropics. In these regions the effect of hemispherically asymmetric short

Figure 3.14: Zonally averaged zonal wind (ms^{-1}), anomaly from the control; (a) control-June 21st; (b) control-5°N; (c) control-10°N.

wave heating of the ozone field generates an increased pole to equator temperature gradient in the southern hemisphere and a reduced gradient in the northern hemisphere. Consistent with thermal wind balance the stratospheric jet weakens in the northern hemisphere and strengthens in the southern hemisphere. Such an acceleration of the southern hemisphere jet is seen in the real atmosphere during JJA giving rise to the polar night jet (cf. Fig. 3.1(b)).

Changes to the mean meridional circulation when compared with the control experiment (cf. Fig. 3.8) also reflect the slight shift southwards of the convective maximum (Fig. 3.15(a)). There is an enhancement of the southern hemisphere Hadley cell, corresponding to a negative circulation anomaly, and weakening of the northern hemisphere Hadley cell amounting to a 20% change from the control. This is consistent with the southern hemispheric cells ability to cool more effectively in the long-wave in the sub-tropical descent region of the Hadley cell.

The mean meridional circulation shows strong sensitivity to the movement of the SST maximum off the equator. In the control-5°N experiment the southern hemisphere Hadley cell intensifies by 50% in response to the weaker convection south of the equator and stronger convection north of the equator (Fig. 3.15(b)). There is also a weakening of the northern hemisphere cell. However, it only amounts to a 35% reduction in the maximum magnitude of the cell and not the near collapse of the summer cell that is seen in observations during solstice conditions. These changes show that the total mass transport of the tropical Hadley circulation increases by about 6%. The latitudinal extent of the whole Hadley circulation also increases by about 5°, but this increase is concentrated in the ascending branch consistent with the spreading out and decrease of the convective precipitation maximum.

A similar but stronger pattern of change is seen between the control and control-10°N experiments (Fig. 3.15(c)). The southern hemisphere cell increases by about 80% and the northern hemisphere cell decreases in strength by just over 50%. Therefore, the sensitivity of moving the SST from 5°N to 10°N is not as great as moving from 0° to 5°N. The two convective maxima seen in the control-5°N and control-10°N experiments are not obvious features in the mean meridional circulation. However, there is considerable tilting in the vertical of the zero contour between the northern and southern hemisphere Hadley cells (not shown), which is strongest in the control-5°N experiment. This would seem to indicate

Figure 3.15: Mean meridional mass streamfunction (kg s^{-1}), anomaly from the control; (a) control-June 21st; (b) control-5°N; (c) control-10°N.

that the convection slopes towards the north with height.

The tilt in the ITCZ is reflected in the vertical velocity field (Fig. 3.16). For the control experiment, although there are two ascent maxima at 750 mb and 300 mb, they are located approximately on the equator. However, in the control-5°N and the control-10°N experiments (Figs 3.16(b) and (c)) the upper-tropospheric ascent maxima move further poleward than the lower-tropospheric maxima. This would suggest that the convective maximum nearer the equator is due to shallow convective events, whereas the secondary convective maximum further away from the equator is due to stronger events maximising in the upper-troposphere. A local minimum in ascent is present in the mid-troposphere at the latitude of the SST maximum and corresponds to the local minimum in precipitation also at this latitude and is most likely an overturning suppressive response to the two convective maxima.

The pattern of zonal mean ascent would suggest that the mid-latitude synoptic systems impact the tropics by destabilising the mid- to upper-troposphere as the troughs move into the tropical regions. This process is more apparent in the control-5°N and control-10°N experiments as the convective maximum has moved poleward towards the latitude of the equatorward edge of the sub-tropical jet. Therefore, the combined effects of the increased baroclinicity in the northern hemisphere due to the stronger latitudinal temperature gradients, and the warmer troposphere where the troughs destabilise the atmosphere leads to more significant convective anomalies.

3.10 Comparisons with a Simple Model

Theoretical arguments based on simple modelling studies by Lindzen and Hou (1988) suggest that the atmosphere is very sensitive to moving the peak heating off the equator thus generating large hemispheric asymmetries. In the hemispherically asymmetric SST experiments this is also the case. However, the sensitivity is much less and in particular the magnitude of the dominant southern hemisphere Hadley cell doubles in experiment control-10°N, whereas in Lindzen and Hou (1988) a movement of the heating maximum to 6°N leads to a four fold increase in the magnitude of this cell. With such a strong increase in the southern hemisphere Hadley cell the zonal wind is dominated by angular momentum

Figure 3.16: Zonally averaged vertical velocity (mb hr^{-1}); (a) control; (b) control- 5°N ; (c) control- 10°N . Negative values indicate ascent

transports into the southern hemisphere. However, the changes to the zonal wind from the control experiment are concentrated mostly in the northern hemisphere (Figs. 3.14(b) and (c)). In the southern hemisphere the increased outflow of the strong Hadley cell increases the tropical easterly jet on the equator by about 12 ms^{-1} in the control- 10°N experiment but does not effect the sub-tropical jet a great deal. Looking at the mean meridional circulation, the increases in the southern cell are mainly confined to the northern hemisphere and so the enhanced angular momentum conserving flow stops just south of the equator. The increase of the southern hemisphere subtropical jet is therefore only 7 ms^{-1} in the control- 10°N experiment.

Changes to the zonal wind in the northern hemisphere are attributable to the combined effects of the reduced strength in the northern hemisphere Hadley cell and the increased extra-tropical baroclinicity. Extra-tropical forcing of the sub-tropical jet is not considered in Lindzen and Hou (1988), but appears crucial in maintaining the strength of the northern hemisphere jet which is actually stronger in the lower-troposphere than in the southern hemisphere. The extra-tropical nature of the southern hemisphere jet is also apparent when compared with the flat experiment. The structure of these jets are very similar, and in the flat experiment they are forced almost entirely in response to transient eddy forcing as the Hadley circulation is absent.

3.11 Conclusions

In performing simplified zonally symmetric experiments it is apparent that the model demonstrates a high degree of sensitivity to the meridional gradient of SST. In particular near-equator gradients are crucial in determining the nature of the ITCZ. Although the absolute magnitude of the underlying SST determines the spatially integrated convective precipitation, the SST gradients determine how this is distributed through dynamical feedbacks from the atmosphere. The organisation of tropical precipitation appears not to be a uniquely tropical process and synoptic scale extra-tropical systems have a significant role in this organisation, particularly when the mean meridional circulation is weak.

Simple theoretical arguments determining the limiting latitudinal SST gradient for which a mean meridional circulation is necessary agree well with the model results. However,

previous studies have shown this transition gradient to be sensitive to model parameterizations, particularly the convection scheme, and using a different convection scheme may give a dramatically different zonal mean climate for the same SST forcing.

We have shown that the equatorial tropospheric vertical temperature profile can differ considerably for the same magnitude of equatorial SST. These differences have their origin in the communication of SST to the lowest layers of the atmosphere. Conditions of very low surface wind speeds lead to poorer communication of SST to the atmosphere and lower boundary layer equivalent potential temperature, thus giving a colder temperature profile through the depth of the troposphere.

In fixed SST experiments such as these the tropospheric impact of changing the insolation forcing is minimal, and restricted to small hemispheric asymmetries in cloud top forcing and clear-sky long-wave cooling. The greatest impact is seen in the asymmetric heating of the stratospheric ozone field.

Greater sensitivity results from moving the SST maximum off the equator into the 'summer' hemisphere with the consequence of a stronger winter Hadley cell and a weaker summer Hadley cell. However, these changes are offset and the sensitivity reduced somewhat by changes to the mid-latitude circulation which gives the greatest changes to the sub-tropical summer jet, contrary to simple theory. Such differences are due to the increased latitudinal SST gradient in the summer hemisphere when moving the SST maximum off the equator. A strange double structure in the ITCZ also occurs with shallower convection near the equator, deeper convection further poleward, and a slight minimum over the SST maximum. One possible explanation for the further poleward maxima is the frequent intrusion of upper-tropospheric troughs destabilising the atmosphere and triggering convection.

In the introduction it was stated that the atmospheric zonal mean circulation in the tropics could be understood without knowledge of zonal-asymmetries. However, in this idealised study this appears not to be the case.

Chapter 4

Tropical Sea Surface Temperature Anomalies

4.1 Introduction

Aqua-planet experiments forced with axisymmetric SST distributions produce many of the observed features of the tropical atmosphere such as the ITCZ, surface trade easterlies, and the sub-tropical westerly jets. However, the observed distribution of surface temperature throughout the tropics is far from zonally symmetric and much of the zonal asymmetry in the tropical atmosphere results in response to the zonal asymmetry in the tropical SST. In order to understand where the convection occurs in association with SST it is necessary to know what factors of the SST field the convection is sensitive to. In particular how does varying the magnitude, zonal gradient, meridional gradient and the position of the individual SST features affect the position and strength of convection as well as the associated response. In this chapter we perform further aqua-planet experiments to investigate the sensitivity of the local and remote response to specific structure in the SST field.

Figure 4.1: Observed SST (in $^{\circ}\text{C}$) from the GISST2.0 climatology (Parker *et al.*, 1995); (a) anomalies from the zonal mean in January; (b) January zonal mean (solid line); (c) anomalies from the zonal mean in July; (d) July zonal mean (solid line). Dashed lines in (b) and (d) show the latitudinal SST profile from the control experiment.

4.2 Motivation and Description of Experiments

To understand the nature of the response to SST forcing we need to examine the sensitivity of precipitation to aspects of the SST field which are often observed in the tropics. Fig. 4.1 shows the climatological distribution of zonal SST anomalies in the tropics for January and July. Cold zonal anomalies are located mainly on the western side of ocean basins, due to up-welling and coastal currents in the sub-tropical oceanic gyres which transport cooler water equatorwards. The warm anomalies are confined mainly to the western and south central Pacific. Between seasons the position of the cool anomalies change little, however, the Pacific warm anomaly centre moves from the south west of Indonesia in January to the east and north into the Asian monsoon region of the Indian Ocean and China Sea. In July this movement of SST coincides with the seasonal shift of the zonal mean maximum SST northwards to about 8°N , reinforcing the SST anomalies in the Asian monsoon region. This shift in the position of the SST maximum is important as it is associated with a shift in the centre of the tropical convective maximum between the two regions.

Experiments have been performed in an attempt to capture the response to a typical tropical SST distribution. A zonal mean SST forcing is specified and superimposed on to this

is a region of enhanced SST, as the positive zonal mean SST anomalies appear to be more important in controlling the movement of the position of the convective maxima than do the negative anomalies. The zonal mean SST distribution chosen for the anomaly experiments is the control profile. This is shown alongside the observed zonal mean SST in Fig. 4.1(b) and (d), and although it falls off too steeply with latitude it gives the most realistic tropical climate of all three hemispherically symmetric experiments discussed in Chapter 3, in terms of rainfall distribution and the zonal mean meridional circulation. Using the control SST profile also allows us to make direct comparisons with the results from the control experiment.

We are only interested in capturing the response to the gross structure of the SST anomalies seen in observations, and so have avoided just using the observed SST distribution, with all its small scale structure, to force the aqua-planet. The response of convection to the anomaly will be different depending on the anomaly's position, therefore, separate experiments have been performed with an anomaly situated on the equator and at 10°S . Magnitudes of the zonal SST anomalies reach almost 3 K in the western Pacific, and so the two standard confined anomaly experiments consist of a 3 K anomaly on the equator and a 3 K anomaly at 10°S (Fig. 4.2).

The linearity of the response is also examined by performing experiments with SST anomalies of 1 K on the equator and at 10°S . A further experiment is carried out with a 6 K anomaly on the equator to examine how the model responds to a very large forcing. This provides a useful test of the parameterizations in a GCM which tend to be tuned to a particular parameter space. Therefore, it is of interest to examine the model's response when the forcing is at one extreme of the parameter range, in this case a very intense SST forcing. The scale of the anomalies are 60° in longitude and 30° in latitude, which approximately covers the region of the 29°C isotherm in January and July. This region is somewhat smaller than the region covered by observed SST anomalies in the west Pacific, but with a smaller SST anomaly we can be sure of keeping the local and remote response to the anomaly distinct. Experiments forced with larger scale SST anomalies are examined in Chapter 5. Experiments with varying zonal SST anomaly gradients will be discussed later in Section 4.10. A summary of all the anomaly experiments discussed in the thesis is given in Table 4.1.

Experiment Name	Anomaly maximum		Region occupied
	Magnitude	Position	
1KEQ	1 K	Equator	65°E → 125°E , 15°S → 15°N
3KEQ	3 K	Equator	65°E → 125°E , 15°S → 15°N
6KEQ	6 K	Equator	65°E → 125°E , 15°S → 15°N
1K10S	1 K	10°S	65°E → 125°E , 25°S → 5°N
3K10S	3 K	10°S	65°E → 125°E , 25°S → 5°N
3KSKE	3 K	Equator	50°E → 110°E , 15°S → 15°N
3KSKW	3 K	Equator	80°E → 140°E , 15°S → 15°N
1.5KW1	+/- 1.5 K	Equator	360° , 30°S → 30°N
3KW1	+/- 3 K	Equator	360° , 30°S → 30°N

Table 4.1: Summary of the aqua-planet anomaly experiments. All anomaly experiments have the maximum SST located at 95°E.

Figure 4.2: Sea surface temperature distribution (in K) for confined anomaly experiments showing the two positions used for the SST anomaly; (a) 3 K confined anomaly on the equator; (b) 3 K confined anomaly at 10°S; (c) as (a) but with the control SST distribution removed; (d) as (b) but with the control SST distribution removed.

4.3 Convective Precipitation

4.3.1 The Time Average

The time-averaged convective precipitation in experiment 3KEQ (Fig. 4.3(a)) has a maximum of 54 mm day^{-1} over the region of the SST anomaly. This compares to a zonal average of about 17 mm day^{-1} in the control experiment and so the non-linear effects of adding an SST anomaly, at least in the magnitude of convection, are very apparent. The strongest precipitation is centred some 5° to the west of the SST anomaly maximum, implying that the position of convection is dependent upon feedbacks from the atmosphere in response to enhanced latent heating, and not just the thermodynamic response alone. East-west asymmetry in the precipitation over the SST anomaly is not reflected in the SST anomaly itself, which is symmetric about its maximum in latitude and longitude. Asymmetry in the precipitation manifests as strong zonal and meridional gradients to the west, with weaker zonal and meridional gradients to the east. Therefore, in response to a symmetric SST anomaly the enhanced precipitation has structure which is a consequence of the atmosphere generating a balanced steady response to the enhanced latent heating.

Differences between the spatial distribution of precipitation in experiment 3KEQ and the control experiment (Fig. 4.3(c)), reveal that the effect of the SST anomaly extends further than just the anomaly region. In particular, there is suppression of precipitation away from the anomaly region, between 10° north and south, over all other longitudes. The strongest rainfall suppression regions are found immediately to the east and west of the area of enhanced rainfall. These regions coincide with areas of descent within steady equatorially trapped waves, forced in response to the enhanced latent heating over the SST anomaly, consistent with results from simple modelling studies (e.g. Gill, 1980). Therefore, the actual response to the increase in precipitation leads to a dynamical suppression of the precipitation elsewhere and over a region much larger than the SST anomaly region itself.

To the east, the pattern of suppression is consistent with descent within a tropically confined steady Kelvin wave response. The suppression is greatest on the equator where, from theory, the wave amplitude is largest. Precipitation is reduced by up to 4.5 mm day^{-1} , representing a 25% decrease compared to the control. Suppression of greater than 2 mm day^{-1} extends 120° east of the SST anomaly centre, occupying one third of the tropical

Figure 4.3: Convective precipitation distribution (in mm day^{-1}) for two confined anomaly experiments; (a) 3KEQ; (b) 3K10S; (c) as (a) but with the control zonal mean precipitation removed; (d) as (b) but with the control zonal mean precipitation removed. Positive contours are every 5 mm day^{-1} , negative contours are every 1 mm day^{-1} . Shaded regions indicate positive anomalies. The vertical dashed line in this and subsequent figures indicates the longitude of the SST anomaly maximum.

longitudes. To the west of the enhanced precipitation the pattern of rainfall suppression is consistent with the descent regions within the $n=1$ steady Rossby wave response. The strength of the Rossby wave response is 3 times the magnitude of the Kelvin wave response to the east and, consistent with this, forces stronger rainfall suppression. Descent within the Rossby wave is maximised off the equator which is reflected in the suppression of $5\text{--}7 \text{ mm day}^{-1}$ centred at 5°N and 5°S . A reduction in precipitation of this amount in this region represents a 50–70% decrease on the control precipitation. There is also suppression on the equator due to the Rossby wave response, but the magnitude is less at $2\text{--}3 \text{ mm day}^{-1}$. A reduction in precipitation due to the Rossby wave extends at least 80° westwards from the centre of the SST anomaly and covers the latitudes of the ITCZ precipitation region. Therefore, the effects of this wave propagation on precipitation are only obvious in the significant precipitation regions of the ITCZ. Effects of these excited waves may extend

further poleward but weak precipitation poleward of 10° makes it difficult to detect in the precipitation field.

The region of precipitation suppression between about 0° and 120°W is less easily explained than the suppression within the equatorial wave responses, although it is definitely a robust feature throughout the 11 month averaging period. The level of suppression reaches 2 mm day^{-1} but does not extend the whole latitudinal width of the ITCZ. Some kind of remote response to the localised latent heating may be responsible for this area of rainfall, establishing a teleconnection pattern between the two regions. Possible remote dynamical effects of the latent heating anomaly will be discussed later.

The superposition of a 3 K SST anomaly at 10°S on to the control profile in experiment 3K10S also results in a localised increase in precipitation (Fig. 4.3(b)). In this experiment the absolute maximum in SST is actually located at 5°S due to the pole to equator SST gradient. The precipitation maximum reaches 24 mm day^{-1} compared with 54 mm day^{-1} for experiment 3KEQ, reflecting the lower absolute SST maximum, 28.8°C compared with 30°C . The position of the SST anomaly away from the equator may contribute to weaker precipitation enhancement in the SST anomaly region. Elsewhere the magnitude and distribution of precipitation appears similar to the control experiment.

Removing the control zonal mean precipitation (Fig. 4.3(d)) reveals a similar pattern of tropic-wide precipitation enhancement and suppression, as with experiment 3KEQ, but with significant differences. The greatest increase compared with the control experiment occurs at 7.5°S , slightly west of the SST anomaly maximum, and represents a 5 fold increase in magnitude. This maximum is located in a region where the SST anomaly greatly enhances the existing pole to equator SST gradient, just south of the absolute SST maximum. The enhanced convective latent heat release due to the SST anomaly at 10°S is still located within the tropical wave guide and is, therefore, able to excite a steady Kelvin wave response to the east of the heating. However, the suppression within the Kelvin wave region is symmetric about the equator. This should be expected since, although the forcing is asymmetric in this experiment, the Kelvin wave is a response to the symmetric component of this forcing. Rainfall is suppressed by about 2 mm day^{-1} , which is less than for experiment 3KEQ, as a consequence of the weaker latent heating and its distance from the equator. Significant suppression of rainfall exists to the west of the SST anomaly, but unlike the Kelvin wave

response there is now asymmetry in the suppression about the equator consistent with the asymmetry of the forcing. South of the equator the rainfall reduction has a maximum of 6 mm day⁻¹ whereas north of the equator the reduction only reaches 3 mm day⁻¹.

The asymmetric forcing is therefore able to excite higher order Rossby wave modes, and in particular the even modes, i.e. $n=2,4,\dots$, which have a pattern of vertical velocity which is antisymmetric about the equator. A consequence of a stronger response from the higher Rossby modes is an associated lower wave speed. Waves for the $n=2$ mode travel, in theory, at $\frac{3}{5}$ the speed of the $n=1$ mode and so will propagate $\frac{3}{5}$ of the zonal distance of the $n=1$ mode before being damped by friction. Although the pattern of precipitation suppression may not fully reveal the effects of the Rossby wave propagation, it is apparent that the strongest reduction of rainfall to the west and south of the equator does not extend as far as in experiment 3KEQ. As the precipitation maximum is now located south of the equator it has enabled a response on the equator suppressing precipitation, even though the SST is actually 0.75°C higher than in the control. It is likely that the precipitation maximum due to the SST anomaly is drawing some of its low-level moisture supply from this region, resulting in the observed suppression.

4.3.2 Linearity of the Response

Experiments with SST anomalies of different magnitudes reveal the extent to which the model responds linearly to the forcing. In experiment 1KEQ over the SST anomaly, there is an increase of 8 mm day⁻¹ compared to the control, and in experiment 6KEQ this increase is 75 mm day⁻¹. Therefore, for experiment 1KEQ and 3KEQ the sensitivity of precipitation to the enhanced SST forcing is about 7.5 mm day⁻¹ per °C, whereas for experiment 6KEQ this increases to about 12.5 mm day⁻¹ per °C. In terms of absolute SST this suggests that the convective response to SST between 27°C and 30°C is linear but between 30°C and 33°C the strength of convection increases more steeply. This result is in disagreement with observational studies (e.g. Zhang, 1993) which suggest that in general convection strength, as measured by OLR, increases for SSTs between about 26°C and 30°C, but decreases and is rarely observed for any further increase in SST. Conditions may, therefore, be unique in the aqua-planet allowing the strength of convection to go on increasing, even for SSTs in excess of 30°C. Observations show that this may be a consequence of the non-interactive

Figure 4.4: Diabatic heating (in K day^{-1}) for (a) Zonal mean of the control experiment; (b) difference between experiment 3KEQ (averaged from 80.625°E and 110.625°E) and the control zonal mean; (c) as (b) but for experiment 3K10S; (d) as (b) but for experiment 6KEQ.

nature of the SST in the model. In regions where there is observed strong convection over SSTs between 27°C and 30°C the convection may act to limit any further increase in SST. Over regions where the SST does reach values greater than 30°C the boundary layer may be dynamically stable enough to suppress convection, since the lack of convection provides the clear skies and surface heating in the first instance. In the aqua-planet however convection and surface fluxes cannot act to regulate the SST and so the strength of convection keeps increasing, even for prescribed SSTs above 30°C .

The maximum suppression within the Rossby wave response region to the west of the SST anomaly is 2.5 mm day^{-1} in experiment 1KEQ and 9 mm day^{-1} in experiment 6KEQ. Therefore, the sensitivity of precipitation suppression to the adjacent increase in SST, is less than the sensitivity of precipitation enhancement. The sensitivity is about 2.5 mm day^{-1} per $^\circ\text{C}$ for experiments 1KEQ and 3KEQ, and about 1.5 mm day^{-1} per $^\circ\text{C}$ for experiment 6KEQ. Of course, the suppression of precipitation is limited by the precipitation that is present in the control, and a reduction of 9 mm day^{-1} in experiment 6KEQ implies near

zero precipitation remaining in the Rossby wave region.

4.4 Distribution of Diabatic Heating

As well as localised increases and decreases in precipitation, forcing from the enhanced SST changes the strength and vertical distribution of heating and cooling when compared with the control experiment. The zonal mean diabatic heating in the control experiment (Fig. 4.4(a)) has a peak of 6 K day^{-1} centred on the equator at 500 mb, due predominantly to the contribution from convective latent heat release. A secondary maximum of 4.5 K day^{-1} is found at 150 mb on the equator and can be attributed to short wave solar heating at the cloud top. There is also long-wave cooling from the cloud top, but this has its maximum slightly below the short wave absorption maximum and cancels with much of the short-wave absorption, giving the local minimum at about 240 mb.

The effect of including an SST anomaly is to locally increase the convective latent release, consistent with the increase in convective precipitation. In experiment 3KEQ over the anomaly region, the extra convective heating which results (Fig. 4.4(b)) is distributed differently in the vertical, such that the maximum additional heating is higher in the atmosphere at about 400 mb, when compared to the control. The latitudinal scale of the diabatic heating increase also expands into a region which was originally being cooled in the control, and so any additional cooling is pushed polewards. Diabatic heating also increases in the region near the tropopause at the cloud top where short-wave heating (not shown) increases. This is possibly due to the more frequent occurrence of deep cumulus clouds reaching the tropopause region and absorbing more insolation at the cloud top.

Associated with stronger and more frequent convection is an increase in long-wave cooling (not shown). Although the higher cloud tops are emitting at a colder temperature than in the control, the increased convection frequency and strength enhances the cloud top emission to space. This emission maintains the local minimum in diabatic heating between the cloud top increase and the convective heating increase. Long-wave cooling and short-wave heating at the cloud top extend higher than in the control experiment, suggesting that there is an obvious increase in the convection depth with an increase in SST.

The strength of cloud radiative forcing in the tropical upper-troposphere is weaker than the convective latent heat release but can still force significant changes in the general circulation and cloud properties (Sherwood *et al.*, 1994). Removing the effects of upper-tropospheric cloud radiative forcing can lead to reduced upper-tropospheric and increased lower-stratospheric temperatures. Additionally there may be a decrease in convection strength and latent heat release over the same underlying SST. Therefore, there may be major implications for the strength of large-scale circulations such as Walker and Hadley circulations, if the cloud top radiative effects are ignored or misrepresented.

In observations anvil clouds in the upper-troposphere spread out in the horizontal away from the convective centre into regions which tend to be cloud free below. The base of these anvil clouds are then able to absorb some of the long-wave radiation emitted from lower in the atmosphere at a higher temperature. Coupled with the cloud top cooling to space this maintains an unstable heating gradient in the vertical, even with the effect of insolation heating taken into account. In the aqua-planet anomaly experiments the enhanced convection results in increased short-wave heating dominating over cloud-top cooling increases due to long-wave emission. Therefore, the diabatic heating near the cloud top increases strongly with increased SST, a maximum of $4.5^{\circ}\text{C day}^{-1}$ in the control rising to $9^{\circ}\text{C day}^{-1}$ over the SST anomaly in experiment 3KEQ. Compared to the real atmosphere this heating is too elevated and not due to long-wave heating which is usually found below this. Including the radiative effects of anvil clouds may improve the representation of the cloud top radiative balance.

Experiment 6KEQ (Fig. 4.4(d)) exhibits similar changes in diabatic heating over the SST anomaly region to experiment 3KEQ, but of greater magnitude. This gives an even more elevated convective cloud top with an increased latitudinal extent, where an increased warming of at least $2^{\circ}\text{C day}^{-1}$ extends between 15°N and 15°S . The cloud top short-wave heating region begins to impinge on the region of stratospheric warming due to absorption of ozone, which suggests that the individual convective towers are strongly penetrating the lower-stratosphere.

Experiment 3K10S (Fig. 4.4(c)) shows a pattern of diabatic heating consistent with the increase in precipitation over the SST anomaly region. The diabatic heating due to convective latent heat release increases by up to $8.5^{\circ}\text{C day}^{-1}$, with the maximum being at the

same pressure as in the control experiment but moved to 7.5°S . This increase is actually accompanied by a slight decrease on the equator, although the decrease is less than $1^{\circ}\text{C day}^{-1}$. Even though the SST on the equator is on average about 0.5°C higher over the SST anomaly compared to the control, the latent heating below 600 mb has been reduced. This is consistent with the slight suppression of precipitation that accompanies the reduction in latent heating.

The dominant zonal mean diabatic cooling in the control experiment is centred at 15°N and 15°S at a pressure of 780 mb, so the strongest zonal mean cooling takes place at a higher temperature than the strongest zonal mean heating. The majority of this cooling is long wave emission to space in the clear-sky descent regions of the Hadley circulation. In the anomaly experiments the increased convective latent heating is not accompanied by an associated large increase in the local long-wave cooling within the local Hadley circulation. The compensating cooling occurs predominantly in the anomalous descent of the Rossby wave to the west and Kelvin wave to the east. There are however elevated cooling regions at 30° north and south, most evident for experiment 6KEQ. These regions as we will see later result from the strong upper-level anticyclonic response to the convective heating.

4.5 Variations in the Tropospheric Depth of Convection

In the anomaly experiments there is a suggestion that the cloud top height and, therefore, convection depth changes in response to changes in localised SST. Since the mean convective precipitation field shows tropic-wide suppression of precipitation, then an analysis of cloud top height is performed for the region of strongest tropical precipitation (5°N to 5°S) to investigate how the character of convection on the grid-box scale changes in response to the direct and indirect effects of the SST anomaly. Using the control and 3KEQ experiments, 6 hourly averaged OLR from each grid point is sampled during the final 3 months of each experiment. The data points are binned into 10 Wm^{-2} intervals and for experiment 3KEQ split into different tropical regions, depending on the characteristics of the mean precipitation. These regions are shown in Fig. 4.5(a) and have been chosen to encompass the enhanced precipitation over the SST anomaly region, suppression in the Kelvin wave and Rossby wave regions, and weak suppression in the region remote from the SST anomaly.

Figure 4.5: Analysis of 6 hourly averaged OLR (in Wm^{-2}) for the 3 K confined anomaly experiment; (a) location of the different regions used in the analysis; (b) normalised spread of OLR for each region as a proportion of the grid points in that region within each specific OLR bin.

The distribution of sampled OLR throughout the tropics in the control experiment (Fig. 4.5(b)), shows that there exists a wide range of cloud top heights. OLR values vary between about 120 Wm^{-2} , for the deepest convection, and $270\text{-}310 \text{ Wm}^{-2}$ where convection is essentially absent and the OLR signal of the sea surface is reaching the top of the model. The large distribution of cloud top height is apparent with only 8.5% of sampled grid points being in the most frequently occurring OLR bin. A direct comparison with OLR values throughout the whole tropics in experiment 3KEQ reveals that the distribution on the whole moves to higher values of OLR, indicating a net decrease in cloud top height throughout the tropics. Suppression of cloud top height in the tropical wave regions is, therefore, dominating over the increase in the SST anomaly region, at least between 5°N and 5°S . Also shown in Fig. 4.5(b) is the breakdown into the OLR for each of the specified regions. Over the anomaly region OLR is skewed towards lower values, peaking at 140 Wm^{-2} indicating a much elevated cloud top. Such small values are rarely observed in tropical convective regions. Convection over the SST anomaly accounts for most of the deep convection in the tropics with OLR values less than 120 Wm^{-2} . The proportion of grid points indicating surface OLR, or the absence of convection, is reduced by almost 40% compared to the tropical mean, indicating that in addition to deeper convective events they become more prevalent. The dominant precipitation suppression is seen in the Rossby wave region to the west of the anomaly and this is reflected in the sampled OLR by an increased frequency of non convecting grid-points. In addition, the proportion of grid-points convecting deeply is much reduced, but the most frequently occurring OLR remains the same as in the control experiment. The distribution of OLR in the Kelvin wave region reflects the suppression of rainfall in a similar way to the Rossby wave region, but with

Figure 4.6: 6 hourly averaged precipitation rate frequency calculated as a percentage of grid points between 5°N and 5°S binned into 5 mm day^{-1} intervals during the final 11 months of the experiment period for (a) control; (b) 3KEQ, but percent change in each 5 mm day^{-1} interval; (c) as (b) but for 3K10S; (d) as (b) but for 6KEQ. Note the different scale in (a).

smaller changes consistent with the weaker precipitation suppression seen in the mean. As the remote region is least affected by the influence of the SST anomaly the distribution of OLR is closest to that of the control experiment. However, overall the mean height of convection in this region is still lower than in the control experiment.

4.6 Variations in Precipitation Intensity

The changes in the characteristics of the grid-point convective events are also reflected in the grid-point sampling of the precipitation rate. Fig. 4.6(a) shows the frequency of precipitation rates of a particular magnitude in the control experiment binned into 5 mm day^{-1} intervals between 5°N and 5°S .

A significant proportion of the mean rainfall rate is made up of the contribution from higher rainfall rate events, such that the time-mean of 16.5 mm day^{-1} is higher than the

most frequent rainfall rate of $10\text{-}15\text{ mm day}^{-1}$. The change in the frequency of a particular rainfall rate interval for experiment 3KEQ (Fig. 4.6(b)) shows changes in the distribution of precipitation consistent with changes in OLR. In particular the distribution has moved to the highest and lowest rainfall rates at the expense of intermediate rainfall rates close to the mean. The number of events in the lowest precipitation rate interval have increased by 3%, reflecting the increase in suppressed and non-convecting grid-points. The increase in frequency of higher precipitation rates is spread over a large number of bins, from $45\text{-}50\text{ mm day}^{-1}$ right up to $95\text{-}100\text{ mm day}^{-1}$, much of which occurs in the atmosphere over the SST anomaly.

Changes to the distribution of precipitation rates for experiment 3K10S (Fig. 4.6(c)) are much less, consistent with the overall weaker impact of the SST anomaly at this latitude, but the pattern of change is the same as in experiment 3KEQ. The response in experiment 6KEQ (Fig. 4.6(d)) generates a more extreme change in the distribution of precipitation rates, such that the 8.5% increase in the lowest rainfall rate interval coupled with a 5% decrease in the $10\text{-}15\text{ mm day}^{-1}$ interval, is enough to make the $0\text{-}5\text{ mm day}^{-1}$ interval the most frequently occurring. Therefore, the regions of equatorial wave suppression are beginning to dominate the tropical rainfall rate distribution.

The OLR and precipitation distribution analysis, therefore, confirms the mean precipitation changes from the control experiment, but also reveals the characteristics of these changes. Firstly changes to the OLR tell us that the depth of the convection is greater over the anomaly region and less elsewhere by virtue of the colder (warmer) cloud-top temperatures indicating a more elevated (lower) cloud-top height. The precipitation rate changes tell us that it is raining more frequently and intensely over the SST anomaly and less frequently and intensely elsewhere. Through this analysis it enables a greater understanding of the consequences of the changes to the precipitation such as, for example, the diabatic heating whereby changes may be predicted to be dominant in the upper-troposphere and force more significant circulation anomalies there than nearer the surface.

4.7 Communication of SST to the Atmosphere

In the hemispherically symmetric SST experiments there is considerable decoupling of the boundary layer from the SST, particularly on the equator and in regions of low surface wind speed. This leads to difficulty in communicating the SST to the atmosphere, resulting in upper-troposphere temperature differences of up to 6°C between individual experiments which have the same underlying SST at the point of interest. With the inclusion of an SST anomaly there is considerably stronger localised precipitation, leading to increased difficulty in communicating the underlying SST to the atmosphere. The drop in temperature between the surface and 1000 mb level increases from 2.2°C in the control experiment, to 2.8°C in experiment 1KEQ, 4.1°C in experiment 3KEQ and 5.7°C in experiment 6KEQ. Therefore, the super adiabatic layer between 1000 mb and the surface intensifies with increasing anomaly magnitude (Fig. 4.7), along with the near surface instability that is triggering the increased convection over the SST anomaly. Below about 700 mb over the SST anomaly there is a difference in temperature between each experiment consistent with the difference in SST, but with approximately half the magnitude of the SST difference. At around 600 mb the temperature difference between the experiments diminishes to such an extent, that experiments 3KEQ and 6KEQ are colder than either the control or experiment 1KEQ at this pressure. However, with increased height above 600 mb the temperature difference between the individual profiles begins to be restored, again reflecting the differences between the SST better than in the boundary layer. For example experiment 6KEQ is 2.5°C warmer than the control at 1000 mb but 5.1°C warmer at 250 mb.

The minimum in temperature difference between the individual experiments, as shown in Fig. 4.7, is revealed in the zonal temperature anomaly along the equator for experiments 3KEQ and 6KEQ (Fig. 4.8(a) and (b)). Convection provides a temperature increase directly above the SST anomaly in the boundary layer and in the upper-troposphere above the anomaly, but there is a slight cooling compared to the zonal mean at 600 mb. There is no associated minimum in convective heating at 600 mb so convection must be extending through the depth of the troposphere above the SST anomaly. At 600 mb the equivalent potential temperature (not shown) is depressed, compared to the upper- and lower-troposphere, which is a possible signal of the influence of convective downdraughts. As downdraught mass flux is, in general, proportional to the convective updraught mass flux one would expect the

Figure 4.7: Tephigram showing the vertical temperature profile (in $^{\circ}\text{C}$) in the region of the highest rainfall for the control experiment (light solid line), experiment 1KEQ (dotted/dashed line), experiment 3KEQ (dashed line), and experiment 6KEQ (heavy solid line).

Figure 4.8: Zonal temperature anomaly along the equator (in $^{\circ}\text{C}$) for (a) experiment 3KEQ; (b) experiment 6KEQ.

influence of the downdraught to be stronger over the SST anomaly in experiments 3KEQ and 6KEQ. One possible explanation for this temperature minimum may be that the downdraught mass flux is predominantly detraining near the 600 mb level, which is much more elevated than usual. This result may be a consequence of the convection scheme operating at the extreme end of its tuned parameter space and giving a response which may be considered slightly unphysical. In observations downdraughts usually force a negative tendency in the equivalent potential temperature at the top of the boundary layer, which is at least some 200 mb lower than the 600 mb level.

Figs. 4.8(a) and (b) also show the significant cooling that results at pressures less than 180 mb above the convective maximum. This is in response to the deeper convection which generates a higher and colder temperature tropopause in this region. The opposite is seen to the west of the anomaly region where the cloud depth is lower than in the control and the temperature tropopause is lower and warmer. These large zonal temperature contrasts force a very localised zonal wind anomaly response in the upper-troposphere particularly in experiment 6KEQ. This response with westerlies to the east of the SST anomaly and easterlies to the west is consistent with a Gill (1980) response, but in general this is not the case for the weaker anomaly experiments on larger scales as we will see in the next section.

4.8 Dynamical Response

The nature of the precipitation response to the SST anomaly has been considered, but much of the precipitation response results as a consequence of the dynamical adjustment to the convective latent heating. The problem to be addressed is whether this dynamical response is consistent with the many theoretical models outlined in Chapter 2, or does even this simplified GCM setup introduce interactions which are strongly non-linear and difficult to disentangle.

The simple two-level response to a heating anomaly of Gill (1980) predicts that the steady circulatory response of the tropical lower-troposphere is the same strength and scale as the upper-troposphere, but with the opposite sign. Immediately there is a fundamental problem with the assumption that the convective heating is distributed simply in the vertical. Fig. 4.4 clearly shows that the additional convective latent heating due to the SST anomaly is skewed towards the upper-troposphere, such that there is a steady increase with height from the surface up to 420 mb and then a strong decrease up to 200 mb. Therefore, the assumption of a first baroclinic mode structure in the vertical becomes increasingly inaccurate. This is additionally complicated by forcing due to cloud top radiative effects, which the Gill (1980) model does not explicitly take account of, but is clearly of the same order of magnitude as the convective latent heating anomaly.

Despite the shortcomings of the latent heating assumption, the lower-tropospheric response is essentially in agreement with the Gill model, shown by the 850 mb streamfunction zonal anomaly (Fig. 4.9). In experiment 3KEQ (Fig. 4.9(a)) there are two cyclonic regions symmetric about the equator at 10°N and 10°S , centred about 15° to the west of the convective heating maximum. The areas of descent and low-level convergence (not shown) in the cyclonic region are consistent with the cyclonic flow. The eastern edge of each cyclone sees poleward flow which diminishes with latitude, consistent with the diminishing magnitude of the equatorially trapped response. The whole Rossby wave response is also consistent with the Gill model as off-equatorial low-level convergence extends the existing region of convergence that would be seen in a purely thermodynamic response to the SST anomaly. This slight extension of the region of convergence also provides part of the east-west asymmetry seen in the precipitation maximum (cf. Fig. 4.3(a)). Off the equator and just to the west of the cyclone centres are the main regions of descent associated with the

Figure 4.9: Streamfunction zonal anomaly (in m^2s^{-1}); (a) experiment 3KEQ at 850 mb; (b) experiment 3K10S at 850 mb; (c) experiment 3KEQ at 150 mb; (d) experiment 3K10S at 150 mb.

tropical wave response to the diabatic heating also seen in the Gill model. This descent is ultimately responsible for the stabilisation of the boundary layer in this region and coincides with the area of precipitation suppression providing further east-west asymmetry.

Further poleward of the equatorially trapped response are cyclonic and anticyclonic circulation anomalies most likely associated with a remote response to the equatorial convective forcing. This is a consequence of an equivalent barotropic structure connecting from the same sign anomaly structure in the upper-troposphere.

In experiment 3K10S (Fig. 4.9(b)) the low-level response to the convective forcing also involves two cyclones straddling the equator, but the southern cyclone has twice the magnitude of the northern one. The westward extent of the cyclones are some 20° less than in experiment 3KEQ. These differences in the low-level response are consistent with the reduced western extent of the strongest Rossby wave precipitation suppression, particularly north of the equator, in this experiment. In addition the strength of the southern cyclone descent region is responsible for the intense rainfall suppression on its north western flank,

and consistent with the extension of the precipitation maximum southwards on its south eastern flank.

Further poleward at this longitude the pattern of closest remote response is also significantly different from experiment 3KEQ. Anticyclones to the north west and south west of the southern and northern equatorial response respectively dominate, as opposed to slightly weaker cyclonic regions to the north east and south east. The strength of this response is about the same magnitude north and south of the equator. This would suggest a more symmetric forcing of the upper-tropospheric circulation anomalies leading to a symmetric equivalent barotropic communication with the lower-troposphere.

Unlike the lower-troposphere, the direct response to the convective heating in the upper-troposphere does not agree with the simple Gill response, nor does it agree with the observed atmospheric response to the convective heating. In the atmosphere during the DJF season, for example, the dominant tropical heating is a maximum at about 130°W on the equator (cf. Fig. 2.4) and the dynamical response to this manifests as two elongated anticyclones either side of the equator over and to the west of this heating. On removal of the zonal mean, the anticyclones are accompanied by cyclones either side of the equator to the east of the heating. In the anomaly experiments the modelled response (Fig. 4.9(c) and (d)) is the reverse of that observed with a pair of intense anticyclones at and slightly to the east of the heating, and a pair of cyclones to the west of the heating. Therefore, it appears that the cyclones extend through the depth of the troposphere, intensifying and drifting slightly westwards with height. Whereas, the anticyclones are mainly confined to the upper-troposphere. Consistent with the reduced strength of convection in experiment 3K10S the anticyclonic response is weaker than in experiment 3KEQ and there is a bias towards the southern hemisphere. In agreement with the lower-troposphere circulation anticyclonic anomalies exist at 60°E and 40°N and S, confirming the near hemispherically symmetric equivalent barotropic structure in this region.

The fundamental differences between observations and the aqua-planet response appears to lie in the nature of the convective divergent outflow and how it impacts on the mean flow. In observations the 150 mb divergent outflow is on a larger spatial scale and, consistent with the distribution of tropospheric diabatic heating, is strongest to the west and north of the heating region. However, in the aqua-planet the distribution of divergent wind is more

Figure 4.10: 150 mb absolute vorticity (s^{-1}) for, (a) experiment 3K10S; (b) experiment 3KEQ.

geographically confined and circularly symmetric about the convective heating maximum. The strongest divergent velocities are, therefore, located in significantly different regions. As a consequence they advect absolute vorticity contours on the whole poleward in different regions, which is where the anticyclonic response is generated.

In observations the advection of absolute vorticity has the effect of weakening its meridional gradient in the deep tropics, tightening the gradient north of the anticyclones, and intensifying the subtropical westerly jets. In the aqua-planet experiments the divergent wind velocities and the advection of absolute vorticity is much stronger such that there is zero meridional gradient in absolute vorticity and a pool of zero absolute vorticity is advected across the anticyclones near the equator. Fig. 4.10(a) shows this effect strongly in experiment 3KEQ either side of the equator and to a lesser extent south of the equator in experiment 3K10S (Fig. 4.10(b)). The equatorial upper-level easterlies are thus increased to the east of the convective maximum which directly opposes the westerly divergent outflow in this region. A further consequence of the anticyclones being positioned to the east of the convective maximum is that the associated poleward rotational flow is situated at, and just to the west of, the longitude of the convective maximum. This reinforces the existing poleward divergent flow and generates a large increase in the local Hadley circulation outflow extending out to about $30^{\circ}N$ and S through the depth 150 mb to 350 mb.

The mean flow on which the effects of the tropical convective heating project certainly has a role to play in determining the response. The absolute vorticity shows significant differences between observations and the aqua-planet experiments at the 150 mb convective outflow region. In observations absolute vorticity varies smoothly between equator and pole with a

slight increase in gradient in the region of the sub-tropical jets, whereas in the aqua-planet experiments the maximum gradient in absolute vorticity is far more pronounced between about 20° and 40° due to the intense westerly jets. The Rossby wave source resulting from the convective outflow is located further east in relation to the convective maximum than is seen in observations during DJF. This is due predominantly to the divergent outflow impacting on the strong sub-tropical jet much further east near the longitude of the convective anomaly.

4.9 Response of the Hadley Circulation

In the study of Ward (1993) a possible mechanism is proposed for the observed tropic wide variability during the JAS season. During the dry Sahel phase of the TWM reduced precipitation in the west Pacific, often in El Niño years, is accompanied by decreased precipitation over the Sahelian and Indian regions. This is conceivably a response of the Hadley circulation whereby poleward exports of heat and momentum have to be maintained and a weakened Hadley cell over the west Pacific is accompanied by an intensification at other longitudes resulting in the precipitation changes observed.

We now examine the confined anomaly aqua-planet experiments to try and identify if such a response exists. Concentrating on experiment 6KEQ in order to obtain the strongest remote response, Fig. 4.11(a) shows an obvious increase in the Hadley circulation in the region of the SST anomaly. Convective outflow intensifies the upper-tropospheric part of the local Hadley circulation. There is a much lower increase in the lower-tropospheric meridional convergence which is consistent with the dominant circulation changes near the surface being in the zonal direction.

Just to the west of the SST anomaly over longitudes previously identified as the Rossby wave suppression region (cf. Fig 4.5(a)) there is an obvious reduction in the strength of the local Hadley circulation (Fig. 4.11(b)). In the upper-troposphere the anomalous circulation is indicative of a capping of convection depth as identified in Sections 4.5 and 4.6. In the lower-troposphere the anomalous descent splits either side of the equator consistent with the off-equatorial Rossby wave suppression. This actually leaves anomalous lower-tropospheric ascent on the equator in this region. In the Kelvin wave suppression region to the east of

Figure 4.11: Wind vectors shown in the height latitude plane (v , ms^{-1} ; ω , mb hr^{-1}) averaged over longitudinal sections for experiment 6KEQ with the control zonal mean removed from each section for (a) 80.625°E to 114.375°E - SST anomaly region; (b) 1.875°E to 69.375°E - Rossby wave region; (c) 118.125°E to 125.625°W - Kelvin wave region; (d) 31.875°W to 121.875°W - Remote region. Note the much larger scale for the wind vectors in (a).

Figure 4.12: (a) Wind vectors shown in the height latitude plane (u , ms^{-1} ; ω , mb hr^{-1}), zonally averaged for experiment 6KEQ; (b) zonally averaged precipitation for the control and 6KEQ experiments.

the SST anomaly (Fig. 4.11(c)) an even stronger reverse anomaly can be seen in the upper-tropospheric Hadley circulation which is balanced by anomalous outflow throughout the depth of the troposphere below about 300 mb. Even over the region most remote from the SST anomaly shown in (Fig. 4.11(d)) there is a weak reversal of the Hadley circulation in the upper-troposphere, which surprisingly is accompanied by lower-tropospheric anomalous ascent just on the equator.

These results would seem to suggest that some adjustment of the Hadley circulation is being undertaken in order to offset the increases in meridional outflow over the anomaly region. However, the suppression is concentrated in the upper-troposphere and changes in the lower-troposphere seem to act to increase the Hadley circulation, at least on and very near the equator.

During integrations of length only one year one would not expect the zonal mean Hadley circulation exports of momentum and heat, for example, to be equal in all the aqua-planet experiments. In fact the confined anomaly has a significant impact on the zonal mean circulation and precipitation. Fig. 4.12(a) shows the changes to the zonal mean Hadley circulation revealing that the net effect of the SST anomaly is to decrease the Hadley circulation at least in the upper-troposphere. Below about 600 mb however there is anomalous ascent on the equator implying the opposite sign to the anomalous Hadley circulation. The changes in the lower-tropospheric circulation appear to be more important in determining the changes to the zonal mean precipitation as shown in Fig. 4.12(b). Nearest the equator in experiment 6KEQ the intense precipitation over the SST anomaly is enough to give a greater zonal mean precipitation on the equator than in the control experiment. On the poleward flanks of the ITCZ this situation is reversed and the anomalous descent in the zonal mean circulation gives rise to precipitation values slightly less than in the control.

Therefore, changes to the upper-tropospheric Hadley circulation in experiment 6KEQ points to considerably weaker zonal mean precipitation in the ITCZ. This, however, detracts from the changes in the lower-tropospheric zonal mean circulation which appear to have a greater role in determining the overall differences in the zonal mean precipitation from the control experiment.

Figure 4.13: SST anomaly distribution (in K) for skewed confined anomaly experiments; (a) 3KSKW; (b) 3KSKE.

4.10 Skewed SST Anomalies

Another characteristic of the observed SST field under investigation is the zonal gradient of SST in the tropics. Sensitivity to the zonal gradient of the observed SST in the Pacific was identified as being important for the strength of the Tropic Wide Mode (Ward, 1993). During years when the tropical Pacific SST maxima is far removed from its climatological position, namely west of 160°E or east of 180° , the tropic wide response over the Sahel and Indian region was found to be enhanced. This has the effect of skewing the cross Pacific zonal SST profile which, for example during El Niño conditions sharpens its gradient in the east of the basin and flattens it in the west.

To examine possible sensitivity to this skewing of SST anomalies two further aqua-planet experiments have been performed. Taking the SST anomaly used in experiment 3KEQ the longitudinal gradient has been changed such that the SST maximum is skewed either to the west of the anomaly region as in experiment 3KSKW or to the east as in experiment 3KSKE. The structure of these anomalies are described in Table 4.1 and shown in Fig. 4.13. One important point to note is that the maximum of each skewed SST anomaly is located at the same longitude as in experiment 3KEQ, so that the actual region occupied by the anomaly changes between the experiments

The structure of precipitation in the skewed experiments shows considerable sensitivity to the different shape of the anomaly Figs. 4.14(a) and (b). As in experiment 3KEQ the position of the precipitation maximum lies to the west of the SST maximum at 95°E . However, the influence of the shape of the anomaly is very apparent. In experiment 3KSKW

the shape of the anomaly is reflected in the shape of the precipitation maximum region and the absolute maximum is closer to the maximum SST. In experiment 3KSKE the distribution of precipitation is considerably different. Firstly the maximum is moved some 10° west of the SST anomaly maximum compared to a 5° shift in experiment 3KEQ. In addition the distribution of precipitation is much more symmetric over the SST anomaly regions and gives little indication that the underlying anomaly is strongly skewed to the east.

Having the strongest zonal gradient to the west of the anomaly as in experiment 3KSKW gives the greatest maximum precipitation of nearly 54 mm day^{-1} compared to 47 mm day^{-1} seen in experiment 3KSKE. This shows the importance of the zonal gradient of SST for the distribution and strength of precipitation. Just from a purely linear point of view one would expect experiment 3KSKW to result in stronger teleconnections by virtue of the more intense diabatic heating, upper-tropospheric divergence and increased Rossby wave source. However, the shape of the diabatic heating and convective outflow is also different between the two skewed experiments and may have a more subtle impact on the strength and location of the Rossby wave source.

When compared with experiment 3KEQ the precipitation in the skewed experiments also differs away from the anomaly region. Fig. 4.14(c) and (d), shows differences of opposite sign over the anomaly region between the two experiments, but away from this region the changes from experiment 3KEQ are similar in both skewed experiments. Between about 60°W and 120°W there is up to 2 mm day^{-1} greater suppression, particularly just off the equator in both cases. There is also a reduction in suppression that is seen in the Kelvin wave region from 120°W to 180° in experiment 3KEQ of up to 2 mm day^{-1} . To the west of the anomaly region there are indications that the suppression due to the excitation of tropically confined Rossby waves is being extended further west in experiment 3KSKE with increased suppression just off the equator. There is also signs of a retreat eastwards of the Rossby wave suppression region in experiment 3KSKW. Both these are changes due to a shift in the position of the main convective centre, but the signal is unclear and a similar shift that may be expected in the Kelvin wave suppression region is not seen with any significance in these experiments.

As in experiment 3KEQ the main change to the circulation near the surface occurs to the

Figure 4.14: Convective precipitation (mm day^{-1}) for (a) experiment 3KSKW; (b) experiment 3KSKE; (c) experiment 3KSKW minus 3KEQ; (d) experiment 3KSKE minus 3KEQ.

Figure 4.15: 1000 mb wind vectors and wind speed (shaded), anomalies from the control for experiment; (a) 3KEQ; (b) 3KSKW; (c) 3KSKE.

Figure 4.16: 150 mb streamfunction (kg s^{-1}), anomaly from experiment 3KEQ; (a) 3KSKW; (b) 3KSKE.

west. Anomalous westerly inflow associated with the steady Rossby wave response to the west dominates over any increase seen in the zonal inflow associated with a Kelvin wave response to the east. Fig. 4.15 shows the anomalous 1000 mb flow vectors when compared with the control experiment. The increase in the zonal gradient of the SST anomaly in experiment 3KSKW to the west of the anomaly maximum sees an inflow strength that is slightly larger than in experiment 3KEQ, due to the enhanced zonal temperature gradient generating an increased zonal pressure force on the equator. This westerly inflow opposes the basic state easterlies due to the equator to pole temperature gradient, and generates strong near surface convergence enabling convection as strong as in experiment 3KEQ. Since the zonal SST anomaly gradient in experiment 3KSKE is flatter on its western side and the changes on this side of the anomaly dominate, then the zonal inflow and implied convergence is weaker than in experiment 3KSKW. The westerly boundary layer inflow may also explain why the position of the precipitation maximum is further east in experiment 3KSKW as the stronger magnitudes are able to move the centre of convergence more over the SST anomaly maximum.

Away from the anomaly region the changes in precipitation, when compared to experiment 3KEQ, were the same in both experiments when one may have expected them to be of opposite sign after considering the changes in the Kelvin wave suppression region. The nature of the wave propagation in the upper-troposphere may go some way towards explaining this. Fig. 4.16 shows the 150mb streamfunction anomalies from experiment 3KEQ for both the skewed anomaly experiments. In experiment 3KSKW consistent with the convective heating and upper-tropospheric outflow positioned further east there are anticyclonic anomalies

well east of the longitude of the maximum SST, with slight cyclonic anomalies just to the west of this either side of the equator. In experiment 3KSKE the anticyclonic anomalies are now positioned to the west of the SST maximum consistent with the position of the convection. In both these cases there is anomalous Rossby wave propagation from the poleward and eastward edge of these anticyclonic anomalies seen as a series of successive cyclonic and anticyclonic circulation anomalies propagating downstream. It appears however that the wave propagation in the two experiments is in phase. The consequence of this is that in experiment 3KSKE the first Rossby wave anticyclonic anomaly is approximately co-located with the equatorial anticyclonic anomalies found in experiment 3KSKW. This in phase behaviour is continued downstream with anticyclonic anomalies centred near the equator at 150°W being observed in both experiments, consistent with the same sign of precipitation anomaly.

Therefore, in these skewed anomaly experiments the direct effect of changing the anomaly zonal gradients is seen in the shift of the convective maximum and the region of Rossby wave suppression. However, direct changes to the suppression on the eastern periphery of the Kelvin wave region are not consistent between the two experiments, and the in phase behaviour of the planetary Rossby wave activity may explain the same sign remote precipitation anomalies seen in these experiments.

The two aqua-planet experiments go some way towards gaining an understanding of the sensitivity to the zonal gradient of SST observed in the tropics wide response to different profiles of SST. One definite conclusion is that the strength of precipitation is increased in response to the strengthening of the SST gradient as seen in experiment 3KSKW. This would seem to suggest a possible increase in teleconnective strength during strong La Niña events. All this is of course dependent on the prevailing mean climate and whether parameters such as the strength and position of the subtropical westerlies are also conducive to enhanced Rossby wave propagation.

4.11 Conclusions

The results from all the confined anomaly experiments show not only an expected precipitation increase in response to localised higher SSTs centred to the west of the maximum

SST, but also significant tropic wide suppression of the ITCZ when compared with the control experiment. Much of this suppression is consistent with the descent regions of steady tropically confined wave disturbances acting to stabilise the atmospheric profile.

In addition to the mean precipitation distribution being changed the actual depth of the convection is increased in the region of the anomaly and decreased elsewhere in the regions of rainfall suppression. This has important implications as to where associated changes in the vertical distribution of diabatic heating are located. In the aqua-planet these changes in heating are predominantly in the upper-troposphere. The vertical profile of heating over the SST anomaly region also shows that the first baroclinic mode assumption is not ideal and may explain why the upper-tropospheric response does not conform to the simple response seen in Gill (1980). In fact the anticyclonic response usually seen well to the west of convective heating anomalies in the real atmosphere (Sardeshmukh and Hoskins, 1985) is seen to the east of the heating anomaly, disagreeing with simple vorticity balance arguments. However, these anticyclones are shown to be associated with a large pool of absolute vorticity such that vorticity balance is maintained.

The eastern extent of the anticyclones and circularly symmetric nature of the upper-tropospheric outflow results in a Rossby wave source located much further east than would be the case in the real atmosphere, which of course has implications for the phase of planetary wave trains propagating westwards downstream. The exceptional nature of the subtropical westerlies in all the anomaly experiments also plays a role in the strength and position of this Rossby wave source.

Although the local response to the off equatorial anomaly experiments 1K10S and 3K10S is hemispherically asymmetric, the more remote response was found to be more symmetric most likely in response to a near symmetric Rossby wave source.

As postulated for a mechanism in the observed TWM, the local and remote response in the anomaly experiments can be considered as adjustments to the strength of the Hadley circulation giving enhanced or suppressed precipitation in the ITCZ. However the strength of precipitation appears just as sensitive to the changes in the Hadley circulation in the lower-troposphere as in the upper-troposphere. In fact the increase in zonal mean precipitation in the anomaly experiments right on the equator is accompanied by a lower-tropospheric increase in the Hadley circulation and an upper-tropospheric decrease.

Skewed SST anomaly experiments reveal sensitivity to the zonal gradient of SST, particularly when the zonal gradient to the west of the SST maximum is increased. The choice of the two skewed SST profile experiments here happened to result in an anomalous planetary Rossby response that originates in distinctly different regions, but which are in phase such that the remote tropical precipitation and circulation anomalies are of the same sign in both experiments.

Chapter 5

Tropical Wave Number One SST Anomalies

5.1 Introduction

As well as the localised response to tropical SSTs, the atmosphere is able to communicate a response from a tropical forcing to remote regions, through different global teleconnection patterns. Although there are obvious remote effects in the confined anomaly experiments, such as the significant suppression of tropical precipitation away from the SST anomaly, the diagnosis of the mechanisms responsible is not trivial. This was mainly due to a remote dynamical signal which is quite weak and not always coherent. Apart from integrating the confined anomaly experiments for longer or using an even larger magnitude of confined SST anomaly to obtain better significance and coherence, there is the option of forcing the aquaplanet with a SST distribution which will give a larger global response in the model. In particular the zonal mean response, of which there is an indication in the confined anomaly experiments, may be expected to become much more apparent.

With this in mind SST distributions with zonal wavenumber one SST anomalies are used to force the UM. Such an SST distribution is by no means purely a thought experiment, as it does capture some of the structure of the tropical pattern of SST. In particular the gross pattern of SST in the tropics consists of generally warm anomalies throughout the Indian Ocean and the west/central Pacific, and generally cool anomalies throughout the east Pacific

Figure 5.1: Sea surface temperature for experiment 3KW1 (in K); (a) full field; (b) anomaly from the control SST distribution.

and Atlantic Oceans in the DJF season. Therefore, one would hope to represent some of the response seen in the atmosphere but at the same time obtaining a smoother more coherent signal as seen in idealised experiments.

5.2 Wavenumber One Experiments

Two wavenumber one experiments have been performed with the UM aqua-planet. They are formulated in a similar fashion to the confined anomaly experiment such that the control SST distribution is used with a 1.5 K (experiment 1.5KW1) and 3 K (experiment 3KW1) zonal wavenumber one SST anomaly superimposed. The SST distributions are summarised in Table 4.1 and shown for experiment 3KW1 in Fig. 5.1. Importantly, even with a wavenumber one SST anomaly the equator to pole SST gradient does not reverse sign in the tropics at any longitude, although it does become small in the region of the equatorial SST minimum, similar to the flat axisymmetric experiment. Therefore, along the equator in experiment 3KW1 the tropical SST varies from 30°C at 95°E down to 24°C, so that half the equator is in a region well above the traditional 26-27°C threshold for strong convection and half is below it.

5.3 Direct Response

The climatology of the aqua-planet changes dramatically when subject to forcing from more extreme SST distributions. The response can perhaps be viewed in the same way as for the

Figure 5.2: Convective precipitation (in mm day^{-1}) for experiment (a) 1.5KW1; (b) 3KW1; (c) as (a) but with control zonal mean precipitation removed; (d) as (b) but with control zonal mean precipitation removed. Shaded regions indicate positive anomalies.

confined anomaly experiments, with a definite local and remote response, but on a larger scale. However, the nature of the SST forcing makes it increasingly difficult to separate remote and local effects. This is particularly the case in the region of the equatorial SST minimum where the distribution of precipitation could be due to a combination of factors including reduced local SST, direct circulations due to the positive SST anomaly region, and remote teleconnections via higher-latitudes.

Convective precipitation for experiment 1.5KW1 (Fig. 5.2(a)) shows a slowly varying distribution of precipitation along the equator consistent with the slowly varying SST. However, the position of the maximum precipitation is some 10° to the west of the SST maximum and the precipitation minimum lies a massive 65° to the west of the SST minimum. The distribution of precipitation must, therefore, be strongly influenced by the dynamical response to the SST maximum and not just the response to the local thermodynamics of the underlying SST.

On removal of the control zonal mean convective precipitation (Fig. 5.2(c)) it is apparent

that the distribution of precipitation enhancement and suppression, in relation to the position of the SST maximum, is significantly different to the confined anomaly experiments. The regions of largest positive anomalies reach just over 6 mm day^{-1} , and are surprisingly not concentrated on the equator but to the east and slightly poleward at 5°N and 5°S . These anomalies are also less spatially coherent than in the confined anomaly experiments. Suppression reaches a maximum of 9.2 mm day^{-1} on the equator, probably in the region where the stabilising effect of cooler SSTs and descent within the steady Kelvin wave response to the east of the precipitation maximum combine to provide the greatest hindrance for deep convection.

Missing from the pattern of suppression present in the confined anomaly experiments, which accounted for the strongest suppression, is the reduction due to descent within the steady Rossby wave response to the west of the precipitation maximum and off the equator. On the poleward and westward edge of the region of anomalously high precipitation, there is a region of small negative precipitation anomaly stretching from 60°E to 60°W and centred at 30°N and S . However, in this region the anomalous descent is strongest in the mid- to upper-troposphere. This indicates it is primarily a response to enhanced Hadley cell outflow as the steady Rossby wave response observed in the confined anomaly experiments is characteristically a shallow lower-tropospheric feature.

Moving on to experiment 3KW1 with a wavenumber one SST anomaly magnitude twice that of experiment 1.5KW1, one might expect a similar pattern of precipitation response to experiment 1.5KW1 but with increased magnitude. Surprisingly, however, this is not the case (Fig. 5.2(b) and (d)). In particular on the equator from 30°E to 90°E one sees a dramatic increase in precipitation, up to 13.2 mm day^{-1} compared to the control, which is 5 or 6 times the increase seen in experiment 1.5KW1. Therefore, it appears that precipitation is very sensitive to increases in the SST gradient, more so than purely an increase in the absolute magnitude of SST. The effect of this dramatic increase is to move the position of the highest precipitation to about 65°E , which is some 30° west of the highest SST, demonstrating the strong interaction of the dynamics and convection in this experiment. Alongside this increase is the mediocre increase just to the east of the SST anomaly, which was the region of maximum precipitation in experiment 1.5KW1 but which only sees a further 30% increase in experiment 3KW1.

The regions of convective precipitation suppression are similar to experiment 1.5KW1, but with a magnitude in the region of the equatorial SST minimum such that totals are only 10%-15% of those in the control. This is almost certainly the effects of not just the lower SST but the suppression due to a remote response from convection over the SST maximum. In the full precipitation field it is possible to interpret the increase in precipitation between 20° and 30° north and south, and centred at 180°, as a splitting of the ITCZ to form a double convective maxima. However, as we will see later this sub-tropical precipitation increase is mainly due to strengthening of extra-tropical synoptic systems.

Zonal mean convective precipitation totals (not shown) in the wavenumber one experiments are considerably lower than the control between 7.5° north and south, with a maximum difference of up to 5.5 mm day⁻¹ on the equator. Poleward of 7.5° the zonal mean convective precipitation in the wavenumber one experiments is greater than the control, but along with the small changes to dynamic precipitation it is not enough to offset the changes in the deep tropics. It seems that although there is no change in the zonally averaged SST between the control and wavenumber one experiments, the total global precipitation is greater in the control experiment on the time scale of a 12 month integration period. Therefore, the suppressive effects of the circulations that result in response to enhanced convective heating more than offset the precipitation increases in the enhanced convective heating region over the SST anomaly.

The lower-tropospheric asymmetric streamfunctions show gross structures that are wavenumber one in nature (Fig. 5.3). There are low-level cyclones either side of the equator centred at about the longitude of the SST maximum. In experiment 1.5KW1 (Fig. 5.3(a)) there is a dual centre to each cyclone, but in experiment 3KW1 (Fig. 5.3(b)) they are stronger and have a single more definite centre. The cyclones are centred well away from the equator at 40° north and south, but extend closer to the equator on and to the west of the SST anomaly to form the anomalous equatorial westerlies. Anticyclonic anomalies exist in much the same way to the north and south of the SST minimum, but extend to form anomalous easterlies on the equator a considerable distance to the west of the main anticyclonic centres.

The subtle differences in the low-level cyclonic structure between experiments 1.5KW1 and 3KW1 are consistent with the differences in the precipitation distribution, and in particu-

Figure 5.3: Zonally asymmetric streamfunction for (a) experiment 1.5KW1 at 850 mb; (b) experiment 3KW1 at 850 mb; (c) as (a) but at 150 mb; (d) as (b) but at 150 mb.

lar the fact that the positions of the absolute maxima differ considerably. Since the local supply of moisture to the convective precipitation maximum through surface evaporative fluxes is insufficient to maintain the magnitude of precipitation observed, there must be an additional import of moisture from elsewhere. This supply is provided by the large fluxes of latent heating into the relatively dry and warm equatorward flow. This air originates predominantly from sub-tropical descent regions where relative humidity is low and the air acquires moisture through surface fluxes at the same longitude as the convective precipitation maximum.

In experiment 1.5KW1 the convective precipitation (Fig. 5.2(a)) shows two equatorial maxima, with values greater than 18 mm day^{-1} at 45°E and 85°E . This is consistent with the anomalous low-level cyclonic response, especially in the northern hemisphere, where there are two discernible regions of equatorward flow corresponding with the position of the equatorial precipitation maxima, and with the longitudes of the greatest surface evaporative fluxes supplying the precipitation (not shown). Experiment 3KW1 differs considerably from this picture. The low-level cyclone anomalies are much stronger and have a greater influence

on the full low-level flow field and, therefore, the moisture supply to the convection. There is also a lack of the double structure seen in experiment 1.5KW1, such that now there is no equatorward meridional wind anomaly at the longitude of the SST anomaly maximum. Consistent with this is the westward shift in the surface evaporative flux maxima to 70°E, giving a single maximum. Ultimately, this leads to the single precipitation maximum seen at 60° to 70°E.

Differences between the two wavenumber one experiments demonstrate the feedbacks onto the strength and distribution of precipitation that can occur in response to the convective forcing. In particular, in experiment 3KW1 the strong low-level cyclones, on and to the west of the heating, are a response to the strong convective heating. However, these low-level cyclones feed back onto the heating by modifying the supply of moisture to the precipitation maxima. A balance is thus achieved between the propensity of convection to form over the warmest water, and the movement of the moisture source and strongest low-level convergence westwards in response to the lower-tropospheric cyclonic anomalies. The characteristics, as well as the strength, of the feedbacks also change between the wavenumber one experiments, demonstrated by two rainfall maxima in 1.5KW1 and one maximum in 3KW1.

In the upper-troposphere (Fig. 5.3(c) and (d)) the responses are very strongly wavenumber one with anticyclones positioned close to the equator. Both the wavenumber one experiments have a pool of zero absolute vorticity (not shown) extending polewards away from the tropical convective maxima to about 15° north and south. A smaller pool of zero absolute vorticity is also seen in the confined anomaly experiments. In experiment 3KW1 the pool of zero absolute vorticity is located further east than in experiment 1.5KW1, and consistent with this the upper-level anticyclonic anomalies are centred 20 to 30° further east in experiment 3KW1. This results in the anticyclonic anomalies sitting on and slightly to the west of the SST and convective maxima in experiment 1.5KW1, and to the east in experiment 3KW1. Therefore, experiment 1.5KW1 appears to be in closer agreement with observations since the anticyclones tend to be positioned predominantly on and to the west of the convective heating maximum, as seen in Fig. 2.4. Reasons for the differences in the location of the pool of zero absolute vorticity are not clear. However, the results from experiment 3KW1 are consistent with the confined anomaly experiments such that, in the presence of very strong divergent outflow in the meridional direction the upper-tropospheric anticy-

clonic anomalies lie to the east of this outflow. Furthermore, the precipitation in experiment 3KW1 extends further poleward on the eastern side of the SST anomaly maximum, and may be more effective at creating the pool of zero absolute vorticity than in the outflow over the convective maximum.

A consequence of the zero absolute vorticity pool is the increased vorticity gradient and subtropical jet speed on the poleward side of the upper-tropospheric anticyclonic anomalies. Therefore, it is even more important to specify the correct Rossby wave source in this case as the inclusion of the advection of vorticity by the divergent flow will make a significant change to the position of the strongest source. This is clearly seen if we compare a simple representation of the Rossby wave source, $-fD$, with the full source including the divergent flow advection term $-\mathbf{v}_\chi \cdot \nabla \zeta$ (from Eqn. 2.50). With just the simple representation of the Rossby wave source (Fig. 5.4(a)) the distribution is antisymmetric about the equator, with the highest magnitudes near the convective maximum just off the equator where divergence is still large from the increased convective outflow and f is increasing. In this region there are predominantly weak easterlies and westerlies, and so the Rossby wave source is less effective at generating wave activity. Further poleward there is also a large Rossby wave source of opposite sign to the tropical maximum. This is associated with the enhanced descent and upper-tropospheric convergence occurring in response to an increase in the strength of the local Hadley circulation in this region.

Considerable changes occur due to the effects of advection of absolute vorticity by the divergent wind (Fig. 5.4(b)). The tropical Rossby wave source maxima when considering just the $-fD$ term are diminished in response to the pool of zero absolute vorticity, and so the tendency from $-fD$ is largely cancelled by contributions from the relative vorticity term, $-\xi D$. Further poleward and slightly to the west of the SST anomaly maximum, the advection of absolute vorticity on the poleward edge of the anticyclones enhances the strength of the Rossby wave source provided by the convective outflow. Therefore, this dramatically increases the spatial scale of the source and it is much more effective when situated in the strong sub-tropical westerlies, which is in agreement with the findings of Sardeshmukh and Hoskins (1988). In addition, since the effectiveness of the source depends on whether it is positioned in strong sub-tropical westerlies, then it is conceivable that the wave activity characteristics are dependent on the mean flow in the model. For example, if a wavenumber one SST anomaly was superimposed onto the flat axisymmetric SST profile

Figure 5.4: Rossby wave source, (RWS, in s^{-2}) at 150 mb for experiment 3KW1; (a) RWS specified simply ($-fD$); (b) contribution to RWS from the relative vorticity stretching terms and the advection of absolute vorticity by the divergent wind ($-\xi D - \mathbf{v}_\chi \cdot \nabla \xi$).

then the non-local response may look quite different.

5.4 Remote Response

With such a large tropical forcing the effects on the atmosphere are significant in most regions away from the SST maximum itself. It therefore makes it easier to document the response and identify possible mechanisms which may be responsible. In the next few sections certain aspects of the time-mean remote response will be investigated, and attempts made to attribute possible forcing mechanisms.

5.4.1 Equatorial Westerlies

The asymmetric streamfunction (Fig. 5.3) gave an indication of strong upper-level westerlies centred at about 70 to 90°E. These westerlies are the most striking remote response in the wavenumber one experiments. Fig. 5.5 shows that the upper-level westerlies, reaching in excess of 45 ms^{-1} for experiment 3KW1 and about half of this in 1.5KW1, dominate over any response seen in the region of the maximum convective activity itself, and extend along nearly the whole of the equator at 150 mb and down to 600 mb at 120°W. Beneath the westerlies lies the strongest low level easterlies which would seem to be indicative of a large-scale Walker circulation along the equator with compensating ascent in the convective maximum and descent downstream.

Figure 5.5: Zonal wind along the equator (in ms^{-1}) for (a) experiment 1.5KW1; and (b) experiment 3KW1.

On closer inspection of the pattern of upper- and lower- tropospheric divergence, it becomes apparent that the circulation is not largely associated with a Walker circulation. The meridional component of lower- and upper-tropospheric divergence, $\frac{\partial v}{\partial y}$ (Fig. 5.6(b) and (d)), dominates over the zonal component, $\frac{\partial u}{\partial x}$ (Fig. 5.6(a) and (c)), implying that the mass flux associated with convective ascent is transported polewards in the upper-troposphere with descent in the sub-tropics. Therefore, the majority of convective mass is taken up by the local Hadley circulation. At upper-levels the pattern of zonal diffluent suggests that the main region of descent is centred at 20°E , which is in the region of enhanced rainfall and so is clearly not the main descent region. The pattern of zonal diffluent at 150 mb is associated with the equatorial westerly jet entrance and exit regions, but is not accompanied by a distribution in the 850 mb zonal diffluent which would indicate a significant Walker circulation. Westerlies in the upper-troposphere in these experiments would seem to be due to processes other than the simple Kelvin wave response and associated Walker circulation.

In a similar model study by Battisti and Ovens (1995) an aqua-planet GCM, as described in Hess *et al.* (1993), is forced with an approximate wavenumber one SST distribution similar to experiment 3KW1. It is, however, tailored slightly closer to the actual distribution of SST within the tropics, with a narrower $+3\text{ K}$ anomaly warm pool region from 20°N to 20°S , and a -2 K anomaly cold tongue region from 10°N to 10°S better representing the east Pacific. Results from the study are qualitatively very similar to experiment 3KW1 with strong ascent in the region of the warm pool anomaly and upper-tropospheric westerlies centred over the cold tongue region.

The main thrust of the study of Battisti and Ovens (1995) was to understand the mech-

Figure 5.6: Components of the divergence field (in s^{-1}) for experiment 3KW1 at different levels; (a) $\frac{\partial u}{\partial x}$ at 850 mb; (b) $\frac{\partial v}{\partial y}$ at 850 mb; (c) as (a) but at 150 mb (d) as (b) but at 150 mb.

anisms involved in generating an easterly jet confined at low levels on the equator in the eastern Pacific. Such a jet is observed throughout much of the year in this region, and in the equatorial Atlantic also. Their model is able to reproduce this jet with a transition from predominantly easterly trade jets, located just off the equator in hemispherically symmetric SST experiments, to a single equatorial jet core. The hypothesis given is that the jet is maintained against the overturning action of meridional and zonal circulations due to the vertical confinement provided by descent through the region of the upper-tropospheric equatorial westerlies.

In the aqua-planet experiment 3KW1, below the region of dominant upper-level divergence there is considerable descent which caps stronger equatorial easterlies than observed in the control experiment. Fig. 5.7(a) shows that the lower-tropospheric zonal mean easterly trade jets, centred at 7°N and 7°S , coincide with the strongest low-level equatorward flow and the strongest meridional pressure gradient, indicating an essentially geostrophic response in the control experiment. There is no equatorial easterly jet maximum, in agreement with Battisti and Ovens (1995), which is possibly due to the convective maxima rapidly

Figure 5.7: Zonal wind (in ms^{-1}) and vector winds in the section (v, ω) (in ms^{-1} and mb hr^{-1}); (a) zonal average for control experiment; (b) zonal average taken along the equator through the region of maximum lower-troposphere equatorial easterlies (170.625°E to 211.875°W). Vector scale applies to ms^{-1} in the horizontal and mb hr^{-1} in the vertical. Zonal wind contour interval is 2ms^{-1} for negative values and 5ms^{-1} for positive values

redistributing momentum in the vertical. However, in the main equatorial descent region within the westerlies of experiment 3KW1 there exists an equatorial easterly jet core of an equivalent magnitude to the trades in the control experiment (Fig. 5.7(b)). The westerlies are accompanied by descent which supports the hypothesis that, since significant convection is now absent, it can no longer redistribute momentum in the vertical and thus enables an easterly jet to form under confinement from equatorial descent. Vector winds in the section (v, ω) (Fig. 5.7(b)) show the strong reversal of the local Hadley circulation away from the heating region. A reversal anomaly was apparent in the confined anomaly experiments, which just weakened the Hadley circulation, but in experiment 3KW1 the anomaly is strong enough to give a local circulation cell in the opposite sense to the Hadley circulation.

Although a low-level equatorial jet capped by descent results in the aqua-planet from a wavenumber one forcing, the mechanism by which this occurs appears different to that of Battisti and Ovens (1995). Descent within a reversed axisymmetric Hadley circulation is the more likely candidate to provide confinement than descent within a Walker circulation, which was shown to be weak at the expense of the upper-tropospheric rotational flow in the UM. Using the control SST profile on which the SST anomalies are superimposed may be responsible for this difference in confining mechanisms. The Hadley circulation in the control climate is considerably stronger than the equivalent experiment of Battisti and Ovens (1995) and remains dominant in the wavenumber one experiments.

5.4.2 Sub-Tropical Surf Zone

A good indicator for diagnosing the tropical regions susceptible to wave disturbances originating from the mid-latitudes, is the potential vorticity (PV) field. In particular, regions of wave-breaking from these disturbances, with associated momentum transfer, can be identified from the PV field. As we will show later, the strong upper-tropospheric equatorial westerly winds result predominantly from momentum transfer due to the stationary eddies which respond to the convective heating maximum and propagate away from the tropics. However, this creates conditions conducive for mid-latitude transient eddies to propagate closer to the equator. PV on the 350 K surface shows the ability of these baroclinic eddy disturbances to penetrate into the sub-tropics and break, thus depositing their associated momentum. This region of wave breaking is known as the sub-tropical *surf-zone* and two distinctly different aqua-planet examples are shown in Fig. 5.8, which gives one day averaged snapshots of PV on the 350 K surface for the control and experiment 3KW1.

In the control there is a tight meridional gradient of PV which is generally well away from the equator between 20° and 30° in each hemisphere. Such a tight gradient acts as a kind of rubber-band which restricts the majority of transient systems from propagating into the tropics. Instead, as the jet is quite strong the disturbances propagate along it almost zonally with little sub-tropical penetration. In experiment 3KW1 this situation changes somewhat. There is still a rubber-band region at, and to the east of, the convective maximum which is where the angular momentum conserving enhanced Hadley circulation outflow accelerates the sub-tropical jets. Again the synoptic disturbances are seen to propagate along the jet well poleward of the tropics. However downstream from the convective maximum, between 30°W and 90°W , the PV contours have moved significantly equatorwards with breaking off of the 2 PVU contour creating irreversible cut off circulations. For equatorward propagating transient wave trains there is a forcing of easterly momentum in the tropics. In the zonal mean this leads to an increase in the EKE in the tropics, but the forcing of easterlies appears minimal compared to the forcing of westerly momentum by the stationary eddies. This method of diagnosing regions conducive for extratropical-tropical interactions provides a useful tool for predicting the indirect effect on transients that tropical convection anomalies have when they change the models mean state, as shown in this extreme wavenumber one experiment.

Figure 5.8: Potential vorticity on the 350 K surface during one day near the end of the 12 month experiment; (a) control; (b) experiment 3KW1. Contours are ± 1 PVU (thin line), ± 2 PVU (heavy line) and ± 3 PVU (dashed line).

5.4.3 Mechanisms for Zonal Mean Forcing

One result of the wavenumber one experiments is that the pattern of convection forces a significant zonal mean response in the model. The response to this wavenumber one forcing can be seen best in the zonal mean zonal wind (Fig. 5.9). In the full zonal average the effect of the tropical westerlies is to merge slightly the subtropical jets across the equator from each hemisphere and give superrotation in the upper-troposphere above 360 mb in experiment 1.5KW1 (Fig. 5.9(a)), and above 550 mb in experiment 3KW1 (Fig. 5.9(b)). Anomalies from the control zonal mean zonal wind (Figs. 5.9(c) and (d)) show that there is a significant net transport of westerly momentum from higher latitudes towards the equator. It is sufficient to decelerate the subtropical jets by 12 ms^{-1} and accelerate the zonal mean winds on the equator by nearly 25 ms^{-1} in experiment 3KW1. The changes in the tropical upper-troposphere in experiment 1.5KW1 are approximately half that of experiment 3KW1, suggesting a near linear relationship between SST anomaly size and the forcing of the tropical zonally averaged zonal wind.

Such a superrotation response to zonally asymmetric tropical heating has been observed in two-level models of the atmosphere (Suarez and Duffy, 1992, Saravanan, 1993, Woolnough, 1997). In these studies a bifurcation occurs between a conventional climate with weak tropical upper-tropospheric easterlies, and a superrotating climate with strong upper-tropospheric westerlies. The superrotating climate of these two-level models manifests itself when a sufficiently large wavenumber two tropical heating anomaly forcing is applied. Transition to this superrotating state is relatively rapid, occurring within 100 days of the start of

Figure 5.9: Zonal mean zonal wind [u] (in ms^{-1}) for (a) experiment 1.5KW1; (b) experiment 3KW1; (c) as (a) but with control [u] removed; and (d) as (b) but with control [u] removed.

the experiment and achieving a westerly zonal mean equatorial jet in excess of 60 ms^{-1} for a heating above about 4K day^{-1} . Although we obtain a superrotating circulation in the UM with a wavenumber one forcing, we need to understand whether the evolution and mechanisms governing the maintenance of such a climate are similar to those in the two-level models or fundamentally different. Attempts at reproducing such a dramatic superrotating climate, but in a model with a larger number of vertical levels, have been carried out by Woolnough (1997) and Saravanan (1993). In the study by Woolnough (1997) a 5 level primitive equation model as described in James and James (1992) was used in an attempt to generate a superrotating climate with the same forcing as in the two-level model. However, no such transition to strong superrotation was observed. One reason for its absence may have been the very different meridional circulations observed in the two and five-layer models. The upper branch of the meridional circulation in particular is much weaker in the five-layer model than in the two-layer model, with meridional wind strengths reaching just 0.1 ms^{-1} . In contrast the UM experiment 3KW1 has upper branch zonal mean meridional winds in excess of 2.5 ms^{-1} . This gives an indication that the processes responsible for superrotation in the two-level model, but seemingly absent in the five-layer model, may be

Figure 5.10: (a) Evolution of $\frac{[u]_{150mb} + [u]_{850mb}}{2}$ (in ms^{-1}) on the equator, a measure of the depth averaged zonal mean zonal wind indicating the extent of superrotation, from the start of the integration (day 270), (b) the time-mean of $\frac{[u]_{150mb} + [u]_{850mb}}{2}$ averaged between the two hemispheres.

present in the UM aqua-planet. The strength of the heating is certainly higher than the threshold required for superrotation in the two-level model, as the SST anomaly generates a diabatic heating anomaly maximum of 9 K day^{-1} in experiment 3KW1. However, in experiment 1.5KW1 the anomaly maximum is only 3 K day^{-1} but there is still an observed superrotation, suggesting that forcing of equatorial westerly momentum occurs for even small wavenumber one forcings.

The nature of the westerly superrotation in the aqua-planet is slightly different from that in the two-level model. Fig. 5.10(a) shows the evolution of the mean of the upper- and lower- tropospheric zonal mean zonal wind from the start of the experiment. It illustrates that the evolution of the increase in equatorial zonal mean westerlies is the same in both experiment 1.5KW1 and 3KW1, even though the forcing in experiment 1.5KW1 is below the threshold required for superrotation in the two-level model studies. Also of note is the time-mean distribution of this measure of the tropospheric zonal mean wind (Fig. 5.10(b)). It shows that the equatorial increase in westerlies through the tropospheric depth is much less than in the two-level studies, and the sub-tropical westerly jets remain dominant.

The two-level model studies identified changes in the transport of angular momentum by transient eddies as being responsible for the transition to superrotation when subject to significant wavenumber two forcing. In a conventional circulation the transient eddies propagate eastwards and from the extra-tropics to the tropics. The orientation of the eddies facilitates the transport of easterly momentum towards the equator, and westerly momen-

tum to higher latitudes maintaining the distribution of easterlies and westerlies. With westerly phase speeds the transient wave disturbances have critical latitudes, usually in the sub-tropics, where the zonal mean wind is equal to an individual wave's phase speed and so can propagate no further into the tropics. This situation is in general stable since the result of a slight westerly torque in the tropics would allow the transient eddies to propagate further into the tropics and apply a restoring flux of easterly momentum nearer the equator. Also if the equatorial easterlies were increased then the transient eddies would not be able to transport easterly momentum as close to the equator. Stability in the zonal mean circulation of this kind is what occurs in the two-level model studies for forcing below about 4 K day^{-1} , which maintains a conventional circulation.

With the existence of a larger forcing the drastic change to a superrotating climate occurs, initially due to the response of the stationary eddies which apply a westerly torque near the equator. This then allows the transient eddies to travel closer to the equator as the critical latitude moves closer to the equator. However the restoring force due to the transport of easterly momentum by the transient eddies is now insufficient to offset the westerly torque being applied by the stationary eddies. The result of this combination of processes is the transition to a superrotating state as the transient eddies with low zonal wavenumbers do not encounter any critical layers and can propagate right across the equator, whereas the eddies with high zonal wavenumbers are reflected away from the equator by the strong westerlies. These reflected eddies then impact on higher latitudes by transporting easterly momentum poleward and reducing the subtropical jet strength.

We therefore need to examine the mechanisms by which the aqua-planet experiments achieve their zonal mean superrotating state in the upper-troposphere. The main contribution to the time-averaged zonal mean zonal wind tendency away from the earth's surface, and therefore neglecting frictional forcing, is detailed by the following:

$$\frac{\partial[\bar{u}]}{\partial t} = (f - \frac{\partial[\bar{u}]}{\partial y})[\bar{v}] - \underbrace{[u'v']_y}_{(a)} - \underbrace{[u'\omega']_p}_{(b)} - \underbrace{[u^*v^*]_y}_{(c)} - \underbrace{[u^*\omega^*]_p}_{(d)} = 0. \quad (5.1)$$

Here (a) and (b) are the horizontal and vertical convergence of westerly momentum by transient eddies respectively, and (c) and (d) are the equivalent but due to the stationary eddy fluxes. The first term on the right hand side represents tendencies due to angular momentum conservation in the Hadley circulation. In the two-level models the horizontal

Figure 5.11: Contribution to the zonal mean zonal wind tendency $\frac{\partial[\bar{u}]}{\partial t}$ (in $\text{ms}^{-1}\text{day}^{-1}$) due to convergence of eddy momentum from (a) $[\overline{u'v'}]_y$ in the control experiment; (b) $[\overline{u'v'}]_y$ in experiment 3KW1; (c) $[\overline{u^*v^*}]_y$ in experiment 3KW1; and (d) $[\overline{u^*\omega^*}]_p$ in experiment 3KW1. The tendency due to the transient fluxes are low pass filtered with a cut-off of 3 days.

convergence of momentum due to transient eddies changes dramatically, such that easterly forcing in the tropics and strong westerly forcing at mid-latitudes is replaced by easterly forcing in mid-latitudes and mostly westerly forcing equatorward of 37° in a superrotating climate. However, in the aqua-planet such a transition is not observed in the transient fluxes. Fig. 5.11(a) and (b) shows the zonal mean zonal wind tendency due to the horizontal convergence of westerly momentum by the transient eddies, for the control and 3KW1 experiments respectively. In the control the major effect of the horizontal transient flux convergence is to accelerate the poleward flank of the westerly sub-tropical jets by about $3.5 \text{ ms}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$, with weak easterly forcing just poleward and equatorward of this. Horizontal transient flux convergence does not change dramatically in experiment 3KW1 or 1.5KW1. There is slight weakening in the westerly forcing consistent with weaker sub-tropical jets seen in Fig. 5.9, but there is no dramatic shift equatorward of the westerly forcing as seen in the two-level models' superrotating climate.

It appears that stationary eddy fluxes in the aqua-planet not only initiate, but also maintain the westerly superrotation in the upper-troposphere. This explains why there is superrotation in experiment 1.5KW1, which is below the two-level superrotating heating threshold, and indeed to a lesser extent in the confined anomaly experiments 3KEQ and 6KEQ (not shown). The strength of the horizontal momentum flux is related to the shape and magnitude of the stationary waves given by

$$\overline{u^*v^*} = -\frac{kl}{2}|\Psi|^2, \quad (5.2)$$

where Ψ is the horizontal stationary wave amplitude. Therefore, a poleward propagating wave packet with constant k and l will transport westerly momentum towards the equator with a magnitude proportional to the square of the wave amplitude. However, the zonal mean westerly anomalies on the equator for the wavenumber one experiments do not reflect this as the anomaly maximum in experiment 3KW1 is just over twice that in experiment 1.5KW1. What is noticeably different between the two experiments is the depth of the equatorial westerly anomaly, reaching much lower in the atmosphere in experiment 3KW1. It turns out that the extent of westerlies through the depth is due to vertical redistribution by the vertical stationary eddies, term (d) in Eqn. 5.1. Fig. 5.11(c) and (d) show convergence of westerly momentum due to the horizontal and vertical stationary eddies respectively, for experiment 3KW1.

The result of the poleward propagating Rossby waves from the region of heating can clearly be seen as a forcing of the zonal mean wind in the upper-troposphere of up to $7 \text{ ms}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$. This is twice the westerly tendency of the horizontal transient flux convergence in the sub-tropics, and very different from the forcing of the stationary eddies in the two-level models. In experiment 1.5KW1 the convergence of westerly momentum is slightly more than half that of experiment 3KW1, but certainly not one quarter as theory and Eqn. 5.2 would suggest. One reason for the disagreement between theory and model observations may lie in the forcing of the stationary waves, which can be strongly dependent on the mean flow.

Local to the convective anomaly linearity is approximately retained as the upper-tropospheric anticyclonic anomalies in experiment 3KW1 are about twice that in experiment 1.5KW1. However, since the magnitude of the zonally averaged momentum flux associated with the

stationary eddies is not consistent with experiment 3KW1 providing twice the forcing of experiment 1.5KW1, then problems must occur at the source of the stationary waves. The Rossby wave source indicates this to a large extent as the magnitude changes little between the two experiments. In fact the major change between the two experiments is one of position and not magnitude, with the Rossby wave source due to the anomalous convective outflow being further west in experiment 1.5KW1 and only 30% weaker than in experiment 3KW1. This difference in position is consistent with the upper-tropospheric cyclonic anomalies on the poleward and eastward side of the tropical anticyclonic anomalies, which are also slightly further west in experiment 1.5KW1 (cf. Fig. 5.3(c)).

Effects of the convergence of westerly momentum due to the vertically and zonally tilted stationary eddies near the equator cancel much of the horizontal westerly momentum flux convergence, especially in the upper-most troposphere, with an easterly tendency of $7.4 \text{ ms}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$ in experiment 3KW1 (Fig. 5.11(d)). There is, however, a redistribution of westerlies throughout the bulk of the troposphere with tendencies of up to $4 \text{ ms}^{-1} \text{ day}^{-1}$, thus accounting for the depth of the equatorial westerlies in the zonal mean of experiment 3KW1. In experiment 1.5KW1 there is significant convergence of eddy momentum in the vertical near the equator, but as with the horizontal convergence it is just over half the magnitude of experiment 3KW1. The spatial distribution is also much different only extending down to about 500 mb and so lacking the second maximum situated at about 680 mb which is seen in experiment 3KW1.

The tendency from the vertical convergence of momentum due to the stationary eddies arises through a global scale zonal wavenumber one eddy where descent is, on the whole, correlated with westerlies in the upper-troposphere, and ascent is correlated with easterlies in the lower-troposphere. In experiment 3KW1 these waves extend down much deeper into the troposphere than in experiment 1.5KW1, illustrated by the deeper vertical convergence of eddy momentum.

5.4.4 Storm Track Changes

As well as the influence in the tropics downstream from the convective heating maximum, the response in the wavenumber one experiments extends to affect changes in the mid-latitude storm tracks. In the zonal average consistent with the slight reduction in the zonal

mean westerlies the eddy kinetic energy (EKE), a measure of storm track activity, is reduced mostly on the equatorward fringe of the mid-latitudes. This is partly in response to the reduced Hadley circulation poleward outflow at most longitudes, which reduces the strength of the angular momentum conserving part of the jet and in general, therefore, the strength of unstable waves able to grow on the jet.

However, in the region of intensified tropical outflow poleward of the convective heating angular momentum is conserved locally to a higher latitude than elsewhere, shown by a pool of zero absolute vorticity in the upper-troposphere. This has the effect of accelerating the sub-tropical jet and making it more baroclinically unstable for disturbances propagating downstream from it. Fig. 5.12 illustrates the changes in mid-latitude activity due to the large tropical heating in experiment 3KW1. The eddy kinetic energy is enhanced downstream of the longitude of the maximum tropical convective heating anomaly on the poleward side of the sub-tropical jet maxima centred at 150°W and 45°N and S . In response to the more intense mid-latitude systems that can grow on the subtropical jet and propagate downstream, the dynamical precipitation due to large-scale processes is enhanced, particularly towards the equator. Magnitudes are greater than in the control by up to 3 mm day^{-1} at around 180° , representing a 40% increase between 25 and 35° in each hemisphere.

This demonstrates that tropical forcing can impact strongly on the downstream mid-latitude climate. Downstream from the tropical convective minima the effects of reduced Hadley circulation outflow are shown by the negative anomalies in EKE and associated reduced dynamic precipitation to the east of this.

A further remote consequence of the tropical convective heating anomaly is the propagation of the mid-latitude systems deep into the tropics just downstream of the dynamic precipitation maxima centred at about 120°E . This is shown by positive anomalies of EKE found in this region, which projects on to the zonal mean giving a local tropical maximum.

Therefore, the mid-latitude systems are intensified slightly downstream of the strong jet at around 45°N and S , consequently increasing the dynamically produced precipitation as well as the convective precipitation as the cold fronts trail into the tropics and trigger convection over the warmer waters. Patterns of synoptic systems propagating into the tropics can be seen in daily aqua-planet model data and are frequently observed during the DJF season in the east Pacific.

Figure 5.12: 250 mb high-pass eddy kinetic energy (contours, in m^2s^{-1}) and dynamic precipitation (shading, mm day^{-1}) from experiment 3KW1, each with the control zonal mean removed. High-pass filtering period is up to 3 days.

The succession of processes by which the stronger mid-latitude disturbances develop and extend into the tropics triggering convection is not dissimilar to that proposed by Slingo (1998b). In the study the author proposes mechanisms based on observations and GCM simulations, whereby the triggering of tropical convection on time scales of days in the east Pacific is part of an intimate tropical-extratropical interaction. The observed sequence of events is shown schematically in Fig. 5.13. The exact mechanism involves the flaring of convection near Indonesia in response to lower-tropospheric cold surges originating off the coast of China and enhancing surface fluxes over the warmer waters. Increasing the Hadley circulation outflow in response to the convective flaring intensifies the jet extending it further eastwards into the Pacific. Amplification of the equatorward Rossby wave train follows, with the ambient upper-tropospheric westerlies in the east Pacific allowing the intrusion of troughs into the tropics and the triggering of convection. Finally the convective response excites easterly waves which propagate near the equator and westwards back along the Pacific.

Much of this series of events occurs in the wavenumber one experiments. However, the initialisation of the warm pool region convection appears to be quite different and not due to cold surges, as shown schematically in Fig 5.14. In animations of model fields the convection intensification is preceded by disturbances propagating along the equator from about 0° .

Figure 5.13: Schematic demonstrating the events associated with the extratropical influence on tropical convection (Slingo, 1998b).

Figure 5.14: Schematic to illustrate the succession of events which occur in response to strong tropical convection over the SST anomaly in the wavenumber one aqua-planet experiments. The light and dark shaded regions represent increases in the dynamic and convective precipitation respectively when compared with the control experiment. The 'T' symbol indicates where the extra-tropical troughs are able to move closer to the equator.

As it moves towards the SST maximum at 95°E the convection intensifies, but when it reaches the SST maximum the disturbance moves poleward around the quasi-stationary anticyclones leading to intensification of the sub-tropical jet on its poleward and eastern side. The path of events after this follows quite closely that in Fig. 5.13 with upper-level troughs impinging into the region centred around 180°E where there are tropical westerlies. These westerlies may be too strong to allow the trough to impact deep into the tropics and the wave trains probably get reflected back poleward. Therefore, increases in convective precipitation occur nearer 25°N and S, giving the impression of a split ITCZ, rather than at 10°N and S as seen in Slingo (1998b) where the upper-tropospheric westerlies in the east Pacific are much weaker.

5.5 Conclusions

Results from the wavenumber one SST anomaly experiments illustrate the non-linear response of the model to large tropical forcings. Locally this is shown as a change in the position of the tropical precipitation maximum between experiment 1.5KW1 and 3KW1, even though the position of the SST anomaly maximum is unchanged. As a consequence the local dynamical response also changes in nature, with the upper-tropospheric anticyclones being displaced between the two experiments. More remote from the SST anomaly region, the magnitude of the forced stationary planetary waves are not linear between experiment 1.5KW1 and 3KW1, with the result that the zonally averaged zonal wind has a smaller than predicted difference between the two experiments.

The forcing of strong zonal mean westerlies occurs through westerly momentum transfer from poleward propagating stationary Rossby wave trains. Unlike the two-level model studies discussed, the mid-latitude transient activity does not change significantly when subject to wavenumber one forcing, and plays no role in generating equatorial westerlies.

Furthermore, this type of simplified experimentation with strong forcing enables processes acting over remote distances to be identified much more easily than in conventional climate studies. In particular the presence of tropical-tropical and tropical-extra-tropical interactions have been identified with the upper-tropospheric rotational response and local Hadley type circulations dominating over longitudinal Walker circulations.

Chapter 6

Transients

6.1 Introduction

Previous chapters have been predominantly concerned with the time-averaged steady response to SST diagnosed in the framework of the long time scale response to tropical convective heating. However, as discussed previously, a large proportion of the time-mean structure of many tropical features such as the ITCZ result as a consequence of coherent shorter time scale transient disturbances which propagate within the tropical wave guide and have temperature, wind and convective precipitation signatures. Analysis of convective organisation on these shorter time scales allows us to identify their wave properties and how the average effects of numerous individual disturbances make up the time-mean response. For example, it is of interest to know whether the ITCZ rainfall is made up of a steady rainfall rate or a succession of higher and lower rainfall events. The nature of this tropical variability is therefore important for determining convective regimes in response to SST. Comparisons between the wave characteristics of the model and theoretical dispersion relationships for waves within the tropical wave guide can also be performed.

6.2 Observed Transient Behaviour

Observations of the real atmosphere clearly show the propagation of a variety of wave-like disturbances within the tropics, organising smaller scale individual convective events

Figure 6.1: Hovmöller plot of twice-daily OLR (in W m^{-2}) averaged between 10°S and 2.5°N and for 6Z on 1st September, 1992 through to 6Z on 1st March 1993. Time increases from top to bottom. Taken from Wheeler and Kiladis (1999).

into a range of larger temporal and spatial scales. These individual disturbances can be seen in Fig. 6.1 which shows OLR, a good proxy for convection, throughout a region of the tropics along all longitudes. Lower values of OLR show the higher convective cloud tops of the deepest clouds associated with the most intense convective precipitation. The tropical continental regions of Africa and South America stand out strongly as a stationary convective signal at about 25°E and 60°W respectively, reflecting the propensity of land surfaces to warm strongly helping to initiate convection.

The regions of strongest transient activity occur in the Indian ocean and west Pacific warm pool region. The largest OLR variance can be seen as a series of eastward propagating disturbances with very low OLR values of less than 140 Wm^{-2} , indicating the strongest precipitation in the period mainly during December to February. Large disturbances of this type in this region are classified as Madden and Julian oscillations (MJOs) (Madden and Julian, 1994). Observations show a strong propagating signal of upper- and lower-tropospheric winds and temperature associated with the disturbance in this region. In some cases a signal in upper-tropospheric velocity potential due to this MJO disturbance can be traced around the globe, mainly as a wavenumber one and two response Lorenz (1984). The MJO is the dominant mode of variability on time scales of 30 to 60 days, but there has been much research into its role in variability on longer time scales, in particular its effect on ENSO. Studies have postulated that the MJO can lead to propagating oceanic Kelvin waves as a response to the westerly wind bursts indicative of a MJO event (Kindle and Phoebus, 1995), which may facilitate the movement of warmer SSTs into the central Pacific during an El Niño event. Indeed the strong El Niño event of 1997/98 was immediately preceded by three strong MJO events between December 96 and May 97 (Slingo, 1998a) with westerly wind bursts suggesting the MJO may, at least in part, be responsible for initiating an El Niño event.

As well as the dominant MJO variability Fig. 6.1 also shows less long lived propagating disturbances with smaller spatial scales that, although their convection signal is weaker, provide considerable mesoscale organisation of convection. Finally the cooler SSTs of the eastern Pacific are evident by the lack of a significant propagating OLR signal. Many of these equatorially trapped wave disturbances prove important in the circulation of the stratosphere through the vertical propagation of wave activity. Indeed theories for the stratospheric quasi-biennial oscillation (QBO) rely on an interaction between vertically

Figure 6.2: Hovmöller plot showing 6 hourly averaged precipitation rate (in mm day^{-1}) averaged between 5°N and 5°S for the whole 12 month period of the control experiment (in 4 month sections). Time increases from bottom to top and the contour interval is 5 mm day^{-1} .

propagating waves originating in the tropical troposphere (Lindzen and Holton, 1968).

6.3 Axisymmetric Experiments

Turning to the aqua-planet axisymmetric experiments it was clear from Chapter 3 that the time-mean model tropical climates are quite different from that observed. In particular the ITCZ precipitation maxima on the equator are considerably greater and more confined in the control and peaked experiments, whereas the flat experiment produced a broad and much reduced precipitation maximum. However the vertical zonal wind profile in the deep tropics was not significantly different between these three cases. Since the transients play a cumulative role in forming the time-mean climate it is important to investigate how they differ between these experiments and the observed situation.

Figure 6.3: As Fig. 6.2 but for experiment using the *flat* SST profile.

6.3.1 Precipitation

The 6 hourly averaged precipitation rate averaged between 5°N and 5°S for the whole 12 month period of the control experiment is shown in Fig. 6.2. Distinct wave propagation patterns are apparent throughout the period. The dominant direction of propagation is eastward with a phase speed of around 18 ms^{-1} . Some disturbances can be seen to propagate around the equator as a series of enhanced and suppressed rainfall regions in a time of about 25 days, especially later in the experiment period. There is also secondary wave propagation in a westward direction, this is seen particularly when the strength of eastward propagation is weaker. The westward disturbances are predominantly slower moving with a phase speed of around 10 ms^{-1} and have a more localised region of propagation. The westward and eastward propagation gives a criss-cross lattice appearance across the domain. The magnitudes of precipitation observed in this experiment reveal that the time-mean is made up of periods of strong rainfall often in excess of 30 mm day^{-1} and periods of relatively

little rainfall, sometimes less than 5 mm day^{-1} for several consecutive days. Comparison with the observed OLR transient activity in Fig. 6.1 reveals that the larger spatial scales of the MJO are not captured in this experiment. However, the model transients are reminiscent of much of the wave propagation throughout the Indian ocean/west Pacific region.

Transients in the peaked experiment are similar to those in the control experiment, despite the mean precipitation on the equator being twice as large as in the control. However, in the transient analysis precipitation is averaged between 5°N and 5°S which gives approximately equal magnitudes in the control and peaked experiments. Analysis of animations show precipitation of greater than 5 mm day^{-1} at all times on the equator and interaction with the mid-latitudes is much less frequent than in the control.

Switching attention to the flat SST experiment, Fig. 6.3 shows a similar 12 month period of precipitation transient activity as shown for the control case. Equilibrium is reached quite rapidly such that the transient activity changes little after about the first 20 days (day 290 of the model clock). Immediately we can see that rainfall rates are much reduced from the control case, as expected, since the mean rainfall rate in this latitude band is approximately one quarter that of the control case. There is little or no propagation in the eastward direction and the westward propagation is at a phase speed of about 9 ms^{-1} which is slightly slower than the control case and close to the value of the mean tropospheric easterlies in this experiment.

It is clear, therefore, that forcing from an SST profile with differing near equator latitudinal distributions results not only in a different mean precipitation distribution but also in radically different transient properties.

6.3.2 Zonal Wind

Analysis of the transient nature of the zonal wind provides an insight into the more dynamical and large-scale consequences of the organisation and propagation of tropical convection. Fig. 6.4 shows the Hovmoller plot of the full 150 mb zonal wind in much the same way as the precipitation Hovmoller plots, except that the averaging is between 6.25°N and 6.25°S . Although the mean zonal wind is slightly easterly at this height, of order 3 ms^{-1} , there are considerable intense bursts of westerly winds that can clearly be traced as propagating

Figure 6.4: Hovmöller plot showing 6 hourly averaged 150 mb zonal wind (in ms^{-1}) averaged between 6.25°N and 6.25°S for the whole 12 month experiment period of the control experiment (in 4 month sections). Time increases from bottom to top and the contour interval is 10 ms^{-1} .

around the equator three or four times, particularly in the middle to latter part of the period. This is consistent with the more dynamical features of the MJO and other tropical wave disturbances being traced around the tropics more easily than in the precipitation signal. The westerly winds seem to, on the whole, provide an envelope for the stronger precipitation wave disturbances and the easterlies for the weaker precipitation disturbances, but this is by no means always the case.

The strongest individual convective events are co-located with a strengthening of the easterlies and westerlies in the local vicinity increasing the amplitude of the propagating wave. The exact relation between this convective organisation and the zonal wind at this level is unclear as the position of this stronger convection in relation to the phase of the wave varies such that there is sometimes intensification or suppression of the propagating wave.

Figure 6.5: As Fig. 6.4 but for experiment using the *flat* SST profile.

The zonal wind transients in the flat experiment (Fig. 6.5) seem to adjust to the new SST after 60 days which is a longer period than the adjustment time for the precipitation. Again as with the precipitation for this experiment the propagation is almost entirely westwards after the initial adjustment period. The zonal wind direction is easterly throughout virtually the whole period and it appears that the weaker easterlies are approximately co-located with the stronger precipitation signals.

6.4 Anomaly Experiments

Inclusion of SST anomalies in the aqua-planet experiments breaks the axisymmetric nature of the mean climate, but how does this change affect the transient disturbance properties? By including tropical SST anomalies one would hope to represent some of the east-west asymmetry seen in the tropical Pacific basin where east Pacific SST is, in non El Niño conditions, some 6K cooler than west Pacific SST.

Figure 6.6: Hovmöller plot showing 6 hourly averaged precipitation rate (in mm day^{-1}) averaged between 5°N and 5°S for the whole 12 month period of experiment 3KEQ (in 4 month sections). Time increases from top to bottom and the contour interval is 5 mm day^{-1} .

6.4.1 Precipitation

The pattern of mean precipitation in experiments forced with confined SST anomalies sees a strong maximum in the region of the SST anomaly with suppression, compared to the control case, just to the west and east of the SST anomaly. The transient activity in precipitation for experiment 3KEQ, shown in Fig. 6.6, clearly reveals the stationary signal of enhanced precipitation over the SST anomaly. However, propagating disturbances are, on many occasions throughout the 12 month period, able to disrupt the intense convection over the SST anomaly. Both the westward and eastward propagating waves seen in the control experiment are also evident in this case and can be seen to influence the position and strength of the precipitation maximum over the anomaly.

It is not immediately apparent whether the wave characteristics of the convective distur-

Figure 6.7: As Fig. 6.6 but for experiment 3KW1.

bances have been significantly changed by the inclusion of the SST anomaly. However, it is certain that the eastward propagating disturbances find it more difficult to penetrate the enhanced precipitation region and propagate right around the globe.

Precipitation transients in the more extreme 3KW1 experiment shown in Fig. 6.7 are, as expected, markedly different from those in any of the other experiments. Firstly, the lower SST, with a minimum of 24°C 180° from the SST maximum, is not conducive to strong convection and so transient signals are difficult to trace in this region. Secondly, from the location of the strongest precipitation events it is not obvious where the SST anomaly reaches its maximum along the equator. The transient disturbances, therefore, have a much greater role in determining the distribution of precipitation which is consistent with observations over the west Pacific and Indian Ocean regions.

To the west of the SST equatorial maximum, between about 30°E and 90°E , the eastward propagating disturbances move up the zonal SST gradient and intensify. Westward propa-

Figure 6.8: Hovmöller plot showing 6 hourly averaged 150 mb zonal wind (in ms^{-1}) averaged between 5°N and 5°S for the whole 12 month period of experiment 3KEQ (in 4 month sections). Time increases from top to bottom and the contour interval is 10 ms^{-1} .

gating disturbances also organise the convection, but this tends to be on a smaller spatial scale and to be confined to the immediate vicinity of the SST anomaly maximum. They originate slightly to the east of the anomaly maximum. There are also extended periods of stationary convective events, some as long as 15 days, in certain longitudinal regions. One such region is centred around 120°E where eastward propagating disturbance have moved through the elevated SST region and become stationary with a modest signal averaging about 30 mm day^{-1} .

Inspection of precipitation animations over the global domain reveals that rather than the convective region becoming stationary, at about 120°E trailing cold fronts from mid latitude systems are able to advect over the warmer region of the SST anomaly. The tropical convection is then able to move meridionally as it is drawn away from the equator due to the interaction of these convective events and the trailing fronts at this longitude.

Figure 6.9: as Fig. 6.8 but for experiment 3KW1.

The cumulative effect of many of these events is reflected in the time-mean precipitation field (cf. Fig. 5.2(a)), where higher precipitation values extend further poleward between 90°E and 120°E than at any other longitude.

6.4.2 Zonal Wind

Analysis of the equatorial zonal wind Hovmoller for experiment 3KEQ (Fig. 6.8) reveals a quasi-stationary signal over the anomaly region with easterlies reflecting the outflow along the equator from the enhanced convection there. However, the eastward propagating waves tend to have associated with them stronger westerlies which push the zonal average at this level from slightly easterly ($[u] \approx 5 \text{ ms}^{-1}$), in the control, to just slightly westerly ($[u] \approx 5 \text{ ms}^{-1}$).

Unlike the control experiment the westward propagating disturbances rarely make it completely around the globe, however, on a few occasions the westerly phase propagates right

through the anomaly region. One clear example of this occurs around day 440 between 60°E and 120°E and when compared with precipitation in Fig. 6.6 it is apparent that this leads to a drastic reduction of precipitation, both in the anomaly region itself and just to the west where the precipitation rate falls below 5 mm day⁻¹ for 3 to 4 days. Other similar events occur when the westerly phase of the westward propagating disturbances impinges on the anomaly region. There then occurs a suppression of precipitation, but not as strong as when the disturbance moves right through the anomaly region.

As with the precipitation field the 150 mb zonal wind in experiment 3KW1 (Fig. 6.9) differs considerably from the control. Extensive westerly anomalies, often in excess of 60 ms⁻¹, propagate eastwards in the western hemisphere region. Such westerly wind pulses are consistent with the quasi-steady Rossby wave response to the convective heating, which generates equatorial westerlies downstream of the heating anomaly as a consequence of westerly momentum convergence from the poleward propagating waves.

As with the previous experiment when the eastward propagating waves are in a strong westerly phase, they are able to impinge on the main convective region which has the effect of reducing the precipitation and pushing the convective region back towards the centre of the SST anomaly maximum. When the westerlies do not propagate strongly into the anomaly region the convection is able to organise much further west of the SST and move over the SST anomaly maximum to give the most intense precipitation. Associated with this precipitation enhancement is a strengthening of the easterlies moving eastwards over the anomaly region.

6.5 2-D Fourier Analysis of Transient Activity

In both observations and the model data, precipitation can be considered to be organised by a whole spectrum of wave disturbances of varying wavenumber, frequency and magnitude. This makes it extremely difficult to quantitatively compare the transient activity between individual aqua-planet experiments and with the observed activity. Since each of the model experiments were performed for a 12 month period, this allows us to calculate statistics of the transient activity based upon a 2-D Fourier analysis in both zonal wavenumber, k , and frequency, ω .

6.5.1 Methodology

The approach we take in our analysis is similar to that taken in the study by Wheeler and Kiladis (1999). They use 18 years of satellite observed OLR in the tropics, which is an extended data set of that shown in Fig. 6.1. Here precipitation data is used, for which OLR is considered to be a good proxy or surrogate. With only one year of data the power of the disturbances will be considerably lower than that of Wheeler and Kiladis (1999). However, the steady idealised nature of the SST and solar forcing are expected to compensate for this to a certain extent.

The time series used for the Fourier analysis is the whole 12 months of data from each experiment, but with the first 20 days ignored to allow for a reasonable amount of spin-up. Referring back to the Hovmoller plots of Section 6.3 and 6.4.1 reveals that the transient precipitation activity characteristic of each experiment is established at about 20 days into the run.

The whole time series is split up into a series of 100 day segments, each covering the tropics between 10°N and 10°S . The UM meridional grid spacing of 2.5° means there are nine grid points between and including 10°N and 10°S , and so each 100 day segment is further split into these nine latitude strips. The region between 10°N and 10°S encompasses the ITCZ feature in the time-mean and rainfall rates poleward of this are negligible in the subtropical high regions and, therefore, are not included. Next the average of each segment is removed and the time series is tapered to zero over the first and last 5 days of each 100 day segment. Data windowing in this way minimises the effects of spectral leakage, and by overlapping the individual 100 day segments by 2 months, giving 7 segments in total, the loss of data due to tapering is kept to a minimum. The results are not sensitive to this overlap period or to whether the tapering is performed over 5 or 10 days. For each latitude in each 100 day segment Fourier analysis is performed in longitude to obtain the zonal planetary wavenumber coefficients, then in time to obtain the full wavenumber-frequency spectrum. Finally the power is averaged for each latitude strip, and then furthermore for each 100 day segment.

Following Wheeler and Kiladis (1999), benefit can also be gained from this 2-D Fourier analysis by comparing the wave characteristics of the observations and aqua-planet experiments

with theoretical analysis of the dispersion characteristics of individual tropical wave modes. This follows the analysis of the shallow water equations relevant to the tropical atmosphere (Matsuno, 1966, Gill, 1980). A summary of such an analysis was given in Chapter 2 and the modes of interest are shown in Fig. 2.2. By superimposing the modes of interest onto the wavenumber-frequency analysis the agreement with theoretical analysis can be assessed.

To extract the maximum information from the wavenumber-frequency analysis additional pre-processing and post-processing of the data is carried out. Before any analysis is performed on the grid point data, $PPN(\phi)$, it is split into its symmetric, $PPNS(\phi)$, and antisymmetric, $PPNA(\phi)$ components such that:

$$\begin{aligned} PPNS(\phi) &= \frac{PPN(+\phi) + PPN(-\phi)}{2} \\ PPNA(\phi) &= \frac{PPN(+\phi) - PPN(-\phi)}{2}. \end{aligned} \quad (6.1)$$

In this way disturbances that are symmetric about the equator can be distinguished from antisymmetric disturbances which have opposite signs on either side of the equator. The sum of the power in the symmetric and antisymmetric components of the spectra is equal to the power of the full component.

After the symmetric and antisymmetric spectra have been calculated further analysis is performed. This involves removing a so called *background* spectra from the raw spectra. This background spectra is constructed by taking the combined power of the symmetric and antisymmetric spectra and smoothing many times in both frequency and wavenumber to sufficiently remove any periodic signals, leaving only a spectra which reflects random non-periodic processes. A sufficient smoothing is 10 passes of a 1-2-1 power conservative filter in both frequency and wavenumber. The results are only significantly sensitive to the exact nature of the smoothing at frequencies greater than 12 to 15 cycles/month, which is in general outside our region of interest. Thus dividing the raw spectra by this background spectra highlights power mostly associated with periodic non-random disturbances.

6.5.2 Observations

Analysis of the observed OLR time series, taken from the study of Wheeler and Kiladis (1999), gives symmetric and antisymmetric spectra which are red in both wavenumber and

Figure 6.10: Observations of the frequency-wavenumber distribution of OLR averaged between 15°N and 15°S for an 18 year period showing (a) antisymmetric wave modes; and (b) symmetric wave modes (Wheeler and Kiladis, 1999).

frequency. However, this very red nature conceals information about the wave disturbances. Dividing the raw spectra by the derived background spectra gives the normalised spectra shown in Fig. 6.10. This and subsequent figures have the dispersion relation for a selection of equatorial wave modes and equivalent depths superimposed. The dispersion relationship is shown for equivalent depths of 12, 25 and 50 m which corresponds to internal gravity wave speeds of 10.8 , 15.7 and 22.1 ms^{-1} respectively. Concentrating first on the eastward propagating waves in the symmetric spectrum, the MJO signal that could clearly be seen in the raw observations appears as the most powerful disturbance with a period between 30 and 60 days, and a scale between zonal wavenumber 1 and 4. This confirms that the MJO is order one important for the organisation of precipitation in the tropics on these time scales. The theoretical Kelvin wave dispersion lines coincide with disturbances that are distinct from the MJO and spread mostly over periods from 2.5 to 10 days and wavenumbers from 2 to 10. The equivalent depth these waves correspond to is about 50 m at low wavenumbers, but the phase speed of these waves appears to slow down to be consistent with an equivalent depth of 25 m at higher frequency and wavenumber.

Of the westward travelling waves the $n=1$ Rossby wave (ER) shows the most power, although

Figure 6.11: Raw 2-D frequency-wavenumber Fourier analysis of precipitation for the control experiment showing the log power; (a) full component; (b) symmetric component; (c) antisymmetric component; (d) background spectra calculated from a smoothed averaged of the symmetric and antisymmetric components.

over a reduced range of wavenumbers and frequency. In addition the waves are slowed compared to the Rossby wave equivalent depth such that the phase speed corresponds more closely with an equivalent depth of 12 m.

Also of note in the symmetric wave spectrum are the $n=1$ westward (WIG) and eastward (EIG) propagating inertio-gravity waves at periods less than 2.5 days^{-1} . These convectively-coupled waves are the weakest disturbances, and will not be considered in this analysis.

In the antisymmetric component of the wavenumber-frequency spectra we can see that there still exists power associated with the MJO, but it is much reduced in strength and wavenumber range compared to the symmetric component. The dominant convectively coupled waves occur between periods of about 6 days and 2 days and can be split into the westward propagating mixed Rossby-gravity waves (MRG) and the faster moving eastward propagating $n=0$ inertio-gravity waves (EIG). These gravity waves have a strong zonal mean signal at about wavenumber 4 and previous to the study of Wheeler and Kiladis (1999) had

Figure 6.12: 2-D frequency-wavenumber Fourier analysis of precipitation for the control experiment after division by the background spectra: (a) full component; (b) symmetric component; (c) antisymmetric component. Values greater than zero represent power above that of the background spectrum. White lines indicate dispersion curves for a number of theoretical equatorial wave disturbances supported by the shallow water equations with equivalent depths of 12, 25 and 50 m.

not been observed. The mixed Rossby-gravity waves are well documented in the atmosphere, having periods of 3-5-days with significant propagation into the stratosphere. Again there is weak power at frequencies smaller than 2 days^{-1} forming convectively coupled eastward (EIG) and westward (WIG) inertio-gravity waves, but for the $n=2$ mode.

6.5.3 Control Transient Statistics

A similar wavenumber-frequency analysis is carried out with the aqua-planet. It is first performed for the control experiment and compared with observations. The analysis of the full, symmetric, and antisymmetric components are shown in Fig. 6.11 together with a derived background spectra for this particular experiment climate. Calculations are only performed up to a period of 2 days or 15 cycles/month. This covers the region up to the thick horizontal line at 2 days^{-1} in Fig. 6.10 and so will not include information about the

higher frequency inertio-gravity waves as noise tends to dominate in this region.

Prior to the removal of the background spectra the power in the westward and eastward propagating waves is apparent. In the absence of any zonal asymmetry, such that the SST and insolation forcing are symmetric, there is still a significant power in the antisymmetric component. As with the analysis of OLR observations the spectrum is red in wavenumber and frequency, but is not as smooth with only 1 year of data.

The result of dividing the full, symmetric and antisymmetric components of the spectra by the background spectra is shown in Fig. 6.12. In this and subsequent figures the theoretical dispersion relationship is overlaid for the same three equivalent depths as shown in Fig. 6.10. Values of log power greater than zero indicates power in the disturbances above that of the background spectra. The spectral peaks are more fragmented and weaker than the observed spectra which is again a consequence of the limited data set available. However there are coherent peaks in both the symmetric and antisymmetric spectra. The symmetric spectrum is dominated by the eastward propagating disturbances which are close to the theoretical Kelvin wave. They coincide with an equivalent depth of between 25 m and 50 m which, while remembering the analysis is for precipitation, is in good agreement with the OLR observations in Fig. 6.10, particularly at lower frequency and wavenumber. This is on the face of it quite surprising since the climatologies in terms of rainfall, zonal mean circulation and land mass distributions differ so markedly.

At frequencies greater than about 6 cycles/month there appears to be a speed up of Kelvin waves. This contrasts with the OLR observations which show a slow down of Kelvin waves at frequencies greater than 6 cycles/month. The Kelvin wave therefore corresponds to the dominant transient activity observed in the model data giving the bands of enhanced and suppressed precipitation propagating around the globe with spatial scales of wavenumber 4 or 5, and a frequency of 3 or 4 cycles/month. There is a considerable spike occurring in the power spectrum at wavenumber 5 and at a frequency of 1 cycle/month. This seems to be outside the envelope of the Kelvin wave and is not immediately obvious in the time series of precipitation. This peak may form part of the models MJO but it is certainly deficient compared to the statistics of the observed MJO.

There is also little evidence of an MJO at periods of 30-60 days and wavenumbers 1 and 2 in the control. This may be due to a number of reasons. Firstly it has been suggested that the

MJO has a large ocean coupled component where SST anomalies propagate eastwards with the convective anomaly, but lagging it by about $\frac{1}{4}$ of a cycle (Hendon and Glick, 1997). Such a mechanism would not be represented in the aqua-planet atmosphere only setup. Secondly the model may not be able to represent the mode at all, even in a coupled configuration. Having performed only non-coupled aqua-planet experiments we cannot know for sure if a coupled configuration could give rise to an MJO. Finally the actual aqua-planet set-up itself, with an ocean covered surface, may be insufficient to produce an MJO and interaction of the ocean atmosphere and land surface could be required in the generation mechanism.

The power in the westward propagating waves is smaller than in the eastward waves, but the convectively coupled $n=1$ Rossby waves can be identified at wavenumbers 1-7 and up to frequencies of 4 cycles/month. At wavenumbers 1-3 the peak in the spectrum coincides with equivalent depths similar to the observations, but at larger wavenumbers the power peaks correspond to a larger equivalent depth of 80-90m. It may, therefore, be the case that the westward propagating precipitation disturbances lock to a greater equivalent depth than seen in observations, in response to the different prevailing climatic conditions of the aqua-planet.

In the antisymmetric spectrum there is less evidence for strong convectively coupled wave activity in the aqua-planet. The strongest antisymmetric wave activity in observations occurs in the form of $n=0$ eastward inertio-gravity waves and westward Rossby gravity waves. Both these wave modes have peaks in their power at zonal wavenumbers greater than 4. In the control experiment there appears to be some power in the eastward inertio-gravity waves at wavenumber 5 and in the mixed Rossby-gravity waves at wavenumbers 5-9. There is though a lack of power for these waves at low wavenumbers. One possible reason for the lack of activity in this wavenumber-frequency region is the dominance of the symmetric modes, mainly Kelvin waves, which can occur in the absence of significant antisymmetric forcing (Itoh and Ghil, 1988). This is certainly the case for the control experiment.

Close inspection of precipitation animations over the global domain reveal that trailing cold fronts from mid-latitude systems seem to be important for the generation of antisymmetric forcing. This is possible since the mid-latitude systems are certainly not in phase between the two hemispheres and so the effects of these systems occur independently in each hemisphere. This observation agrees with the hypothesis of Itoh and Ghil (1988) who sug-

gest that the antisymmetric forcing from mid-latitudes will help select the dominant zonal wavenumber of these mixed Rossby-gravity waves. In this case the dominant mid-latitude structure is of order wavenumber 6 or 7, which agrees approximately with the wavenumber of the peak in the Rossby gravity wave disturbances.

Overlaid in Fig. 6.12(c) are the dispersion curves corresponding to the $n=2$ Rossby wave, for the three equivalent depths as before. At frequencies less than 3 cycles/month and wavenumbers 1-2 there is power maxima in westward propagating disturbances. This is an antisymmetric wave, but the location of the peak is at a frequency which is possibly too high to indicate a convectively coupled $n=2$ Rossby wave. Alternatively it may be an $n=2$ Rossby wave but locked to an equivalent depth which is very much greater than 50m.

6.6 Other Aqua-Planet Experiment Transient Statistics

The control experiment provided a good case for comparison of observed and model statistics. For the remainder of this chapter the effects of varying the distribution of SST on the transient wave statistics will be examined. The wavenumber-frequency characteristics of four aqua-planet experiments will be studied to compare how the power and dispersion properties change in response to these different forcings. Two confined SST anomaly experiments will be studied, 3KEQ and 6KEQ along with experiment 3KW1 and the axisymmetric flat experiment.

The spectra of the full component of the precipitation field for these four experiments are shown in Fig. 6.13. In particular, the nature of the forcing is revealed in the stationary, i.e. zero frequency, part of the spectrum. For the confined anomaly experiments the stationary precipitation forcing is the strongest in the domain and is made up of a superposition of Fourier components. This is shown by the strong power at zero frequency between wavenumber 1 and 12 with a peak at wavenumber 2 which is equal for eastward and westward waves. This signal is stronger in the 6K confined SST anomaly case as the amplitude of the contrast between the precipitation maxima and the regions of suppression, as seen in the mean, is obviously stronger. In experiment 3KW1 the stationary forcing is represented with fewer wavenumbers, just wavenumber 1 to 5, and the peak power is now found at a wavenumber coinciding with the zonal scale of the SST forcing. The flat experiment is like

Figure 6.13: Raw 2-D frequency-wavenumber Fourier analysis of the full component of precipitation for experiment: (a) 3KEQ; (b) 6KEQ; (c) 3KW1; (d) axisymmetric flat (in mm day^{-1}).

the control experiment in that there is no stationary forcing from the SST beyond the zonal mean, but that is removed prior to the analysis and so there is no signal in the spectrum at zero frequency. The full spectra of the control experiment (Fig. 6.11(a)) shows comparatively close agreement with the full spectra of the confined anomaly experiments, and to a certain extent experiment 3KW1. However, it is obvious that the flat experiment spectrum differs considerably from the control experiments. This is demonstrated more clearly in the derived background spectra shown in Fig. 6.14. The background spectra of the three SST anomaly experiments are very similar and the control experiment background spectra could provide a good approximation of the non-periodic random disturbances in these experiments also. For completeness though the different individual background spectra were used in each experiment. The control background spectra would be unsuitable to represent the non-periodic process in the flat experiment. In particular, it would severely overestimate the power in the eastward waves of the spectrum.

Figure 6.15: Symmetric frequency-wavenumber Fourier analysis of precipitation after division by the background spectra for experiment: (a) 3KEQ; (b) 6KEQ; (c) 3KW1; (d) axisymmetric flat (in mm day^{-1}).

control symmetric spectra there did not seem to be a large contribution of wave activity from gravity waves, it appears that the confined anomaly experiments are able to excite stronger gravity waves at frequencies greater than about 12 cycles/month. This is particularly the case for the 6K confined anomaly experiment. In general the whole spectrum of the two confined anomaly experiment seems much less distinct and noisy in both wavenumber and frequency than the control. At lower frequencies and higher wavenumbers this effect seems to be more noticeable.

Moving onto experiment 3KW1 we can see that the spreading of power to a wider range of frequencies and wavenumbers weakens the spectral power peaks especially in the westward Rossby wave region. The Kelvin waves show a spreading of power to give a larger range of equivalent depths for the convective events. The reason for this possibly lies in the fact that the SST varies all the way along the equator unlike the control or confined anomaly experiments. Convection may then lock to different equivalent depths and travel at different speeds depending on the magnitude of the underlying SST. The suggestion is that convection both moves to deeper equivalent depths and increases its phase speed. This is consistent

with dryer, faster Kelvin waves in the region of coolest SSTs along the equator where precipitation is less intense and the eastward waves move with a faster phase speed.

Finally, as expected, the spectrum for the flat experiment is fundamentally different from any of the other experiments. The major difference is the complete absence of virtually any Kelvin wave activity, particularly at the lowest frequency and wavenumber. The only significant peak, although it does not show up very well in Fig. 6.15(c), is a very low frequency disturbance of 0.3 cycles/month at wavenumber one. Analysis of the transient precipitation activity in Fig. 6.3 shows this slowly varying disturbance, particularly, in the third four month period of the time series. Slightly elevated precipitation values of 8-12 mm day⁻¹ propagate once around the globe in the four month period. The peaks in the westward propagating Rossby wave envelope correspond to deeper equivalent depths and, therefore, higher phase speeds than in any of other aqua-planet experiments. Again this may be due to the weaker convection coupling such that the Rossby waves propagate closer to the faster 'dry' phase speed.

The problem of dispersion of power to a larger range of wavenumbers is not so evident in this case as it seems in the anomaly experiments. It may, therefore, be the case that breaking the zonal uniformity with forcing from an SST anomaly generates a response in the convectively coupled waves which is spread over a larger range of equivalent depths compared to purely axisymmetric forcing.

6.6.2 Antisymmetric Spectra

As with the control experiment the spectra for the antisymmetric waves exhibit much less noise (Fig. 6.16). The spectra in the confined anomaly experiments do not differ significantly from the control, except possibly for a more localised region of power in the mixed Rossby-gravity wave envelope at wavenumber 7 to 8 and a frequency of 6 cycles/month. The spectrum for experiment 3KW1 shows, as with the symmetric spectrum, considerably reduced power in the westward propagating waves. There is also a suggestion that the spatial extent of these disturbances have moved to larger wavenumbers and, therefore, smaller spatial scales.

The difference between the antisymmetric spectrum for the flat case and other experiments is

Figure 6.16: Antisymmetric frequency-wavenumber Fourier analysis of precipitation after division by the background spectra for experiment (a) 3KEQ; (b) 6KEQ; (c) 3KW1; (d) axisymmetric flat (in mm day^{-1}).

much less marked than for the symmetric spectrum. Mid-latitude systems in this experiment impinge into the tropical region more readily than in the control experiment due both to the higher baroclinicity and the warm SSTs extending into the sub-tropics, which helps trigger convection in the trailing cold front regions. Power in the $n=0$ eastward gravity waves is reduced compared to the control experiment.

In all the experiments there is significant power in westward disturbances of the antisymmetric wave spectra at frequencies of 6 to 9 cycles/month and wavenumbers greater than 9. These waves can be distinguished from Rossby-gravity waves and are not associated with any other theoretical equatorially trapped free waves. The origin of these signals are tropical depression type disturbances and easterly waves which tend to occur off the equator in each hemisphere. The peaks in the model spectra may be the models representation of hurricane type disturbances, although of course there is insufficient resolution to represent real hurricanes.

6.7 Conclusions

The transient activity in integrations of the aqua-planet has been shown to be involved in much of the organisation of tropical convection in the model. In experiments with a confined SST anomaly the mean precipitation signal dominates in the SST anomaly region, whereas for more slowly varying wavenumber one SST anomalies the mean signal is difficult to detect and transient organisation tends to dominate at any particular time. For the time scales under consideration the MJO is the dominant transient organiser of convection in observations, whereas in the aqua-planet this feature is absent and the dominant precipitation organisation is provided by the convectively coupled Kelvin wave of zonal wavenumber 4 to 5, and a frequency of 4 to 5 cycles/month. In the control experiment and the anomaly experiments away from the anomaly region, the westerly phase of this dominant Kelvin wave is broadly associated with an enhancement of the local precipitation, and the easterly phase with a local suppression. However, this relationship appears to change near the longitude of the SST anomaly with suppression events being more closely associated with upper-level westerly anomalies.

A frequency-wavenumber analysis performed on the aqua-planet experiments reveals that characteristics of many of the observed transient features of the real atmosphere, such as the speed of Kelvin and Rossby waves, are well represented in the model. Even in the absence of an antisymmetric tropical forcing mechanism antisymmetric convectively coupled waves are shown to make up a large component of the convective organisation. Organisation on these time and space scales is made possible through the influence of mid-latitude systems on the tropics.

Changes in the gross characteristics of the transient activity occur with the inclusion of an anomaly in the SST field, generating zonal non-uniformity. In particular, the spread of phase speeds associated with an individual disturbance, as identified by the theoretical dispersion curves, increases slightly in the confined anomaly experiments and significantly in experiment 3KW1. These changes manifest themselves as a much noisier and dilute wavenumber-frequency spectrum. It is postulated that these differences result as a consequence of convectively coupled waves travelling at a different speed and locking to a different equivalent depth, depending on the magnitude of the underlying SST. Therefore, since these waves are zonally propagating it follows that there will be a greater spread of phase speeds

for any particular class of wave in the anomaly experiments, with the greatest spread when the zonal SST continually varies as in experiment 3KW1.

Ideally, to gain greater significance and to have more confidence in our results, the length of the experiments should be extended so that the wavenumber-frequency analysis can be performed over a longer period as possible, thus eliminating more of the noise. However, one years analysis provides a useful summary of how similar the spectra are to that observed in the real atmosphere, and the sensitivity of the transient characteristics to changes in the tropical SST forcing. In fact it is vital to understand how the transient activity responds to changes in the SST forcing if we are to gain a greater insight into what goes into making up the time-mean response of the UM.

Chapter 7

Comparison with Simplified Atmospheric Models

7.1 Introduction

Two broad ranging questions arise from analyses of the UM aqua-planet experiments so far. Firstly, given the response to the SST forcing, what are the essential processes that need to be represented in order to capture the gross response seen in the UM? Secondly, is the response we see in the model actually correct, in that if the real atmosphere was forced with the SST distributions being used here, would we see the same response as in the UM?

On the first question, it is possible to compare the results of the aqua-planet with a range of simplified models, as summarised in Chapter 2. In their design these models make use of certain simplifying tropical approximations and the dominance of particular dynamical processes assumed to act. One such model is used here with boundary forcing provided by the aqua-planet SST distributions and analysed to see if the aqua-planet response is reproduced.

The question of whether the model gives the correct response is more difficult to answer. Usually the procedure is to compare model results with the correct solution, namely observations. However, in this case there are no observations to compare with as the observed SST never resembles any of the SST distributions used here. Therefore, it is only possible

to investigate whether the model results are robust, i.e. given the same forcing as the UM would a GCM with a similar setup and complexity give the same answer. More generally would the results be robust across a number of independently developed GCMs of equal complexity and with a range of different numerical and parameterization schemes.

To go some way towards assessing the robustness of the results we repeat the aqua-planet experiment in an intermediate atmospheric GCM. The model is specifically chosen because of the fundamentally different way in which it deals with convective processes. In this way it is possible to assess which components of the response are robust between the two models and which are model dependent.

7.2 Single Layer Boundary Layer Model

The model used to assess the dominant mechanisms involved in the response to the SST distribution is the single layer boundary layer model of Lindzen and Nigam (1987), hereafter denoted LN, which was described briefly in Chapter 2. This model in particular was chosen as it relates the distribution of SST, through the depth averaged pressure field in response to horizontal temperature gradients, to the boundary layer depth averaged flow. The model is also desirable as it can be forced by SST distributions in exactly the same way as the UM, rather than specifying a vertical distribution of diabatic heating, as is often the case with many other simple tropical models.

7.2.1 Model and Experiment Formulation

The main assumption made in this simple model concerns the boundary layer temperature and how it relates to the SST. In particular the atmosphere is assumed to be in equilibrium with the SST. Taking just the zonal anomaly or 'eddy' surface temperature field, this is assumed to decay with height, along with an adiabatic decrease of the zonal mean temperature, such that the eddy temperature at the top of the boundary layer (≈ 700 mb) falls to about 70% of its surface value. The dependence of the boundary layer temperature distribution on surface temperature is therefore determined from Eqn. 2.35. We can test how good an approximation this is by examining the temperature distribution at the top of

Figure 7.1: Eddy temperature distribution for experiment 3KW1 (in K) for (a) SST; (b) 750 mb temperature.

the boundary layer in the UM aqua-planet experiments. Fig. 7.1 shows the eddy SST and the eddy temperature field near the top of the boundary layer at 750 mb for experiment 3KW1.

In the tropics between 20° north and south the general pattern of the eddy SST is communicated up to 750 mb, especially in the region of negative eddy temperature where the magnitude reaches -2.2 K thus retaining 73% of the surface value. At the specified boundary layer top of 700 mb the retained eddy temperature magnitude is therefore between 65% and 70% and is consistent with the assumed temperature distribution in LN. However, the approximation is not ideal everywhere. In particular near the region of the convective maximum there is structure which is not present in the eddy SST. A local minimum in eddy temperature is found along the equator in this region, with maxima at about 12° north and 12° south, which are actually higher than the eddy SST in the same location. Poleward of 20° north and south the atmospheric response generates eddy temperature features not seen in the eddy SST. However, this is in general outside our region of interest and due to processes not represented in the simple model of LN.

In LN the eddy temperature at 1000 mb is used to force the model and not the observed SST. In this study both these temperature fields are used to force the model to determine whether the response is consistent with forcing from the eddy SST or the 1000 mb eddy virtual temperature. One would expect the eddy SST and the eddy 1000 mb temperature to be very similar, but this is not always the case in some tropical regions of the aqua-planet. The differences between these two fields are discussed in Section 7.2.2.

Two different versions of the model are used, one with the depth of the boundary layer fixed

at 3 km (about 700 mb), and a second where the depth of the boundary layer is allowed to vary and adjust to the boundary layer flow. By fixing the depth of the boundary layer the depth averaged flow can be solved analytically using Eqns. 2.39 and 2.40. However, when the boundary layer depth is allowed to vary the flow solutions have to be found numerically. The details of the methods used to solve the equations of motion are given in the appendix to this chapter. High SSTs give rise to high humidity in the tropical boundary layer which can have an impact on the strength of the boundary layer flow response. In the simple model these effects are included in a gross sense by using the virtual surface temperature as approximated from the absolute humidity field, q , using:

$$T_{VS} = T_S \left(1 + \frac{0.61q}{1-q} \right). \quad (7.1)$$

The set of experiments performed with each aqua-planet surface temperature distribution follow the standard experiments of LN. Specifically the linear drag coefficient, ϵ , is kept at a value of 2.5 days^{-1} representing the net effects of the surface drag on the whole of the boundary layer flow, and the cumulus adjustment time scale, τ_c , is kept at 30 minutes.

7.2.2 SST or Near Surface Temperature Forcing?

In observations the underlying SST is, in general, closely balanced with the near surface temperature on time scales of the order of a few days. However, this is not necessarily the case with the UM aqua-planet as the SST is fixed and does not respond to fluxes from the atmosphere. Significant differences between the SST and the temperature of the lowest atmospheric level are seen in the aqua-planet, particular where strong convection is present. Fig. 7.2(a) shows that the 1000 mb temperature distribution, with its wavenumber one structure and magnitude, is obviously that of experiment 3KW1, but there are significant departures when compared with the pattern of SST (Fig. 7.2(b)). The reduction in temperature between the surface and 1000 mb is so strong on the equator between about 0° and 90°E , that the meridional temperature gradient is actually reversed between 5° north and south in this region. The implications for the boundary layer flow response to this temperature distribution are significant as we will see later.

In light of these significant differences between the SST and 1000 mb temperature field both

Figure 7.2: (a) 1000 mb temperature field (in $^{\circ}\text{C}$); and (b) difference between SST and 1000 mb temperature (in K), for experiment 3KW1.

will be used to force the boundary layer model in order to determine what proportion of the flow can be attributed to the surface temperature forcing, and whether the response is consistent with forcing from SST or the 1000 mb temperature field. Therefore, errors will occur in this simple model associated with the assumption that the 1000 mb temperature is in equilibrium with the SST, which is clearly not the case for the UM aqua-planet

7.2.3 Equatorial Confined Anomaly Experiments

The simplest and easiest to understand boundary layer model experiments consist of the analytical solution, i.e. fixed boundary layer depth forced with the eddy SST distribution. Since the model is linear the pattern of response for experiment 6KEQ is the same as for experiment 1KEQ, but with six times the magnitude. However, this linearity in the response to the eddy SST is not reproduced in the actual boundary layer eddy flow in the aqua-planet experiments.

Fig. 7.3 shows the solution for the eddy boundary layer zonal wind, U' , for experiment 3KEQ from the simple model alongside the computed UM boundary layer depth averaged flow for all three equatorial confined anomaly experiments. We can see that the response to the SST forcing in the boundary layer model is essentially geostrophic to within a few degrees of the equator, with the zonal flow parallel to the meridional eddy temperature gradient induced pressure gradient force. On and close to the equator the balance is between the zonal temperature induced pressure gradient force and frictional forces, giving a zonal convergence centred exactly on the SST anomaly maximum. As the height of the boundary layer is not allowed to vary the response is confined purely to the region of eddy SST and

Figure 7.3: (a) Boundary layer eddy zonal wind (U') for experiment 3KEQ; (b) UM aqua-planet computed boundary layer mean flow for experiment 3KEQ; (c) as (b) but for experiment 1KEQ; (d) as (b) but for experiment 6KEQ (all in ms^{-1}).

so does not extend further poleward than 15°N and 15°S .

Comparing the solution from the simple model experiment 3KEQ (Fig.7.3(a)) with the computed boundary layer flow from the UM for this experiment (Fig.7.3(b)) reveals both significant similarities and differences. The position and strength of the westerly inflow core is reproduced well, but there is a significant region of strong easterly inflow in excess of 9 ms^{-1} which is completely absent in the UM. In addition there are features in the subtropics, and away from the SST anomaly region which are not seen at all in the boundary layer model. The response of the meridional wind field (not shown), although in the correct region with equatorward flow just to the west of the SST anomaly maximum, is too strong in the boundary layer by a factor of nearly four and also too confined to the equator. These strong near equator meridional winds generate boundary layer convergence which is an order of magnitude greater than that observed in the UM.

Comparison with experiment 1KEQ and 6KEQ shows that the UM does not respond to different magnitudes of forcing in a linear fashion. Focussing on U' (Fig. 7.3(b),(c) and

(d)) we can see that there is an element of linearity in the response to experiment 1KEQ and 3KEQ with a maximum westerly inflow anomaly in the former of about one third the magnitude of the equivalent region of westerlies in experiment 3KEQ. However, with a 6K SST anomaly in experiment 6KEQ the westerly flow maximum increases by only 1 ms^{-1} compared to experiment 3KEQ. There is a more substantial increase in the eddy boundary layer meridional wind, V' , and divergence, D' , in experiment 6KEQ but it does not amount to a doubling of the magnitudes in experiment 3KEQ. Therefore, it appears that the strength of the response, particularly for the largest SST anomaly forcing, is overestimated in the boundary layer model. The nature of the fixed boundary layer depth version of the model does not allow for the redistribution of mass in the boundary layer which, in reality, would weaken the pressure gradients and the associated flow response. The excessive response in this version of the boundary layer model is in agreement with LN.

Still using the eddy SST forcing but now allowing for the adjustment of the boundary layer height to convergence with a time scale, τ_c , of 30 minutes the response changes markedly, particularly in its magnitude. These marked changes result in response to minimal perturbations in the depth of the boundary layer, h' . For example, in experiment 3KEQ the largest depth perturbations are no greater than 10 m, demonstrating the high sensitivity of the equatorial flow to very small changes in the boundary layer height and, therefore, pressure distributions. The variation of boundary layer depth also allows non-zero amplitudes in the solution to extend into regions of zero eddy SST forcing, beyond 15° north and south in the confined anomaly experiments.

With forcing provided by 1000 mb eddy temperature there is considerably more structure to the solution, particularly away from the SST anomaly region, as one would expect given the structure in the 1000 mb temperature field. Using a fixed boundary layer depth (Fig. 7.4(a)) U' has slightly better structure than the same model setup but forced by SST, with westerly inflow to the SST anomaly occupying a greater area and a reduction in the equatorial easterly inflow not seen in the UM. Easterlies on and near the equator have also been generated from 30°E to 60°E , and from 120°O to 180°W in agreement with the observed U' from the UM (Fig.7.3(b)). To the east and polewards of the SST anomaly centre the pattern of zonal wind looks more like that observed in the UM, but it is much too confined near the equator, barely extending poleward of 15° . There is considerably more success in reproducing the V' (not shown) field with the strength and position of the

main meridional inflow matching closely with the UM. However, this is slightly deceiving as the distribution of convergence given by the flow is still much too tightly confined to the equator and too intense.

When the boundary layer depth is allowed to vary (Fig. 7.4(b)) similar changes in the characteristics of the flow occur as were observed using the eddy SST forcing. The magnitude of U' is much reduced everywhere, but the distribution is much better particularly as there is minimal easterly inflow along the equator towards the SST anomaly consistent with the UM. In addition, the varying boundary layer depth allows the off equator response near the SST anomaly to move further poleward and cover a region more closely matched with U' in the UM. The magnitude of V' and D' also suffers in this model setup, but the distribution of D' in particular is much improved.

With a variable boundary layer height V' and D' are reduced by an order of magnitude compared to the fixed height case, whereas U' is only reduced to one third of its original magnitude. This shows the dominance of the meridional convergence in determining the strength and location of the low-level convergence, which is consistent with results from the UM aqua-planet where the pattern of enhanced upper-tropospheric divergence and lower-tropospheric convergence in the SST anomaly region was shown to be dominated by an enhanced local Hadley circulation. In terms of linearity of the solution, in the UM aqua-planet experiment 6KEQ the enhanced low-level convergence compared to experiment 3KEQ is provided predominantly by intensification of V' and thus mostly enhances meridional convergence. However, the boundary layer model predicts that the increase in low-level convergence would be distributed equally between zonal and meridional convergence for an increase in forcing, indicating a non-linear response in the UM.

The spatial distribution of the boundary layer flow is better represented when allowing the boundary layer depth to vary. Westerly inflow into the anomaly region extends over a greater region to the west of the SST anomaly maximum which is an improvement on the previous model setup, but it still does not capture the double structure to the westerlies in the UM with a central strong core on the equator and a weaker region surrounding this.

It is obvious that certain features of the flow seen in the UM are reproduced by the boundary layer model in response to the SST and so can be seen as a direct response to temperature induced pressure gradients. However, there are features in the UM flow which cannot be

Figure 7.4: Simulated boundary layer eddy zonal wind, U' , forced with 1000 mb eddy virtual temperature for experiment 3KEQ; (a) boundary layer depth fixed; (b) boundary layer depth allowed to vary with a time scale, τ_c of 30 minutes.

reproduced in response to SST.

Briefly summarising this small set of experiments, it appears that the two different LN model setups individually provide desirable characteristics of the flow needed to reproduce the equivalent fields in the UM. By holding the boundary layer depth fixed it provides the strength of the flow seen in the UM. This is much too strong when eddy SST forcing is used and slightly too strong with 1000 mb eddy virtual temperature forcing. Allowing variation of the boundary layer depth gives a much better representation of the spatial variation of the fields as seen in the UM, but magnitudes are much too small. It appears that a much better representation of the UM flow could be achieved by retaining the variable nature of the boundary layer depth for the spatial variation, but decreasing the adjustment time scale to improve flow magnitudes.

On reducing τ_c to 15 minutes the distribution of the flow is not changed dramatically, and the magnitudes only increase by some 30-40%, which is still well below the observed UM fields. It turns out that to obtain the most accurate representation of the UM boundary layer flow a value for τ_c of just 1 minute appears to be the most suitable. U' for this case is not significantly different from the fixed boundary layer solution of U' which seems to be the best representation with 1000 mb eddy temperature forcing. However, both V' and D' are greatly improved with this value of τ_c , as shown in Fig. 7.5. The tropical portion of V' is reproduced with maxima of 2 ms^{-1} at 85°E and 5° north and south. In the UM the V' field extends out eastward and polewards into the sub-tropics, but the boundary layer model becomes less applicable in these regions and does not reproduce V' very well. Similarly the convergence maxima D' is reproduced with about the correct magnitude, and

Figure 7.5: Comparison of UM boundary layer parameters (V' , D') with simulated solutions from the boundary layer model for experiment 3KEQ; (a) V' from the UM; (b) D' from the UM; (c) V' from the boundary layer model, (d) D' from the boundary layer model. The boundary layer model is forced with the 1000 mb eddy virtual temperature field, and uses a relaxation time scale of 1 minute for perturbations to the boundary layer depth.

covering the same area just to the west of the SST anomaly maximum. It is particularly important to represent this area of boundary layer convergence as it gives the location of the mass supply for the convective maxima region.

The greater sensitivity of both V' and D' to the time scale τ_c contrasts with the much lower sensitivity of U' . Therefore, the meridional flow appears more dominant in determining the lower-tropospheric convergent flow for different values of τ_c . In a similar way the lower-tropospheric convergence in the UM is more sensitive to changes in the meridional flow, but this is of course due to the greater sensitivity to the meridional SST gradients associated with an imposed SST anomaly.

7.2.4 Off Equatorial Confined Anomaly Experiments

Using the boundary layer model with off equator SST anomalies, and in particular experiment 3K10S, gives a much better representation of the UM boundary layer flow than for the confined anomaly experiments, especially when forced with the 1000 mb eddy temperature field. The main reason for this is that the SST communicates to the the lower-troposphere much more effectively than in the equatorial confined anomaly experiments. Communication of SST was poorest on the equator where there was a convective maximum, but with off equator confined anomalies convection is reduced due to the cooler absolute SST maximum, and its position moves away from the sensitive equator region. Differences between the eddy SST and 1000 mb eddy virtual temperature are thus reduced considerably compared with the confined anomaly experiments, particularly in the region of the SST anomaly maximum. In experiment 3KEQ the eddy temperature maximum decreases from 2.7 K for the SST to just 1.2 K for the 1000 mb temperature, whereas for experiment 3K10S the maximum only decreases to 2.0K.

As with the confined anomaly experiments the best solution for U' is found with 1000 mb eddy virtual temperature forcing with a fixed boundary layer, or variable boundary layer with a small value for τ_c . Fig. 7.6 compares the UM U' field with the solution from the fixed depth version of the boundary layer model. In the vicinity of the SST anomaly the region of westerly inflow is reproduced very well, although it is slightly too weak, and the region of easterlies between 10°S and 20°S matches with the equatorward edge of the easterlies in the UM. Perhaps the most encouraging result is the accurate reproduction of the zonal wind field away from the SST anomaly region. Although the magnitudes are not as large as in the UM, the spatial distribution is in very good agreement.

Of particular note in the off equator SST anomaly experiments are the intense northerlies that are generated when the boundary layer model is forced with the eddy SST. Magnitudes reach in excess of five times those observed in the UM. In reality the atmosphere cannot sustain such large meridional temperature gradients near the equator as specified in experiment 3KEQ. This is due to the small value of the Coriolis parameter which tends to balance the pressure gradient terms away from the equator (cf. Eqn. 2.36) but is less able to do so within close proximity to the equator. When the boundary layer depth is allowed to vary this effect is much reduced as the eddy SST induced pressure gradient terms can

Figure 7.6: Comparison of UM boundary layer U' (in ms^{-1}) with solutions from the boundary layer model for experiment 3K10S; (a) observed U' from the UM; (b) boundary layer U' when forced with 1000 mb eddy virtual temperature, and using a fixed boundary layer depth.

now be balanced more effectively by forcing from terms which result from the variations in boundary layer perturbation depth h' . In effect this forcing redistributes mass in the boundary layer near the equator, thus reducing pressure gradients. In moving the centre of the SST anomaly just 10° south compared to experiment 3KEQ, the problem of equatorial zonal easterly inflow to the SST anomaly, which is not seen in the UM, is almost completely removed in this case. This is probably because the easterly inflow was a response due to the balance between zonal pressure gradients and frictional forces near the equator where the coriolis force is relatively small or zero. However, in experiment 3K10S the strongest zonal SST gradients, and therefore pressure gradients, have moved off the equator where the balance becomes more geostrophic and westerly inflow dominates just south of the equator.

7.2.5 Wavenumber One Experiments

We now move to analysing the response of the boundary layer model to the wavenumber one SST distributions. Compared with results from the confined anomaly experiments one would expect, a priori, that the boundary layer model would produce a better representation of the UM flow. The reason for this is the more smoothly varying SST field with a lower intensity of precipitation and, therefore, lower- tropospheric convergence. Thus, this would be more a kin to the real tropical situation which, in LN, gave a much better representation of the flow when used to force the boundary layer model.

The UM U' and V' for experiment 3KW1 (Fig. 7.7(a) and (b)) shows significant zonal and meridional flow occupying the whole tropics. In comparison with the confined anomaly

Figure 7.7: UM boundary layer flow for experiment 3KW1 (in ms^{-1}); (a) U' ; (b) V' , and comparison with the equivalent boundary layer model solutions forced by 1000 mb virtual temperature with a fixed boundary layer depth; (c) U' ; (d) V' .

experiments there is westerly eddy inflow occupying a more extensive region from 60°W to 120°E . There is now also easterly inflow which was always present in the boundary layer model solution with the confined anomaly experiments, but never seen in the actual UM U' field.

When forced with eddy SST the boundary layer model gives a reasonable distribution of near equator zonal wind, although surprisingly the magnitudes are less than observed in the UM, reaching only one third the speed. Unlike the confined anomaly experiments including the variation of the boundary layer depth with SST forcing does not significantly improve the spatial distribution of zonal wind. It appears, therefore, that the zonal winds on the equator organise on a shorter latitudinal scale than the SST field, and so better reproducibility of the flow is obtained in the absence of boundary layer variability. Poleward of 10° north and south the zonal flow solutions in particular are very inaccurate when compared to the UM. This is not surprising since in this experiment mid-latitude synoptic systems have a significant influence in the sub-tropics. This obviously involves processes not represented

in the boundary layer model.

Subject to forcing from the 1000 mb virtual temperature the model reproduces the U' field between 7.5° north and south with some success (Fig. 7.7(c)). One area of disagreement with the UM is on, and just to the east of, the eddy SST maximum where the boundary layer model predicts weak westerlies, but here the strongest westerlies in the tropics are observed in the UM reaching 6.5 ms^{-1} . However, this is a region where trailing cold fronts from mid-latitude systems can penetrate, triggering convection, seemingly with the consequence of accelerating the equatorial zonal flow. In contrast to U' the eddy meridional flow, V' , and eddy divergence, D' , are drastically in error using the fixed boundary layer height configuration. Fig. 7.7(d) shows that in close proximity to the equator the prevailing direction of V' is poleward. This is completely the wrong sign, and gives divergence in a region which sees the largest low-level convergence below the region of strongest convection. It turns out that the error is due to the very poor communication of SST to the lower-troposphere in the main convective region, which is sufficient in the slowly varying SST field of the wavenumber one experiments to reverse the gradient of 1000 mb temperature between the equator and sub-tropics, as was shown in Fig. 7.2.

Including the variation in the depth of the boundary layer effectively smoothes out the reversal in meridional temperature gradient. This gives a more accurate distribution of V' and D' , and of the correct sign, but with reduced magnitudes when a 30 minute boundary layer adjustment time scale is used. Therefore, it is even more vital in the wavenumber one experiments to include a varying boundary layer depth if one wishes to reproduce even the gross characteristics of the flow.

7.2.6 Discussion

Using the model of LN to reproduce the boundary layer climate of the UM experiments clearly reveals the complexity of the response, which includes interactions and processes not represented in the boundary layer model. On the question of whether the UM atmosphere responds more strongly to the SST or the 1000 mb temperature field it appears it may be a combination of both. The strength of the gradients in SST are certainly reflected in the atmospheric response, especially on the equator near the main convective regions where the zonal momentum balance is between the pressure gradient and frictional terms. Forcing

from the 1000 mb virtual temperature field provides much more of the structure seen in the UM experiments and so would be preferable to using the SST, particularly in light of the fixed nature of the SST. The exact nature of the response is also crucial when considering that ocean models are frequently driven by wind stresses derived from a model such as that of LN.

In all the experiments performed with the boundary layer model, V' and D' were found to be very sensitive to how the boundary layer depth was specified. With a fixed boundary layer depth V' and D' were much too confined near the equator with overly strong magnitudes. When the boundary layer depth was allowed to interactively vary in response to D' with a time scale of 30 minutes, the spatial distribution was, in general, much improved but the magnitudes suffered as a consequence. Sensitivity tests for the confined anomaly experiments reveal that the the best representation of the UM flow resulted when the boundary layer model was forced with the 1000 mb virtual temperature, and the relaxation time scale of the boundary layer depth was reduced to just one minute.

Such a large difference between the relaxation time scale for convection, when trying to reproduce the observed boundary layer flow, and the UM aqua-planet boundary layer flow implies that the climate of the aqua-planet is indeed significantly different from the observed climate. Assumptions in the boundary layer model are clearly not well suited to accurately reproducing the aqua-planet flow. The reason for this may be the fixed nature of the SST or the intense and persistent nature of the convection which makes it much more difficult to define a boundary layer depth, as mass is continually being vented into the free troposphere by the convection. However, in regions away from the SST anomalies convection is not continuous and less intense, thus giving a better defined boundary layer depth allowing for better representation of the boundary layer flow. This was certainly the case in experiment 3K10S and to a certain extent is consistent with arguments giving in Battisti *et al.* (1999) suggesting different time scales for relaxation of the boundary layer depth in convecting and non-convecting conditions, since this relaxation will be governed by different processes depending on the presence or absence of convection.

The scale of the SST anomaly used can also prove important in the extent of coupling between the SST and the boundary layer pressure gradients as was shown in Allen and Davey (1993). For SST anomalies of zonal wavenumbers greater than 6 the coupling to the

boundary layer pressure gradients effectively tends to zero. The greatest coupling was seen for wavenumber one SST anomalies which agrees with our experiments, whereby experiment 3KW1 saw the best overall reproduction of the UM boundary layer flow. The confined anomaly experiments which correspond to a zonal wavenumber 3 forcing, gave poorer flow solutions in the SST anomaly region in agreement with the poorer coupling observed in Allen and Davey (1993) for smaller scale disturbances.

Finally the assumption of linearity has to be questioned with the aqua-planet experiments since the lower-tropospheric flow in response to the zonal mean SST distribution is significant. Further experiments performed with U' linearised about the zonally averaged observed UM flow gave an improvement in the spatial distribution of the off-equator boundary layer flow, which is where the largest errors in U' were previously seen.

7.3 Quasi-Equilibrium Tropical Circulation Model

7.3.1 Model and Experiment Formulation

In order to determine the robustness of the results from the UM aqua-planet the same experiments have been repeated, but using a completely different atmospheric model. This allows a direct comparison to be made between the dynamics and physics of the models in response to identical simplified forcings. Such experiments facilitate the test bed methodology identified earlier in the thesis providing an intermediate test of parameterizations that lies between a full complex GCM and simpler models, such as single column and cloud resolving models.

The model used for comparison was chosen specifically because the convective parameterization differs significantly from the scheme in the UM. The Quasi-Equilibrium Tropical Circulation Model (QTCM) (Neelin, 1997, Neelin and Zeng, 1999, Zeng *et al.*, 1999) is an intermediate level atmospheric model that assumes the atmosphere is in a state of *quasi-equilibrium*. This means that changes in energy at the large-scales are approximately balanced by changes associated with small-scale convective activity. Vertical profiles of temperature are therefore defined by a reference profile such that the model restores departures in temperature back to this reference profile. Effectively the large-scale flow is

constrained by the convection. The model uses a version of the Betts and Miller (Betts, 1986) convection scheme where the effect of an ensemble of convective clouds is to reduce a certain measure of CAPE and constrain the large-scale temperature profile. This constrained temperature profile is used to construct analytical solutions for the large scale flow in deep convecting regions. The model is then constructed by using these analytical solutions as so-called *tailored basis functions* designed to retain vertical structures associated with the dominant physics of interest. This so-called Galerkin like representation is used to represent the vertical structure in the model as opposed to the conventional approach of splitting the vertical into a number of discrete levels. The total fields can be reconstructed at any vertical level as:

$$T = T_r(p) + a_1(p)T_1(x, y, t) \quad (7.2)$$

$$q = q_r(p) + b_1(p)q_1(x, y, t) \quad (7.3)$$

$$\mathbf{v} = \mathbf{v}_0(p) + V_1(p)\mathbf{v}_1(x, y, t), \quad (7.4)$$

where T_r and q_r are the temperature and humidity reference profiles, and \mathbf{v}_0 and \mathbf{v}_1 are the barotropic and baroclinic components of the velocity.

Taking this approach provides a large reduction in the number of degrees of freedom, and in the version of the model used here only one baroclinic, and one barotropic mode is represented (Eqn. 7.4). The model equations retain spherical geometry and viscosity is added to the system to keep it stable. In addition to the convective parameterization the model contains intermediate long-wave and short-wave radiation schemes, surface flux calculations and a cloud prediction scheme parameterizing four different cloud types. The horizontal resolution is 5.75° in longitude and 3.75° in latitude extending between 60°N and 60°S . The assumption of quasi-equilibrium is generally valid throughout the tropics where there exists deep convection and the atmosphere is unstable throughout most of its depth. The model is also designed to give a reasonable representation of atmospheric dynamics up to one Rossby radius away from the tropics. Further poleward of this the QTCM becomes qualitatively similar to a two-level model with a single temperature level. Regions poleward of 60°N and S are not included and a sponge layer is implemented from 45°N to 60°N and 45°S to 60°S . This sponge layer reduces heat and moisture fluxes and increases momentum damping.

With a much simpler configuration than a full GCM the QTCM is able to run much faster but still reproduce many of the characteristics of tropical rainfall, including its seasonal evolution, when forced with monthly varying SSTs (Zeng *et al.*, 1999). Particular patterns simulated well include the extent and position of the main ENSO rainfall anomalies, the northward progression of the monsoon onset and the seasonal evolution of the tropical convergence zones. The suite of experiments performed with the UM aqua-planet have been repeated here using the QTCM. The final year of a three year integration is averaged and analysed for each experiment. Oceanic values of the initial albedo and cloud fields are zonally and annually averaged observed, so as to be suitable for use in an aqua-planet configuration.

7.3.2 Zonally Invariant SST Experiments

The zonal mean distribution of precipitation in the QTCM using the control, peaked and flat hemispherically symmetric SST profiles is shown in Fig. 7.8(a). Compared with the UM the QTCM appears to reproduce the relative distribution of precipitation well, with the peaked experiment giving the highest equatorial values and the flat experiment giving the lowest values. However, the equatorial maximum precipitation is only one third of the UM total in the control case and less than one quarter in the peaked case. The flat experiments are in much closer agreement between the two models with a value of just over 3 mm day^{-1} between 10°N and 10°S in both cases. Off-equatorial peaks seen in the UM at 16°N and S are not reproduced in the QTCM for the flat experiment. One would expect this result since these maxima in the UM were shown to be due to interactions with mid-latitude systems. Quasi-equilibrium does not hold well away from the tropics and thus leads to a poorer simulation of mid-latitude climate in the QTCM, especially since circulations are subject to a damping sponge region poleward of 45°N and S .

These results suggest that the QTCM is more consistent with the UM when the precipitation is predominantly a thermodynamic response to the local SST as is generally the case in the flat experiment where there is a weak large scale axisymmetric circulation. The zonal mean evaporation in the QTCM (Fig. 7.8(b)) supports this hypothesis. For the control and peaked experiments there is a maximum in evaporation on the equator which contradicts the UM results where there is a local minimum in evaporation on the equator (cf. Fig 3.9(a) and

Figure 7.8: QTCM forced with hemispherically symmetric SST distributions; (a) zonally averaged precipitation (mm day^{-1}) (solid line - control, dashed line - peaked, dotted line - flat), compare with UM Fig. 3.6; (b) as (a) but for evaporation (mm day^{-1}), compare with UM Fig. 3.9; (c) zonally averaged zonal wind from the QTCM control experiment (ms^{-1}), compare with UM Fig. 3.7(a); (d) as (c) but for meridional wind (ms^{-1}).

(b)). It would appear that in the UM the light winds and very moist near surface air inhibits evaporation much more than in the QTCM, therefore relying on a greater moisture supply from higher latitudes. In the QTCM there is a closer balance between local precipitation and evaporation.

The response in the zonal mean circulation is shown in Figs. 7.8(c) and (d) for the control experiment, but many of the general points also apply to the peaked and flat experiments. The zonally averaged zonal wind shows sub-tropical westerly jets of about the same magnitude as the UM experiment, peaking at 65-70 ms^{-1} at 200mb. However, they differ considerably in structure between the two-models. The jets are centred at about 15°N and 15°S which is some 10° further equatorward than in the UM. The jets are also more baroclinic since the surface zonal wind beneath the upper-tropospheric jet maxima are slight easterlies as opposed to westerlies of nearly 10 ms^{-1} in the UM. The most striking differences between two models are near the equator. In the QTCM upper-tropospheric winds are westerly in excess of 40 ms^{-1} and the vertical profile is strongly baroclinic suggesting a possible lack of angular momentum conservation. The zonally averaged zonal momentum equation for the barotropic and baroclinic components of the flow in the QTCM is given by:

$$\frac{\partial u_0}{\partial t} + \mathcal{D}_{v0}(u_0, u_1) - fv_0 = -\epsilon_0 u_0 - \epsilon_{10} u_1 \quad (7.5)$$

$$\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial t} + \mathcal{D}_{v1}(u_0, u_1) - fv_1 = -\epsilon_1 u_1 - \epsilon_{01} u_0. \quad (7.6)$$

where \mathcal{D}_{v0} and \mathcal{D}_{v1} are the advection-diffusion operators for the barotropic and baroclinic components respectively. Therefore, angular momentum conserving flow will be dependent on the parameterization of the stress terms in the equations, and more specifically on the values taken by ϵ_0 , ϵ_{01} , ϵ_1 and ϵ_{10} . The terms involving ϵ_0 and ϵ_1 act like a spin down on the barotropic and baroclinic components of the wind respectively. However, the terms involving ϵ_{01} and ϵ_{10} act as a transfer between the two components.

Although the model formulation assures that the vertical integral of the parameterized stress is correct, only retaining two modes does not allow for a very realistic vertical distribution of the stress contribution. The vertical profile of the baroclinic wind component is constrained to be consistent with the baroclinic pressure gradients implied from the imposed quasi-equilibrium temperature profile, but this vertical profile is far from ideal when projected

on to the stress terms. Therefore, instead of restricting the contribution of the stress terms to the boundary layer the projection allows significant contribution to the momentum equations throughout the depth of the troposphere. This appears not to allow angular momentum conservation in the tropics at least in terms of an individual air parcel ascending in the ITCZ and moving poleward in the upper-troposphere.

The absence of the same constraint on angular momentum conservation as in the UM may indicate why the precipitation in the control and peaked QTCM experiments is much less than in the UM. If not subject to angular momentum conservation then the Hadley circulation flow will not act to flatten the curvature of the atmospheric temperature gradient. This adjustment was, in the UM, responsible for the stronger precipitation particularly in the peaked experiment where the greatest overturning occurred in order to constrain the implied zonal thermal wind to be angular momentum conserving.

The zonally averaged meridional wind for the control experiment (Fig. 7.8(d)) reflects the weaker meridional circulation when compared with UM. There is an obvious Hadley circulation centred about the equator with lower-tropospheric inflow and upper-tropospheric outflow. However, the maximum velocity fails to reach 1 ms^{-1} , whereas in the UM the control experiment sees outflow velocities of around 6 ms^{-1} but in a more vertically confined region. The QTCM flat experiment has a pattern of zonally averaged meridional wind which is also indicative of a Hadley circulation but with a lower magnitude. Therefore, unlike the UM it appears that no strong regime transition occurs between the control and flat experiments when a Hadley circulation is no longer required as a consequence of angular momentum conservation constraints.

Since the tropical zonal wind was found to be much stronger throughout the depth than in the UM a sensitivity experiment was performed by reducing the value of the stress term coefficient, ϵ_{10} . This coefficient determines the time scale of momentum transfer from the baroclinic to the barotropic component of the flow. By reducing ϵ_{10} from 0.9 days^{-1} to 9 days^{-1} , changes to the zonal mean circulation sees the QTCM response to the control SST resemble more closely that seen in the UM (Fig. 7.9). In particular, the changes are confined mainly to the tropics. The precipitation is increased by up to 1.5 mm day^{-1} between 10°N and S, and reduced by up to 1 mm day^{-1} in the sub-tropics. Since the changes to the evaporation are minimal then the strengthening of the ITCZ is achieved

Figure 7.9: QTCM forced with the control SST distribution, but with drag coefficient ϵ_{10} decreased from (0.9 days^{-1}) to (9 days^{-1}) ; (a) zonally averaged precipitation (solid line) and difference from the standard QTCM control experiment (dashed line) (mm day^{-1}); (b) as (a) but for evaporation (mm day^{-1}); (c) zonally averaged zonal wind (ms^{-1}); (d) as (c) but for meridional wind (ms^{-1}).

more by enhancement of the mean meridional circulation. This is confirmed by a doubling of the strength of the meridional wind. The zonal wind is now easterly on the equator and has much more the appearance of the UM zonally averaged zonal wind with weak magnitudes in the tropical upper-troposphere, although they remain westerly. The subtropical westerly jets also move 5° further polewards giving greater agreement with the UM. Therefore, the sensitivity to the stress coefficients appears much more important when the QTCM is subject to the aqua-planet SST distributions and may have not been very obvious when subject to observed SST distributions in Zeng *et al.* (1999) where the near equatorial flow was much weaker.

The damped nature of mid-latitude processes in the QTCM also leads to greater sensitivity

when the UM hemispherically asymmetric experiments are repeated with this model. Fig. 7.10(a) shows the zonally averaged precipitation from the three hemispherically symmetric experiments as outlined for the UM in Section 3.6.2. When the insolation is fixed at perpetual summer solstice conditions as in the control-June 21st experiment the precipitation increases by about 10% compared to the QTCM control experiment and moves slightly into the summer northern hemisphere. Accompanying the changes in precipitation are an intensification of the southern winter hemisphere Hadley cell by about 50% with the strength of the northern summer cell remaining about the same. These changes are substantially greater than in the equivalent UM experiment demonstrating a greater sensitivity of the radiation scheme in the QTCM, particular in the long-wave cooling region of the descending branch of the southern winter Hadley cell. Therefore, the increase in precipitation in this experiment appears to be forced in response to enhanced sub-tropical descent.

The off-equatorial SST maximum control-5N and control-10N experiments lack the double maximum structure seen in the UM experiments. The maximum magnitude of precipitation increases when the SST maximum is moved off the equator, such that in the control-10N experiment there is a massive 50% increase in the zonally averaged precipitation, even though the SST magnitude remains the same. Such sensitivity is not observed in the UM which see a decrease in the maximum magnitude for the control-5N and control-10N experiments.

Therefore, it appears that the QTCM shows low sensitivity to near equatorial SST gradients, but when there exists significant cross-equatorial gradients in SST the response intensifies dramatically. This results in a precipitation maximum in the control-10N experiment which is actually higher than in the peaked experiment with its very strong unrealistic near-equatorial SST gradients. It appears that this dramatic response is again facilitated by a very much intensified southern winter Hadley circulation, with increased sub-tropical descent which leads to zero zonally averaged precipitation between 8°S and 30°S in the control-10N experiment. The massive intensification of the southern hemisphere cell is demonstrated by the enhancement of the meridional wind in the control-10N experiment (Fig. 7.10(b)). Magnitudes are some five times greater than in the control experiment. This compares to just a doubling in the strength of the southern winter Hadley cell between the equivalent UM experiments.

Figure 7.10: QTCM forced with hemispherically asymmetric SST distributions; (a) zonally averaged precipitation (mm day^{-1}) (solid line - control-5N, dashed line - control-10N, dotted line - control-June 21st), compare with UM Fig. 3.14; (b) difference in zonally averaged meridional wind between the control and control-10N experiments (in ms^{-1}).

Such large sensitivity is consistent with Lindzen and Hou (1988). However, the study of Lindzen and Hou (1988) relied on angular momentum conservation arguments to obtain the large sensitivity, and the QTCM precipitation totals and Hadley circulation strength are also still much weaker than in the UM. Therefore, it appears more likely that the sensitivity is due to the lack of influence of the mid-latitude circulation, which is considerably damped in the QTCM. In the UM the extra-tropical response to the SST gradient was able to sustain the strength of the northern summer Hadley cell, due to an increased eddy driven Ferrel cell, and to restrict the strength of the dominant southern winter Hadley cell.

7.3.3 Confined Anomaly and Wavenumber One Experiments

In the UM there is large sensitivity to the inclusion of both longitudinally confined anomalies and zonal wavenumber one anomalies. These anomaly experiments were repeated using the QTCM to examine whether the same sensitivity was present. Focussing on experiments 3KEQ and 3KW1, the distribution of precipitation (Fig 7.11(a) and (b)) appears similar to the UM, bearing in mind the fact that average magnitudes are much lower as was apparent in the QTCM zonally invariant experiments. The position of the maximum precipitation is much less affected by the low-level flow than in the UM and sits exactly over the SST maximum in both cases. In the UM the position of the maximum is strongly affected by the low-level flow, particularly in experiment 3KW1 where the maximum precipitation lies

some 30° west of the SST maximum. This again indicates that precipitation in the QTCM is very strongly tied to the magnitude of SST.

The most striking difference between the UM and the QTCM is the markedly different sensitivity between experiments 3KW1 and 3KEQ. The UM shows the greatest sensitivity to experiment 3KEQ where as demonstrated in the simple experiments of the boundary layer model of LN, the strong SST gradients lead to greatly enhanced boundary layer flow and low-level convergence. This sensitivity leads to a precipitation maximum of 53 mm day^{-1} in experiment 3KEQ, compared to nearly 30 mm day^{-1} in experiment 3KW1. In the QTCM this situation is reversed and the greatest precipitation maximum is seen in experiment 3KW1 reaching nearly 17 mm day^{-1} , almost twice the maximum value in experiment 3KEQ of 9 mm day^{-1} .

The QTCM does a good job of capturing the regions of remote precipitation suppression as shown by the precipitation anomalies from the control in Figs. 7.11(c) and (d). Suppression in the descent regions of the tropical confined Rossby wave is represented in experiment 3KEQ and reduces precipitation just polewards and westwards from the SST anomaly by about 50% compared with the control. However, the region of suppression in this experiment is much less latitudinally confined than in the UM and the region of greatest remote suppression in the QTCM centred on the equator at 100° W , is in a region of minimum suppression in the equivalent UM experiment. There is only weak suppression due to any Kelvin wave response to the east of the enhanced convection. Therefore, it appears that the QTCM can capture this suppressive response seen in the more complex UM but with much reduced magnitudes relative to the control precipitation totals.

In experiment 3KW1 the pattern of anomalies are less in agreement with the UM. Firstly, it is apparent that the zonal mean precipitation on and near the equator is higher than in the control, whereas in the UM the equatorial zonal average is found to be slightly reduced compared to the control with an increased zonal average further poleward. The position of the downstream equatorial precipitation minimum is co-located with the SST minimum, again emphasising the dominance of the thermodynamic response to the SST. As with experiment 3KEQ the suppression is not as latitudinally confined as in the UM and regions of negative precipitation anomaly exist centred around 25° N and 25° S at the same longitude of the convective maximum. Such a region of suppression is absent from the UM response

Figure 7.11: Precipitation (in mm day^{-1}) from the QTCM for (a) experiment 3KEQ, compare with UM Fig. 4.3(a); (b) experiment 3KW1, compare with UM Fig. 5.2(b); (c) experiment 3KEQ minus control zonal mean, compare with UM Fig. 4.3(a); (d) experiment 3KW1 minus control zonal mean, compare with UM Fig. 5.2(d). The contour interval is 1 mm day^{-1} for values below 6 mm day^{-1} and 2 mm day above this, with additional contours at -0.25 and -0.5 mm day^{-1} to identify negative anomaly regions. Shaded areas indicate regions of positive anomaly.

predominantly because the strong mean meridional circulation of the control generates very dry sub-tropical regions with near zero precipitation and any increase in this circulation seen in experiment 3KW1 makes little difference to the precipitation total in these regions. In the QTCM there is $1\text{-}2 \text{ mm day}^{-1}$ of precipitation in this region so any strengthening of the mean meridional circulation has a noticeable impact.

One advantage of the QTCM over the UM is the clarity and coherence of the dynamic response to the enhanced convection in all the anomaly experiments. In particular the equivalent barotropic structure of the Rossby wave response remote from the SST anomaly is apparent in the dominance of the barotropic component over the retained baroclinic component of the flow. The adjustment in the Hadley circulation to the localised increase in convective heating of experiment 3KEQ is apparent in the meridional wind at 200 mb

and 850 mb (Fig. 7.12(a) and (b)). At 200 mb the enhanced outflow from the increased convection occurs exactly over the maximum SST and associated with this is a strong equatorward return flow immediately to the east. This is indicative of upper-tropospheric anticyclones lying on and to the east of the heating. This agrees with the results from the UM for this experiment and inspection of the vorticity shows that as with the UM the QTCM produces a pool of zero absolute vorticity in the region of convective outflow to balance the vorticity budget. Remote from the SST anomaly region the 200 mb meridional wind indicates weak anomalous convergence on the equator. This is consistent with the remote precipitation suppression seen in Fig. 7.11(c). The 850 mb wind anomaly also points to a suppression of precipitation at every longitude away from the SST anomaly region with anomalous flow towards the equator representing lower-tropospheric divergence anomalies on the equator.

The response local to the heating anomaly at 850 mb is very interesting when compared with the experiments performed using the boundary layer model of LN in Section 7.2.3. Referring back to these simple model experiments we can see that the meridional wind from experiment 3KEQ using the QTCM is much closer to the solution obtained using the model of LN (Fig. 7.5(c)) than the UM (Fig. 7.5(a)). Therefore, this reminds us that the dynamics of the QTCM is still relatively simple retaining one baroclinic mode in a similar way to the boundary layer model of LN.

The reasons for the large differences in the distribution of precipitation in experiment 3KW1 become apparent when we examine the dynamical response to the heating. Changes to the 200 mb zonal wind (Fig. 7.12(c)) are dominated by the local response to the convective heating anomaly, with strong easterly anomalies in excess of 30 ms^{-1} centred over the anomaly and acceleration of the sub-tropical westerlies in response to the meridional convective outflow increase. There is virtually no change in the zonal wind remote from the convective anomaly. This is in complete contrast to the equivalent UM experiment where the upper-tropospheric response was dominated by the generation of strong equatorial westerlies in excess of 45 ms^{-1} . In the UM this resulted in the basic state zonally averaged upper-tropospheric weak easterlies being changed to super-rotating westerlies.

In the QTCM the zonally averaged wind anomaly is easterly throughout the whole depth of the tropical troposphere as shown in (Fig. 7.12(d)). There is no doubt that the basic state

Figure 7.12: QTCM velocity field anomalies (in ms^{-1}); (a) experiment 3KEQ 200 mb meridional wind minus control; (b) as (a) but at 850 mb; (c) experiment 3KW1 200 mb zonal wind minus control; (d) experiment 3KW1 zonally averaged zonal wind minus control, compare with UM Fig. 5.9(d). Uneven contouring in (a) and (b) is ± 0.1 0.25 0.5 1 2. Shaded areas indicate regions of positive anomaly.

equatorial zonal mean westerlies in the QTCM control experiment play a significant role in giving a response in experiment 3KW1 that is completely opposite to the response seen in the UM. The apparent problems in angular momentum conservation in the QTCM may also cause problems locally in the large scale stationary eddies where absolute vorticity may not be properly conserved due to the projection of the equations onto the surface stress terms. Whether this is the reason for the lack of anomalous forcing is not clear, but the basic state westerlies are certain to change the characteristics of the stationary eddy forcing that was found to be responsible for the equatorial westerlies in the UM experiment 3KW1.

7.3.4 Discussion

It is clear that the QTCM is able to reproduce much of the observed temporal and spatial distribution of tropical precipitation. However, the nature of the convection scheme and

dynamical formulation in particular appears to lead to fundamentally different results when forced with the idealised aqua-planet SST distributions.

One possible reason for this lies in the different nature of the convection schemes. In the UM the convection scheme is more independent of the observed climate in that the mean vertical profile of temperature, although constrained by convection, is not constrained to a particular profile. When using the QTCM this is not the case since the temperature and humidity are relaxed towards a distribution characteristic of the observed climate. Therefore, in essence the aqua-planet experiments can be viewed as a climate change experiment where the reference profiles of temperature and humidity applicable to the observed atmosphere do not necessarily apply.

The dynamical framework of the QTCM may also cause problems for angular momentum conservation since, as stated previously, the severe vertical truncation does not allow for the realistic distribution of the effects of surface stress. It may be the case that the inclusion of just one or two more vertical modes will result in a better vertical distribution of surface stress effects, confining it nearer to the surface.

Comparison of the QTCM and UM experiments show the usefulness of constructing a set of standardised experiments with which to test different aspects of an individual model set-up. The thinking behind such model intercomparison is that if we cannot understand the response to a large simplified forcing such as used in experiment 3KW1, and identify changes due to differences in the key parameterization schemes such as for convective and boundary layer processes, then we cannot hope to currently understand differences identified in more complex inter-comparison projects such as AMIP (Gates, 1992).

7.4 Conclusions

Examining the response of the model of LN to the suite of aqua-planet SST distributions we have seen this simple model captures much of the essential response observed in the UM. In particular the near equatorial flow is reproduced reasonably well implying that much of the near surface flow arises as a consequence of boundary layer temperature field induced pressure field. However, there are many caveats to this and in particular there is

a danger in assuming that the SSTs are communicated to the boundary layer in the same way, whether or not a region is convecting. The assumption of linearity in the LN model becomes increasingly unrealistic for large forcings and there is an obvious bias towards low-level meridional convergence in the UM not reproduced in the LN model. The danger of presuming the near surface temperature of the model is in equilibrium with the SST has been highlighted. It is not obvious which is the correct field to use since forcing from the SST reproduces the strength of the boundary layer flow well but not its distribution, whereas forcing from the 1000 mb temperature field produces the distribution of the flow well but not its strength.

Problems also arise when specifying how the boundary layer responds to convection and to what extent it redistributes the convergent mass. Our experiments have shown that this is problematic and that the boundary layer depth may not easily be defined in regions of strong convection. There is no doubt that processes which govern the boundary layer depth should depend on whether or not a region is convecting.

The repetition of the suite of aqua-planet experiments with the more complex QTCM demonstrates a number of common elements between its response and that of the UM. When subject to forcing from the zonally invariant SST profiles the QTCM captured the enhanced equatorial precipitation in response to the increased meridional SST gradients varying from the flat case to the peaked case. However, it was apparent that the QTCM was much less sensitive to these changes giving much lower precipitation increases. The reason for this almost certainly lies in the convection scheme and it is interesting that the QTCM and UM can give a very similar precipitation response to observed SST distributions but differ so markedly when subject to the aqua-planet SST distributions. One wonders whether model tuning in the parameter space of current observations may potentially be a dangerous practice.

In response to SST anomalies the sensitivity in precipitation is reversed compared to the UM such that the local increase in experiment 3KW1 is larger than in experiment 3KEQ. The position of upper-tropospheric anticyclones and the remote suppression of precipitation appear to be robust features of both the UM and QTCM, although the equatorial confinement of these features is somewhat reduced in the QTCM. However, fundamental differences occur between the wavenumber one experiments, with the zonally averaged zonal

wind forcing in the tropical troposphere being of the opposite sign between the two models. Such a contrasting response is almost certainly due to basic state westerlies in the QTCM control experiment as opposed to basic state easterlies in the UM control experiment, in addition to lack of constraint from angular momentum conservation. This leads to a very different basic flow on which the increased wave activity in the wavenumber one experiments have to propagate.

Appendix A7.1 Numerical Formulation of a Simple Model of the Tropical Boundary Layer

The single level boundary layer model (LN) is solved using the variables as they are set out on the staggered 'B'-grid of the UM (Fig. 7.13). This means that T_s and h' are staggered from U' and V' by half a grid spacing in longitude and latitude.

Figure 7.13: The Unified Model 'B'-grid used in the numerical code for the LN boundary layer model.

For the variable boundary layer version of the model the solutions to Eqns. 2.43, 2.45 and, 2.46 are performed numerically. The approach taken here is to formulate a time-dependent problem and iterate until the solution converges, given the forcing fields $[T_S]$ and T'_S . A simple centred time scheme and centred space scheme taking advantage of the grid staggering is used, which gives the prognostic tendencies and time-stepping as shown below. The initial time-step is a forward one.

$$\frac{\partial U'}{\partial t} = fV'_t - \frac{g}{a \cos \phi} \left[(2 - n[T_S])|_U + n\alpha H_0 \right] \frac{\partial h'}{\partial \lambda} \Big|_U \quad (\text{A7.1})$$

$$- \frac{nH_{BL}}{2} \left(1 - \frac{2\gamma}{3} \right) \frac{\partial T'_S}{\partial \lambda} \Big|_U - \epsilon U'_{t-1}$$

$$\frac{\partial V'}{\partial t} = -fU'_t - \frac{g}{a} \left[(2 - n[T_s]|_U + n\alpha H_{BL}) \frac{\partial h'}{\partial \phi} \Big|_U - \frac{nH_{BL}}{2} \left(1 - \frac{2\gamma}{3} \right) \frac{\partial T'_s}{\partial \phi} \Big|_U - \frac{nh'|_U}{2} \frac{\partial [T_s]}{\partial \phi} \Big|_U \right] - \epsilon V'_{t-1} \quad (\text{A7.2})$$

$$\frac{\partial h'}{\partial t} = -\frac{H_{BL}\rho}{a \cos \phi} \left[\frac{\partial U'}{\partial \lambda} \Big|_T + \frac{\partial (V' \cos \phi)}{\partial \phi} \Big|_T \right] - \frac{h'_{t-1}}{\tau_c} \quad (\text{A7.3})$$

$$V'_{t+1} = V'_{t-1} + 2\Delta t \frac{\partial V'}{\partial t} \quad (\text{A7.4})$$

$$U'_{t+1} = U'_{t-1} + 2\Delta t \frac{\partial U'}{\partial t} \quad (\text{A7.5})$$

$$h'_{t+1} = h'_{t-1} + 2\Delta t \frac{\partial h'}{\partial t} \quad (\text{A7.6})$$

Filtering is performed on the prognostic fields U' , V' , and h' , to prevent separation of the solution, which is often observed using a centred time scheme. Using a Robert-Asselin filter (Eqn. A7.7) couples the odd and even time-steps preventing the growth of the computational mode. Including a filter is akin to adding a diffusive term and so introduces a damping component. However taking the value for δ as just 0.02 minimises the damping effect.

$$\tilde{\Gamma}_t = \Gamma_t + \delta(\Gamma_{t+1} - 2\Gamma_t + \Gamma_{t-1}) \quad (\text{A7.7})$$

Interpolation of the model variables is required in order to calculate the boundary layer flow tendencies on the U-grid, and the boundary layer height perturbation tendencies on the T-grid. This is performed linearly. Therefore for interpolation performed on the U-grid the following approximations are used:

$$T'_S|_U = \frac{T'_{S(i+\frac{1}{2},j+\frac{1}{2})} + T'_{S(i+\frac{1}{2},j-\frac{1}{2})} + T'_{S(i-\frac{1}{2},j+\frac{1}{2})} + T'_{S(i-\frac{1}{2},j-\frac{1}{2})}}{4} \quad (\text{A7.8})$$

$$\frac{\partial T'_S}{\partial \lambda} \Big|_U = \frac{(T'_{S(i+\frac{1}{2},j+\frac{1}{2})} + T'_{S(i+\frac{1}{2},j-\frac{1}{2})}) - (T'_{S(i-\frac{1}{2},j-\frac{1}{2})} + T'_{S(i-\frac{1}{2},j+\frac{1}{2})})}{2\Delta \lambda} \quad (\text{A7.9})$$

$$\left. \frac{\partial T'_S}{\partial \phi} \right|_U = \frac{(T'_{S(i+\frac{1}{2},j+\frac{1}{2})} + T'_{S(i-\frac{1}{2},j+\frac{1}{2})}) - (T'_{S(i-\frac{1}{2},j-\frac{1}{2})} + T'_{S(i+\frac{1}{2},j-\frac{1}{2})})}{2\Delta\phi} \quad (\text{A7.10})$$

$$[T_S]|_U = \frac{[T_S]_{(j+\frac{1}{2})} + [T_S]_{(j-\frac{1}{2})}}{2} \quad (\text{A7.11})$$

$$\left. \frac{\partial [T_S]}{\partial \phi} \right|_U = \frac{[T_S]_{(j+\frac{1}{2})} - [T_S]_{(j-\frac{1}{2})}}{\phi}. \quad (\text{A7.12})$$

For calculations using U', V' performed on the T-grid the following interpolations are used:

$$\left. \frac{\partial U'}{\partial \lambda} \right|_T = \frac{(U'_{(i+\frac{1}{2},j+\frac{1}{2})} + U'_{(i+\frac{1}{2},j-\frac{1}{2})}) - (U'_{(i-\frac{1}{2},j-\frac{1}{2})} + U'_{(i-\frac{1}{2},j+\frac{1}{2})})}{2\Delta\lambda} \quad (\text{A7.13})$$

$$\left. \frac{\partial V'}{\partial \phi} \right|_T = \frac{(V'_{(i+\frac{1}{2},j+\frac{1}{2})} + V'_{(i-\frac{1}{2},j+\frac{1}{2})}) - (V'_{(i-\frac{1}{2},j-\frac{1}{2})} + V'_{(i+\frac{1}{2},j-\frac{1}{2})})}{2\Delta\phi}. \quad (\text{A7.14})$$

In general there is very good convergence after 10 days when the computed solution varies by less than 1%. The crucial parameters of the linear drag time scale (Rayleigh friction coefficient), ϵ , and the cumulus adjustment time scale, τ_c , are held constant at the experiment specified values between 40° north and south. Poleward of this ϵ is slowly increased to 10 times the experiment value, and τ_c is reduced to zero in order to prevent numerical instabilities due to grid-point convergence near the pole.

Chapter 8

Conclusions

The research in this thesis has attempted to increase our understanding of the physical and dynamical processes which lead to the communication of SST to the atmosphere and subsequent local and remote effects of convective heating. This is facilitated by the analysis of results from a sequence of experiments with an idealised version of the UM subject to simplified SST distributions. In the introduction four key areas of investigation were highlighted and results that have implications in these areas are summarised here.

8.1 Convective Response to SST Distribution

In Chapter 3 the nature of the zonal mean ITCZ is found to be strongly dependent on the distribution of the SST. With large curvature in the latitudinal gradient of SST the ITCZ precipitation becomes intense and confined nearer to the equator. This is more a consequence of the increased hydrostatically induced pressure gradients, which leads to frictional convergence of the boundary layer zonal flow, being confined closer to the equator. There is no significant increase in the moisture supply to the ITCZ. A transition of the model regime from one with a preferred strong ITCZ centred on the equator to one with no preferred region and quasi uniform precipitation throughout the tropics, occurs for a pole to equator temperature gradient which is approximately in agreement with simple theory and modelling studies (Held and Hou, 1980). However, it is doubtful that this regime transition will be independent of the convective parameterization used. Indeed, results from the

QTCM experiments (Chapter 7) which suggest no regime transition for the experiments performed, and the results of Hess *et al.* (1993) appear to support this conclusion.

As well as the regime transition characteristics, the actual strength of the ITCZ differs markedly between the aqua-planet experiments and the QTCM experiments. The strong sensitivity to the near-equator gradient of SST seen in the aqua-planet is not reflected in the QTCM. Again this may be due to differences in the parameterization of convection. Whereas in the UM convection strength is related to the stability of the initial convecting layer the convection scheme of the QTCM determines convection strength by restoring the atmospheric temperature to a pre-determined vertical profile. However, the vertical temperature profile for the control and peaked experiments is shown to vary considerably for the same underlying SST. Therefore, consistent with the summary of Frank (1983), moist convective adjustment schemes in general bypass the main physics of the system and are not optimal for investigating interactions between convection and larger scales as is performed in the idealised experiments of this thesis. The results from the QTCM indicate this, as the convective response is mainly thermodynamic and instability associated with interactions with the large-scale circulation appear smaller than in the UM.

The zonally averaged response when the SST maxima lies just off the equator also differs between the UM and the QTCM. In the UM the precipitation changes are complex with a slight double structure in the ITCZ and reduction in precipitation strength compared to the equatorial SST maximum. In the QTCM the changes are less complex with a single ITCZ structure being retained. However, the precipitation sensitivity is reversed such that the ITCZ becomes stronger by up to 50%, and this is accompanied by a strong reduction of precipitation on the opposite side of the equator. Therefore, whereas the UM shows greater sensitivity to changes in the curvature of the SST gradient the QTCM appears more sensitive to the position of the SST maximum.

The influence of mid-latitude processes on the distribution of tropical precipitation is found to be significant in the UM. In particular when the ITCZ is absent precipitation maxima are found on the fringes of the tropics where the strongest mid-latitude systems are able to penetrate and destabilise the lower-troposphere. Warmer waters extend a considerable distance poleward when the meridional curvature of SST is small and equatorward flow of colder air behind the frontal regions appears responsible for triggering convection, leading

to the precipitation maxima. Therefore, synoptic interaction between the tropics and extra-tropics has a noticeable impact on the distribution of tropical rainfall when the large-scale organisation of tropical precipitation is weak.

The aqua-planet SST anomaly experiments reveal the large sensitivity to the characteristics of the SST field. There exists strong non-linearity in the convective response to the magnitude for realistic amplitudes of SST anomaly. However, given the results from the experiments of Chapter 3 the intense response appears more likely to be realised through the existence of enhanced curvature in the latitudinal SST gradients rather than in response solely to an increase in the absolute magnitude of SST. In all anomaly experiments the precipitation maximum lies to the west of the SST anomaly maximum, implying feedback from the dynamical response to the additional convective heating. This aspect is particularly sensitive to the scale and zonal gradient of the anomaly emphasising that the location of tropical convection is not necessarily locked to the region of maximum SST. The position of convection is indeed sensitive to the flow anomalies induced by the subtle boundary layer pressure gradients, consequential of the tropical gradients in SST.

Analysis performed in Chapter 6 found that the transient organisation of precipitation is also a strong function of near equatorial SST gradients in the hemispherically symmetric experiments. Wavenumber-frequency analysis following Wheeler and Kiladis (1999) reveals that much of the dispersion characteristics of the observed tropical atmosphere are present in the aqua-planet UM. In particular there is greatest power in tropically confined Kelvin and Rossby wave disturbances. One wave disturbance that is notably absent in all the aqua-planet experiments, but present in the full version of the UM, is the global scale MJO.

As with the time-mean distribution of precipitation there is a strong transition change between the control experiment and the flatter equatorial SST experiment. In the peaked and control experiments the greatest organisation of precipitation was provided by Kelvin waves with zonal wavenumbers 4 and 5 travelling west to east with a phase speed of 18 ms^{-1} . Power in the Kelvin wave disturbances is much reduced with flatter equatorial SST gradients and any organisation is by westward moving wave disturbances.

Of all the SST anomaly experiments a wavenumber one anomaly provides the largest changes to the characteristics of the wavenumber frequency distribution. In particular the power in the Kelvin wave disturbances is distributed over a larger range of wavenumbers as a con-

sequence of the continually changing magnitude of SST along the equator, which generates zonally propagating convective disturbances of varying intensity and speed. The presence of an SST anomaly and its associated quasi-stationary convective maxima also provides a block to the Kelvin wave disturbances which in the control experiment were traceable for several consecutive revolutions of the earth.

The wavenumber-frequency analysis performed in this thesis provides a good tool for summarising as to whether a model is capturing the observed transient disturbances in the atmosphere. This may be vital if transient disturbances are the key to understanding how the atmosphere communicates local climate anomalies to remote regions.

8.2 Direct Dynamical Response to Convective Heating

The motivation for using the aqua-planet was to obtain a more coherent signal of the response to convective heating. This was certainly the case in the hemispherically symmetric and hemispherically asymmetric experiments. In the experiments with a strong ITCZ the Hadley circulation is found to be confined very close to the equator consistent with the more confined ITCZ. This suggests that the zonal asymmetries present in the observed atmosphere act to latitudinally broaden the tropical circulation features. Furthermore the sub-tropical westerly jets are also much closer to the equator than observed as angular momentum conserving flow extends much less further poleward in the Hadley circulation.

The meridional SST gradient curvature at which the need for a Hadley circulation is removed agrees with the simple angular momentum conservation arguments of Held and Hou (1980). Viewing the zonal mean circulation in terms of angular momentum conserving flow simplifies the diagnosis of the zonal mean circulation. In particular, it is useful to interpret the Hadley circulation as the meridional overturning necessary to sufficiently adjust the imposed atmospheric temperature distribution, such that the implied zonal thermal wind distribution no longer violates angular momentum conservation. The angular momentum constraint does not appear to be present in the QTCM dynamics given that a transition to a climate with no Hadley circulation is not seen.

Changes to the zonally averaged circulation that occur when the SST maximum is moved off

the equator are not simple. In the UM experiments the increases in the Hadley circulation are offset to an extent by the changes in the baroclinically driven Ferrel cell due to changes in the extra-tropical gradient of SST. Therefore, the changes in the extra-tropics acts to reduce the large dominance of a single winter Hadley circulation often predicted in simple sensitivity studies of the Hadley circulation (e.g. Lindzen and Hou, 1988). This restriction of the sensitivity by the extra-tropical circulation may explain why the QTCM has the winter Hadley cell dominating strongly. In the QTCM extra-tropical processes are represented very simply and are also largely damped poleward of 45°N and S. The QTCM would thus be less sensitive to changes in the gradient of SST in the extra-tropics and be unable to affect the dominance of the tropical circulation.

In the confined anomaly experiments (Chapter 4) the pattern of rainfall suppression is consistent with the descent regions of a tropical confined wave response to a diabatic heating anomaly following Gill (1980). However, the vertical profile of the diabatic heating anomaly is shown to have considerable structure with large contributions from both convective and cloud-top radiative processes, particularly in the upper-troposphere. Therefore, the lower-tropospheric flow in general agrees with tropical wave theory with a Rossby wave response to the west and a Kelvin wave response to the east. However, in the upper-troposphere the response is much less Gill-like and the dominant anticyclonic response is found on and to the east of the heating, rather than to the west. This situation is found to satisfy vorticity balance arguments by virtue of a pool of zero absolute vorticity extending across the centre of the anticyclones regions.

The different morphology of the region of divergent outflow and the close proximity of strong westerlies nearer the equator when compared with observed may also contribute to this very different upper-tropospheric response. A further consequence of this eastward shift in the anticyclonic response is shown to be an associated shift in the Rossby wave source region. The shift in the diabatic heating anomaly due to changes in the shape of the SST anomaly also has a significant impact on the location of the Rossby wave source regions.

8.3 Atmospheric Teleconnections

In Chapter 1 a summary of possible tropical-tropical teleconnection mechanisms listed both tropically overturning Walker circulations and more indirect planetary Rossby wave propagation as candidates. However the dominant large-scale response to convection is, in the first instance, realised primarily through an enhancement in the local Hadley circulation. Results from Chapter 5 reveal that tropical meridional divergence anomalies are much larger than zonal divergence anomalies, the position of which are inconsistent with the zonal flow structure suggestive of a Walker circulation response.

The possibility of changes in the Hadley circulation being able to facilitate tropic-wide changes in precipitation, as proposed for the TWM (Ward, 1993), was investigated in the SST anomaly experiments of Chapter 4. Even though experiments were not performed for JAS conditions, the local and remote response to an SST anomaly would seem to suggest a significant role for the Hadley circulation. A local enhancement of the Hadley circulation in both hemispheres is indeed accompanied by a weakening over the longitudes of rainfall suppression. However, the remote changes are more complex than a simple reduction of cloud top in the ITCZ and a reversal anomaly in the Hadley circulation. These changes do occur in the suppression regions but lower in the troposphere the nature of the confined tropical wave response to the heating means that reversal of the Hadley circulation ascent is realised most strongly just off the equator and there is actually an increase in ascent on the equator.

The nature of the remote response to tropical heating anomalies is illustrated most clearly in the experiments performed in Chapter 5. The downstream upper-tropospheric equatorial westerlies are most prevalent in the wavenumber one experiments but are actually present to a lesser extent in the confined anomaly experiments. Analysis of the divergent flow shows that these westerlies are inconsistent with a Walker type circulation and more consistent with an upper-tropospheric rotational response. Analysis of the stationary eddy component of the flow pinpoints the generation mechanism to convergence of eddy momentum flux associated with an eastward and poleward propagation of stationary Rossby waves. This westerly momentum is also transported downwards to the mid-troposphere by zonal wavenumber one scale eddies oriented in the vertical.

Performing the very idealised wavenumber one SST experimentation in Chapter 5 has, therefore, enabled processes involving remote teleconnections, of which there were weaker indications of in the confined anomaly experiments, to be more clearly identified.

8.4 Simple Models and Model Intercomparison

The experiments performed in Chapter 7 aimed to test the ability of simpler atmospheric models to represent aspects of the UM circulation when subject to the same SST forcing. The boundary layer model (Lindzen and Nigam, 1987) did not reproduce the boundary layer flow anomalies from the UM SST anomaly experiments as well as it was able to reproduce the flow anomalies from observations. One reason for this was the disagreement between the eddy SST and the eddy 1000 mb temperature in the UM. The fixed nature of the SST and the way in which the lowest levels of the model respond to the SST in regions of extreme convection may account for the differences. This demonstrates that care must be taken when using such a simple model. For example the SST is often taken from an ocean model and assumed to be representative of the 1000 mb temperature in order to use the boundary layer model to calculate surface stress and feed back onto the ocean model. The relationship between SST and 1000 mb temperature can have significant geographical variations as seen from the UM. A further conclusion from using this simple model is that in regions of intense convection over the SST anomaly it appears that the boundary layer depth may be ill defined making estimates of the perturbations to this depth difficult, especially since these are the same regions where SST and 1000 mb temperature can differ the most.

The QTCM experiments proved very useful in demonstrating how results from models with very different dynamical and physical representations can vary given identical and simple boundary forcing. It is perhaps somewhat surprising that both the UM and the QTCM are able to reproduce realistic mean and seasonal evolution of the observed precipitation distribution given that the pattern of boundary forcing is infinitely more complicated than in the aqua-planet configuration. Such a situation highlights that a certain amount of tuning is performed with numerical models in order to achieve success in the parameter space of observations

The reasons for the fundamental differences between the UM and the QTCM are difficult

to pin down. It appears that the projection of the vertical modes onto the surface stress terms does not give a good representation of the effects of surface stress in the vertical. This does not seem to allow local angular momentum conservation, particularly within the deep tropics. A large sensitivity to the parameterization of surface stress was found in the tropics when the transfer coefficient from the baroclinic to the barotropic component of the flow was reduced by an order of magnitude. Such sensitivity seen in the aqua-planet experiments is not observed when the QTCM is forced with observed SSTs.

8.5 Further Work

The work carried out in this thesis has highlighted the benefits of taking a complex model but forcing it with the simplest boundary conditions. Possible extensions to this work concerned with two aspects of the experimentation are discussed below.

8.5.1 Tropical Climate Variability

Following this thesis the dependence of the remote climate tropical variability on local SST anomalies is by no means fully understood, but further experimentation on the same lines as this thesis may prove to be beneficial. The seasonality of any remote response to SST forcing will be significant given the observed seasonal variations of the sub-tropical jets, which of course has implications for the wave guide properties necessary for any tropical-extratropical communication. Indeed, the teleconnections associated with the TWM were found to be most prevalent and statistically significant mainly during the JAS season.

Another area of future work could involved testing the dependence of the aqua-planet results on the nature of the model convection parameterization. In particular changes have been made to a subsequent version of the UM convection scheme. From UM version HadAM2b, the version used in this thesis, to version HadAM3 the convective parameterization has been changed to incorporate convective momentum transport processes (Gregory *et al.*, 1997). The sensitivity of the UM to this enhancement to the convection scheme is tested in Kershaw and Gregory (1997) and partially corrects the zonal mean westerly model bias in the tropical mid-troposphere during the DJF season. The inclusion of convective momentum

transport also has a noticeable impact on the tropical variability, increasing it in some regions and decreasing it in others. Rerunning the aqua-planet experiments using the updated version of the convection scheme may result in fundamentally different model results. In particular the tropical shear present in the wavenumber one experiments may be very sensitive to the transport of lower-tropospheric easterly momentum into the upper-troposphere. Additionally the strength of the transient Kelvin wave disturbances, which provides the dominant organisation of tropical precipitation, may be adversely affected by the introduction of convective momentum transports.

Many of the problems associated with the communication of SST to the lower-troposphere were due to the fixed nature of the SST which could not adjust to temperature, momentum and moisture fluxes from the atmosphere. Therefore, a natural progression of this study would be to include some kind of interactive component to the ocean. In the first instance this may be a simple thermodynamic ocean which could respond to fluxes of heat and moisture from the atmosphere. With such an interactive ocean the SST would be able to adjust to the large fluxes of heat between the SST and the boundary layer, seen particularly in regions below the intense ITCZ convection. With such an interactive ocean, SST and lower-tropospheric temperature would probably be more closely balanced than in the fixed SST aqua-planet. This may also have interesting consequences for the strength and distribution of tropical precipitation, particularly since the poorest SST communication is located beneath the most intense precipitation in the UM.

In keeping with maintaining the simplified nature of the aqua-planet boundary conditions but extending the scope of the study, the effects of the land surface on the distribution of precipitation could be investigated. This would involve including an idealised land mass in the model similar to the study of Cook and Gnanadesikan (1991). In that work the effect of an idealised land mass, straddling the equator, on the position and strength of the nearby ITCZ and Hadley circulation was examined and found to change their characteristics due to interactions with land surface processes. To be of relevance for identifying mechanisms involved in the TWM, the effect of idealised northern hemispheric land masses such as the Asian monsoon and North Africa continents could be investigated. Indeed, Ward (1993) suggested that land surface processes and in particular soil moisture content may have a significant role in the distribution of precipitation associated with the TWM.

8.5.2 Implications for Tropical Climate Modelling

The tools available for understanding the role of convection in the tropical climate system have to date been restricted to single column models, cloud resolving models, and full GCMs with realistic but complicated boundary conditions. Single column and cloud resolving models tell us much about the behaviour of convection on the smallest scales and its role in distributing heat, moisture, and momentum in the vertical. Simple dynamical models tell us much about the response to some imposed consequential convective heating. These models certainly assist with our understanding of convective processes and the response to them, but only to a point. As was apparent from all the aqua-planet experiments the interaction of convection with the dynamics is not an obvious one and the role played by the individual model parameterizations is indeed subtle. In full GCMs the interaction of convection and dynamics is represented but the complexity of the boundary conditions makes it extremely difficult to attribute any element of the model response to particular processes or parameterizations.

One possible way to help remedy these inadequacies and possibly fill the niche between the simplest models and full GCMs, is to perform standard experiments with an aqua-planet setup. This may help us understand more clearly the role of a particular parameterization in a model, and could also be utilised as a GCM intercomparison tool much like the AMIP project with full GCMs. The standard set of experiments would consist of a number of SST distributions designed to test certain gross aspects of the models response but in the simplest possible way. In the same way that the GCM dynamical core tests of Held and Suarez (1994) aim to *isolate the dynamics as much as possible from the complexity of physical parameterizations*, the aqua-planet tests would aim to isolate the response to the SST field from the complexity of the land surface parameterization and land-sea contrasts. For instance the hemispherically symmetric SST profiles used in Chapter 3 would enable the threshold for the change in regime between a strong ITCZ and weak ITCZ climate to be determined for a range number of GCMs. The intercomparison of the response would be far simpler than for the AMIP project and the differences due to the use of different parameterizations between models, say for convection, would be much more readily identifiable.

The set of experiments would certainly include SST distributions with tropical anomalies.

Experiments would determine the response to a composite El Niño SST distribution. In particular the anomaly experiments may help to identify much clearer signals of the following aspects of the models response:

- The lower-tropospheric supply of moisture for convection.
 - The position of maximum precipitation in relation to the maximum SST.
 - The vertical distribution of diabatic heating.
 - The strength of tropical wave response to convective heating and associated precipitation suppression.
 - The sensitivity of the tropical zonal flow.
 - The nature of the interaction with the mid-latitude climate and remote tropical climate.
-

List of Symbols

β	Meridional gradient of planetary vorticity ($\text{s}^{-1}\text{m}^{-1}$).
f	Planetary vorticity (s^{-1}).
g	Acceleration due to gravity (ms^{-2}).
ζ	Absolute vorticity (s^{-1}).
ξ	Relative vorticity (s^{-1}).
ϕ	Latitude (degrees).
λ	Longitude (degrees).
r_e	Mean radius of the earth (ms^{-1}).
ρ	Density (of air) (kg m^{-3}).
ψ	Streamfunction (m^2s^{-1}).
χ	Velocity potential (m^2s^{-1}).
θ	Potential temperature (K).
Φ	Geopotential (m^2s^{-2}).
u	Zonal velocity (ms^{-1}).
\mathbf{u}	Three dimensional velocity vector (ms^{-1}).
\mathbf{v}	Two dimensional horizontal velocity vector (ms^{-1}).
u_M	Zonal velocity due to angular momentum conservation (ms^{-1}).
u_E	Zonal velocity due to radiative equilibrium (ms^{-1}).
v	Meridional velocity (ms^{-1}).
w	Vertical velocity (height) (ms^{-1}).
\mathbf{v}_ψ	Rotational component of the two dimensional horizontal velocity vector (ms^{-1}).
\mathbf{v}_χ	Divergent component of the two dimensional horizontal velocity vector (ms^{-1}).
\mathbf{v}_0	Barotropic horizontal velocity vector (ms^{-1}).
\mathbf{v}_1	Baroclinic horizontal velocity vector (ms^{-1}).
ω	Vertical velocity (pressure) (mb hr^{-1}).
Ω	Planetary rotation rate (rad s^{-1}).
k	Zonal wavenumber.
l	Meridional wavenumber.
m	Vertical wavenumber.
K	Total wavenumber = $\sqrt{k^2 + l^2}$.
K_s	Stationary wavenumber = $\sqrt{(\beta - U_{yy})/U}$.

Q_0	Large-scale scaled diabatic heating term (Ks^{-1})
H_T	Depth of the (tropical) troposphere (m).
H_0	Equivalent tropospheric depth (m).
ϵ_0	Damping coefficient of the barotropic velocity (s^{-1}).
ϵ_1	Damping coefficient of the baroclinic velocity (s^{-1}).
ϵ_{01}	Transfer coefficient from the barotropic to the baroclinic wind (s^{-1}).
ϵ_{10}	Transfer coefficient from the baroclinic to the barotropic wind (s^{-1}).
$\bar{\Gamma}$	Time mean of quantity Γ .
Γ'	Deviation from zonal mean of quantity Γ .
$[\Gamma]$	Zonal mean of quantity Γ .
Γ^*	Deviation from zonal mean of quantity Γ .

References

- Allen, M. R. and Davey, M. K. (1993). Empirical parameterization of tropical ocean-atmosphere coupling: The 'Inverse Gill problem'. *J. Climate*, **6**, 509–530.
- Arakawa, A. and Schubert, W. H. (1974). Interaction of a cumulus cloud ensemble with the large-scale environment. Part I. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **31**, 674–701.
- Battisti, D. S. and Ovens, D. D. (1995). The dependence of the low-level equatorial easterly jet on Hadley and Walker circulations. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **52**, 3911–3931.
- Battisti, D. S., Charachik, E. S., and Hirst, A. C. (1999). A consistent model for the large scale steady surface atmospheric circulation in the tropics. *J. Climate*, **Accepted**.
- Betts, A. K. (1986). A new convective adjustment scheme. I: Observational and theoretical basis. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.*, **112**, 677–691.
- Bjerknes, J. (1966). A possible response of the atmospheric Hadley circulation to equatorial anomalies of ocean temperature. *Tellus*, **118**, 820–829.
- Branstator, G. (1985). Analysis of general circulation model sea-surface temperature anomaly simulations using a linear model. Part I: Forced solutions. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **42**, 2225–2241.
- Charney, J. G. and Eliassen, A. (1964). On the growth of the hurricane depression. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **21**, 68–75.
- Cook, K. H. and Gnanadesikan, A. (1991). Effects of saturated and dry land surfaces on the tropical circulation and precipitation in a general-circulation model. *J. Climate*, **4**, 873–889.
- Cullen, M. J. P. (1993). The unified forecast/climate model. *Meteorol. Mag.*, **122**, 81–94.
- Emanuel, K. A., Neelin, J. D., and Bretherton, C. S. (1994). On large-scale circulations in convecting atmospheres. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.*, **120**, 1111–1143.
- Frank, W. M. (1983). The cumulus parameterization problem. *Mon. Wea. Rev.*, **111**, 1859–1871.
- Gates, W. L. (1992). AMIP: The atmospheric model intercomparison project. *Bull. Amer. Met. Soc.*, **73**, 1962–1970.
- Geisler, J. E., Blackmon, M. L., Bates, G. T., and S. Muñoz (1985). Sensitivity of January climate response to the magnitude and position of equatorial Pacific sea surface temperature anomalies. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **42**, 1037–1049.
- Gibson, J. K., Kallberg, P., Uppsala, S., Hernandez, A., Nomura, A., and Serrano, E.

- (1997). *ECMWF Re-analysis, Project Report Series. 1. ERA Description.*
- Gill, A. E. (1980). Some simple solutions for heat-induced tropical circulations. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.*, **106**, 447–762.
- Goswami, B. M., Shukla, J., Schneider, E. K., and Sud, Y. C. (1984). Study of the dynamics of the intertropical convergence zone with a symmetric version of the GLAS model. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **41**, 5–19.
- Gregory, D. and Rowntree, P. R. (1990). A mass flux convection scheme with representation of cloud ensemble characteristics and stability dependent closure. *Mon. Wea. Rev.*, **118**, 1483–1506.
- Gregory, D., Kershaw, R., and Inness, P. M. (1997). Parameterization of momentum transport by convection. II: Tests in single-column and general circulation models. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.*, **123**, 1153–1183.
- Hadley, G. (1735). Concerning the cause of the general trade-winds. *Phil. Trans.*, **29**, 58–62.
- Halley, E. (1686). An historical account of the trade-winds and monsoons observable in the seas between and near the tropics with an attempt to assign the physical cause of said winds. *Phil. Trans.*, **26**, 61–80.
- Hayashi, Y. Y. and Sumi, A. (1986). The 30-40 day oscillations simulated in an aqua-planet model. *J. Meteor. Soc. Japan*, **65**, 843–852.
- Held, I. M. and Hou, A. Y. (1980). Nonlinear axially symmetric circulations in a nearly inviscid atmosphere. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **37**, 515–533.
- Held, I. M. and Suarez, M. J. (1994). A proposal for the intercomparison of the dynamical cores of atmospheric general circulation models. *Bull. Amer. Met. Soc.*, **75**, 1825–1830.
- Hendon, H. H. and Glick, J. (1997). Intraseasonal air-sea interaction in the tropical Indian and Pacific oceans. *J. Climate*, **10**, 647–661.
- Hess, P. G., Battisti, D. S., and Rasch, P. J. (1993). The intertropical convergence zones and the large-scale tropical circulation on a water covered earth. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **50**, 691–713.
- Hoerling, M. P., Kumar, A., and Zhong, M. (1997). El Niño, La Niña and the nonlinearity of their teleconnections. *J. Climate*, **10**, 1769–1786.
- Horel, J. D. (1982). On the annual cycle of the tropical Pacific atmosphere and ocean. *Mon. Wea. Rev.*, **110**, 1863–1878.
- Horel, J. D. and Wallace, J. M. (1981). Planetary scale atmospheric phenomena associated
-

- with the southern oscillation. *Mon. Wea. Rev.*, **109**, 813–829.
- Hoskins, B. J. and Karoly, D. J. (1981). The steady linear response of a spherical atmosphere to thermal and orographic forcing. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **38**, 1179–1196.
- Hoskins, B. J. and Rodwell, M. J. (1995). A model of the Asian summer monsoon, Part I: The global scale. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **52**, 1329–1340.
- Hoskins, B. J., Hsu, H. H., James, I. N., Masutani, M., Sardeshmukh, P. D., and White, G. H. (1989). Diagnostics of the Global Atmospheric Circulation, based on ECMWF analyses. Technical Report WCRP-27, World Meteorological Organisation (Geneva).
- Ingram, W. J. (1995). 'Radiation'. *Unified Model Documentation Paper 23 (v1)*. Meteorological Office, London Road, Bracknell, Berkshire RG12 2SZ, UK.
- Itoh, H. and Ghil, M. (1988). The generation mechanism of mixed Rossby-gravity waves in the equatorial troposphere. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **45**, 585–604.
- James, I. N. and James, P. (1992). Spatial nature of the ultra-low frequency variability of the flow in a simple atmospheric general circulation model. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.*, **118**, 1211–1233.
- Ju, J. and Slingo, J. (1995). The Asian summer monsoon and ENSO. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.*, **121**, 1133–1168.
- Kershaw, R. and Gregory, D. (1997). Parameterization of momentum transport by convection. I: Theory and cloud modelling results. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.*, **123**, 1133–1151.
- Kindle, J. C. and Phoebus, P. A. (1995). The ocean response to operational westerly wind bursts. *J. Geophys. Res. (Oceans)*, **100**, 4893–4920.
- Kuo, H. L. (1974). Further studies of the parameterization of the influence of cumulus convection on the large-scale flow. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **31**, 1232–1240.
- Lau, K. M. and Lim, H. (1982). Thermally driven motions in an equatorial β plane: Hadley and Walker circulations during the winter monsoon. *Mon. Wea. Rev.*, **110**, 336–353.
- Lau, N. C., Held, I. M., and Neelin, J. D. (1988). The Madden-Julian oscillation in an idealised general circulation model. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **45**, 3810–3832.
- Lindzen, R. S. and Holton, J. R. (1968). A theory of the quasi-biennial oscillation. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **25**, 1095–1107.
- Lindzen, R. S. and Hou, A. Y. (1988). Hadley circulations for zonally averaged heating centered off the equator. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **45**, 2417–2427.
- Lindzen, R. S. and Nigam, S. (1987). On the role of sea surface temperature gradients in forcing low-level winds and convergence in the tropics. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **44**, 2418–2436.
-

- Livezey, R. E., Masutani, M., Leetmaa, A., Rui, H., Ji, M., and Kumar, A. (1997). Teleconnective response of the Pacific-North American region atmosphere to large Central equatorial Pacific SST anomalies. *J. Climate*, **10**, 1787–1820.
- Lorenc, A. C. (1984). The evolution of planetary-scale 200 mb divergent flow during the FGGE year. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.*, **110**, 427–441.
- Madden, R. A. and Julian, P. R. (1994). Observations of the 40-60 day tropical oscillation – A review. *Mon. Wea. Rev.*, **122**, 814–835.
- Manabe, S., Smagorinsky, J., and Strickler, R. F. (1965). Simulated climatology of a general circulation model with a hydrologic cycle. *Mon. Wea. Rev.*, **93**, 769–798.
- Matsuno, T. (1966). Quasi-geostrophic motions in the equatorial area. *J. Meteor. Soc. Japan*, **44**, 25–43.
- Miller, M. J., Beljaars, A. C. M., and Palmer, T. N. (1992). The sensitivity of the ECMWF model to the parameterization of evaporation from the tropical oceans. *J. Climate*, **5**, 418–434.
- Neelin, J. D. (1989). On the interpretation of the Gill model. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **46**, 2466–2468.
- Neelin, J. D. (1997). Implications of convective quasi-equilibrium for the large-scale flow. In R. K. Smith, editor, *The Physics and Parameterization of Moist Convection*, pages 413–446. Kluwer Academic Publishers.
- Neelin, J. D. and Zeng, N. (1999). The first quasi-equilibrium tropical circulation model – Formulation. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **Submitted**.
- Palmer, T. N. and Mansfield, D. A. (1986). A study of wintertime circulation anomalies during past El Niño events using a high resolution general circulation model. I: Influence of model climatology. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.*, **112**, 613–638.
- Parker, D. E., Jackson, M., and Horton, E. B. (1995). The GISST2.2 sea surface temperature and sea-ice climatology. CRTN 63, Hadley Centre, U.K. Meteorological Office.
- Philander, S. G. H. (1985). El Niño and La Niña. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **42**, 652–662.
- Ropelewski, C. F. and Halpert, M. S. (1996). Global and regional scale precipitation patterns associated with El Niño/Southern Oscillations. *Mon. Wea. Rev.*, **115**, 1606–1626.
- Saravanan, R. (1993). Equatorial superrotation and maintenance of the general circulation in two-level models. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **50**, 1211–1227.
- Saravanan, R. and Chang, P. (1999). Interaction between tropical Atlantic variability and El Niño-Southern Oscillation. *J. Climate*, **Submitted**.
- Sardeshmukh, P. D. and Hoskins, B. J. (1985). Vorticity balances in the tropics during the
-

- 1982-83 El Niño-Southern Oscillation event. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.*, **111**, 261-278.
- Sardeshmukh, P. D. and Hoskins, B. J. (1988). The generation of global rotational flow by steady idealised tropical divergence. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **45**, 1228-1251.
- Saxen, T. S. and Rutledge, S. A. (1998). Surface fluxes and boundary layer recovery in TOGA COARE: Sensitivity to convective organisation. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **55**, 2763-2781.
- Schneider, E. K. (1977). Axially symmetric steady-state models of the basic state for instability and climate studies. Part II. Nonlinear Calculations. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **34**, 280-296.
- Schneider, E. K. and Lindzen, R. S. (1977). Axially symmetric steady-state models of the basic state for instability and climate studies. Part I. Linearised Calculations. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **34**, 263-279.
- Sherwood, S. C., Ramanathan, V., Barnett, T. P., Tyree, M. K., and Roeckner, E. (1994). Response of an atmospheric general circulation model to radiative forcing of tropical clouds. *J. Geophys. Res. (Atmospheres)*, **99**, 20829-20845.
- Simmons, A. J. (1982). The forcing of stationary wave motion by tropical diabatic heating. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.*, **108**, 503-534.
- Slingo, J. M. (1998a). The 1997/98 El Niño. *Weather*, **53**, 274-281.
- Slingo, J. M. (1998b). Extratropical forcing of tropical convection in a northern winter simulation with the UGAMP GCM. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.*, **124**, 27-51.
- Smith, R. N. B. (1993). 'Subsurface, Surface and Boundary Layer Processes'. *Unified Model Documentation Paper 24 (v2)*. Meteorological Office, London Road, Bracknell, Berkshire RG12 2SZ, UK.
- Soman, M. K. and Slingo, J. (1997). Sensitivity of the Asian summer monsoon to aspects of sea-surface-temperature anomalies in the tropical Pacific Ocean. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.*, **123**, 309-336.
- Suarez, M. J. and Duffy, D. G. (1992). Terrestrial superrotation: A bifurcation of the general circulation. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **49**, 1541-1554.
- Swinbank, R., Palmer, T. N., and Davey, M. K. (1988). Numerical simulations of the Madden and Julian oscillation. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **45**, 774-788.
- Trenberth, K. E., Branstator, G. W., Karoly, D., Kumar, A., Lau, N.-C., and Ropelewski, C. (1998). Progress during TOGA in understanding and modelling global teleconnections associated with tropical sea surface temperature anomalies. *J. Geophys. Res. (Oceans)*, **103**, 14291-14324.

- Walker, G. T. (1923). Correlation in seasonal variations of weather. VIII. A preliminary study of world weather. *Mem. Indian Meteorol. Dep*, **24**(4), 75–131.
- Wallace, J. M. and Gutzler, D. S. (1981). Teleconnections in the geopotential height field during the northern hemisphere winter. *Mon. Wea. Rev.*, **109**, 784–812.
- Ward, M. N. (1993). *Tropical north African rainfall and worldwide monthly to multi-decadal climate variations*. Ph.D. thesis, University of Reading, U.K.
- Webster, P. J. (1981). Mechanisms determining the atmospheric response to sea surface temperature anomalies. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **38**, 554–571.
- Webster, P. J. and Lukas, R. (1992). TOGA COARE: The coupled ocean-atmosphere response experiment. *Bull. Amer. Met. Soc.*, **73**, 1377–1416.
- Webster, P. J. and Yang, S. (1992). Monsoon and ENSO: Selectively interactive systems. *Q. J. R. Meteorol. Soc.*, **118**, 877–926.
- Wheeler, M. and Kiladis, G. N. (1999). Convectively coupled equatorial waves: Analysis of clouds and temperature in the wavenumber-frequency domain. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **56**, 374–399.
- Woolnough, S. J. (1997). *A study of equatorial superrotation in a two-level model of the atmosphere*. Ph.D. thesis, University of Reading, U.K.
- Xie, P. and Arkin, P. A. (1996). Analyses of global monthly precipitation using gauge observations satellite estimates, and numerical model predictions. *J. Climate*, **9**, 840–858.
- Zebiak, S. E. (1982). A simple model of relevance to El Niño. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **39**, 2017–2027.
- Zebiak, S. E. (1986). Atmospheric convergence feedback in a simple model for El Niño. *Mon. Wea. Rev.*, **114**, 1263–1271.
- Zeng, N., Neelin, J. D., and Chou, C. (1999). The first quasi-equilibrium tropical circulation model – Implementation and simulation. *J. Atmos. Sci.*, **Submitted**.
- Zhang, C. (1993). Large-scale variability of atmospheric deep convection in relation to sea surface temperatures. *J. Climate*, **6**, 1898–1913.
-